

*Digitalization in the World of Work and Individuals in Their Second Half
of Working Life in Germany*

Dissertation

zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades
Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D)
im Fach Sozialwissenschaften

eingereicht am 23.08.2024
verteidigt am 13.03.2025

an der Kultur-, Sozial- und Bildungswissenschaftlichen Fakultät der
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

von Lisa Katharina Kortmann

Prof. Dr. Claudia Becker
Dekanin der Kultur-, Sozial- und
Bildungswissenschaftlichen Fakultät

Prof. Dr. Julia von Blumenthal
Präsidentin der
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Gutachterin / Gutachter:

1. Prof. Dr. Johannes Giesecke
2. Prof. Lena Hipp, PhD

Digitalization in the World of Work and Individuals in Their Second Half of Working Life in Germany

1. Introduction

Digitalization processes in the world of work come along with multiple changes for workers. Processes and structures at work have transformed, as will the skill demands faced by workers. Over the last years, the overall demand for digital skills as well as the variety in skill demands were increasing; at the same time skills became outdated faster due to accelerating innovations (Kubicek, Paškvan, & Korunka, 2015; O'Kane et al., 2020; Wegman et al., 2018). When it comes to digitalization and the labor market to date only little attention has been paid to older workers (Komp-Leukkunen et al., 2022). While younger workers grew up in a digitalizing country and are likely to have gained digital skills during their primary educational phase, older workers are not digital natives. Since older workers' initial educational phase is a longer time ago and technologies are rapidly evolving, their skills may be more likely to become outdated. In addition, it is the group of older workers that is presumed by employers to be less digitally savvy and that is less encouraged to take up digital skills (Van Dalen, Henkens, & Schippers, 2009). Similarly, older workers assess their digital competencies on average lower than younger workers do and are less likely to participate in or to be considered for job-related training (Curtarelli et al., 2017; Czaja et al., 2006; Petery et al., 2020; Posthuma & Campion, 2009; Vasilescu et al., 2020).

Recently, the COVID-19 pandemic was seen as “great accelerator” for digitalization processes, also at the workplace, making the need for a successful adaption to related changes even more relevant (Amankwah-Amoah et al., 2021; Nagel, 2020; OECD, 2020). At the same time, recent demographic trends increasingly pressure the German labor market and the welfare state (Börsch-Supan et al., 2003; Buchholz et al., 2011; Henseke, Hetze, & Tivig, 2009). One influential factor is population ageing and

relatedly the baby boomer generation¹ approaching retirement age. In essence, the share of labor market participants that mainly contribute to the social security system will further shrink while the number of retirees and pensioners will further rise. This trend is the reason why the avoidance of early retirement had become an important objective of recent statutory reform policies, like the stepwise rise of the statutory pension age from 65 to 67 until 2031 or pension deductions in case of early retirement (Bäcker et al., 2023; BMBF, 2021).

While there is a lot of optimism when it comes to digitalization, which is often seen as panacea for recent and upcoming challenges, it is not clear how digitalization processes will affect different aspects of the occupational situation of older workers. Workplace digitalization could become both a curse or a blessing for older workers. Against this briefly outlined background, the following overarching question is addressed in this publication-based dissertation: What are potential implications of digitalization in the world of work for older workers in Germany?

Focusing on selected aspects of working life, the main contributions of this dissertation are the identification of potential negative or beneficial effects emerging from digitalization processes at work for different groups of older workers. Related to that, this dissertation helps to detect potential push factors encouraging early retirement and emerging or aggravating social inequalities among older workers. Overall, this dissertation helps to understand how digitalization impacts older workers. It may create a reference point for the development of political or operational measures that encourage older workers to retire later. Furthermore, it can help to shape measures that aim to make digitalization beneficial for all groups of workers in their everyday working life. Finally, this dissertation provides empirical evidence for an understudied, emerging, and fragmented field of research (Komp-Leukkunen et al., 2022) and may contribute to the development of new theoretical perspectives.

¹ The so called “baby boomer”-generation refers to individuals born in the years after World War II, in years marked by exceptionally strong birth rates. Such baby boom-years can be found in many countries involved in the war, yet there are country differences regarding the specific periods of the baby boom years (Phillipson, 2008). In Germany individuals born between mid-1950s and mid-1960s are part of the baby boomer generation.

Now, that the topic and the motivation for this dissertation has been sketched out very briefly, some relevant background information on the context of this work will be provided in the following sections. In section 2 the existing literature on digitalization in the world of work and older workers is presented and the aims of the dissertation are embedded in the current research. After approaching the concept of digitalization, the often vaguely used term “digitalization” is defined (2.1) and studies on potential effects of digitalization processes in the world of work are introduced (2.2). Next, relevant country background information about the German labor market, welfare system and demography will be provided briefly (2.3). In section 2.4, the relevance and overarching contribution of this publication-based dissertation will be explicated. In section 3 the overarching theoretical approach, the data and the sample of this dissertation will be introduced, before a short summary of the three papers of the dissertation along with a related overview table are provided in section 4. (Please note that the three papers of the publication-based dissertation on digitalization’s implications on employees training participation, subjective job quality and self-perceptions of aging are presented in their full length in the appendix (7.1).) An overarching discussion of the results of this dissertation is presented in section 5. Here, the limitations of the dissertation are discussed (5.1) and its strengths, contribution and relevance are elaborated (5.2.).

2. Literature Review

The dissertation is placed at the intersection of *digitalization in the world of work*, *the working situations of individuals*, and *older workers*. The main interest of this work is to examine, if and how changes due to digitalization at the occupational level are related to selected aspects of older individual’s working lives. In that course, digitalization data aggregated on the occupational level and individual level data of older workers is used. Overall, this dissertation investigates potential mechanisms between digitalization processes in the world of work and the occupational situation of older workers (see fig. 1). To date, research on digitalization and older individual’s working life is still evolving, but it is related to several points in the existing literature. The following overview on the existing literature starts with clarifying the scope and defining the meaning of the often vaguely used term of “digitalization” (2.1). After terminological clarifications, literature is introduced that aims to determine potential

effects of digitalization on the labor market, such as effects on the wage distribution, skill development or employment rates. It is focused on approaches that examine potential effects of digitalization on the labor market at the occupational level and for

Figure 1: Potential Mechanisms Between Digitalization in Occupations and the Situation of Individual Workers.

Note. Own figure.

this purpose break down occupations into its task compositions (2.2.1 & 2.2.2). The value of referring to occupations to investigate individual-level outcomes is made clear in section 2.2.3. In the subsequent section a second approach investigating digitalization in the world of work is introduced: the digital skills approach (2.2.4). The basic idea of the approach is comparable to that of the task-based approach, but it breaks occupations down into skills instead of tasks. Advantages and disadvantages of the task-based and the digital skills approach are pointed out (2.2.4). In the subsequent section, literature on digital divides among individuals in general is introduced and existing inequalities in access and use of digital technologies revealed in literature are elaborated (2.2.5). Since digitalization alters work and relatedly the

tasks executed at work, it comes with increasing demands for digital skills. Therefore, section 2.2.6, focusses on digital skills and discusses the role of workers age in this context. Job-related training is one central strategy of adapting workers' skills to new demands at work. Therefore, in section 2.2.7, literature on job-related training and digitalization is introduced briefly. Lastly some contextual information on the German labor market, welfare system and demographic trends are provided, since this dissertation focusses on Germany (2.3). Based on the literature section and provided contextual information, the relevance of this dissertation is clarified, and research gaps are elaborated (2.4).

2.1. Digitalization - A Definitional Approach and a Brief Historical Outline

In literature, some authors describe digitalization as “disruption” that upheavals social and economic structures in Western societies (Hirsch-Kreinsen & Wienzek, 2019; Trenerry et al., 2021). Also, terms like “Third” and “Fourth Industrial Revolution”² coined by Jeremy Rifkin (2011) and Klaus Schwab (2017), or “Second Machine Age” (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014) are used in connection with the process of digitalization. The terminology reflects the relevance and extent of the transformation processes. Even if the process of digitalization is not a synonym to the abovementioned terms, they integrate digitalization as “main force” (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014, p. 40) shaping an overall transformation process.³ Even authors that are somewhat reluctant to label digitalization a “disruptive process” acknowledge that it induces far-reaching changes in economy and society (Valenduc & Vendramin, 2017). What consensually emerges from these formulations and perspectives is that digitalization is understood as a profound and comprehensive transformation process for societies and economies. And following from this, it becomes clear for research that, on the one hand, it is relevant to understand and disentangle the potential effects of digitalization

² The First Industrial Revolution is located at the end of the 18th century and is characterized in particular by the invention of the steam engine. The Second Industrial Revolution that is characterized by the board use of electrical energy, gas and oil is situated in the end of 19th century. The Third Industrial Revolution is marked by the emergence of information technologies and electronics at the end of the 20th century. And the Fourth Industrial Revolution is located at the 21st century and characterized by interconnectivity and smart automation. An alternate term to circumscribe the innovations in the 21st century, which is just as widespread in Germany is “Industry 4.0”.

³ E.g., globalization – that is closely interlinked with digitalization – is another process considered as part of the process of upheaval.

to counteract negative effects. And on the other hand, the pervasiveness and multifaceted nature of digitalization complicates the understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

But what exactly is meant when we talk about digitalization? Digitalization describes the upcoming and dissemination of new, digital technologies throughout society from the early 1980s onwards. Though, some key technologies for digitalization already have been invented in the post-war years from late 1940s onwards. Among those key technologies the invention of the microprocessor in the late 1960s to early 1970s is often seen as particularly important, and is interpreted even as starting point of the digital transformation (Eurofond, 2018). A microprocessor is often labelled as “brain of the computer”, since it reads, processes, tracks and stores information (Goel, 2010). Its practical value refers to its very small size. Several of today’s digital devices are ran by microprocessors, such as personal computers, smartphones, televisions, washing machines, traffic light controls, military applications, or industrial controllers. However, digitalization gained momentum with the dissemination of digital technologies in everyday and working life from the 1980s onwards, when prices for personal computers and microelectronics were rapidly falling and performance increased.⁴ In addition, the upcoming of the world wide web in 1989 can be seen as further important milestone for the sweeping impact of digitalization. To wrap it all up, digitalization in the world of work can be defined as process of rapid dissemination of digital technologies in the working context. Furthermore, technologies can be described as “digital” if they run on computers or computer-based machines – or to break it down even further – if they contain automated operations than run on algorithms translatable in “0s” and “1s” (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). Algorithms can be thought of as unambiguous sequences of actions with fixed decision rules to perform specific tasks. Overall, digitalization can be seen as one phase of the general process of technological change, nonetheless it should be considered and investigated specifically due to its “disruptive” or “revolutionary” character (Murawski & Bick, 2017). In contrast to earlier phases of technological change, digitalization shows a remarkably wide range of tasks

⁴ This trend can be exemplified by Moore’s law, which is an prominent perception that has been proven true about the fast increase of performance of microchips and the simultaneously falling costs for computers (Moore, 2021).

that can be performed by digital technologies currently or the near future (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014).

Up to now, digitalization has brought several far-reaching changes and innovations to the world of work. Some digital innovations have led to a full automation of some work processes. Other tasks are only supported or complemented by digital technologies. A prominent example on automation due to the introduction of digital technologies is the spread of automated teller machines (ATMs) from the 1970s onwards in the United States of America (Bessen, 2015). While ATMs automated a wide range of the occupational tasks of a bank teller (e.g., cash-handling), it hadn't led to a substitution of bank tellers in the long-term. Rather, bank tellers experienced a profound change in their occupational task profile towards not automatable service tasks (Bessen, 2015).

In general, digitalization in the world of work has induced the integration of personal computers and other digital technologies in many working tasks of today. The impact of the upcoming and broad dissemination of digital technologies is assessed as revolutionary since it comes with major changes throughout society. It offers some new opportunities, such as communication that is temporally and spatially unbounded, rapid information flows, exact and fast execution of complex calculations, collection, storage, and procession of big amounts of data, or the full automation of physical work by industrial robots. Recently, artificial intelligence, cloud solutions and collaborative machines find their way into many workplaces. But digitalization also poses challenges, such as acceleration of information flows and work processes that stresses workers, high demands for and – same time – high decay rates of digital skills, the responsible control of huge data quantities, new opportunities of surveillance at work, technical breakdowns, or ethical issues.

2.2. Effects of Digitalization in the World of Work

Digitalization in the world of work describes great transformation processes, that may result in new or aggravating social inequalities. Hence, it is important to unravel and understand potential effects of digitalization processes. Most prominent in literature on digitalization and social inequalities are studies on polarizing effects in the workforce and studies on job losses due to automation. The literature predominantly uses task profiles of occupations to derive the impact of digitalization from this. The interest of

this literature is mainly on macroeconomic outcomes of digitalization, such as skill-, wage-, or employment-structures. However, occupations are described to constitute “among the most versatile categories of information about a person available in quantitative data” (Christoph, Matthes, & Ebner, 2020, p. 41). This dissertation is interested in potential impacts of digitalization on occupation-related aspects at the individual level. However, literature with macroeconomic focus will be briefly presented in the following sections since it contains relevant aspects and approaches (2.2.1 & 2.2.2). In section 2.2.3, an approach is presented that is closely interlinked with the task-based approach. However, instead of using tasks in occupations to investigate digitalization’s impact, the alternate approach refers to the demand of digital skills that are required for occupations. Existing literature on potential beneficial or detrimental impacts of digitalization at the individual level is presented in section 2.2.5. In the following section (2.2.6) emerging skill demands in course of digitalization are elaborated. Then, two options for older workers to adapt to altered work environments are introduced and discussed, namely training and retirement (2.2.7).

2.2.1. Polarization

Technological innovations are not new and a bunch of literature on its effects on the labor market already exists. However, due to its disruptive character (see chapter 1.2.1) digitalization should be treated and investigated as distinct (but related) phenomenon. In face of increasing wage inequalities in several developed countries from 1980s onwards, empirical interest was sparked in a potential association of digitalization and labor demands, respectively wages. Several studies found evidence for a positive correlation between the use or introduction of new, digital technologies and increasing relative demands for high skilled workers in contrast to lower skilled workers, and relatedly, higher relative wage premiums for high skilled workers (for informative overviews see e.g. Atkinson, 2008; Goldin & Katz, 2008; Katz & Autor, 1999). Other factors also associated with labor demands and wages, such as globalization or wage-setting institutions, have been evidenced to be less influential compared to digitalization (Goldin & Katz, 2008; Goos, Manning, & Salomons, 2009). The significant positive correlation of digitalization with increasing wage inequality was interpreted as evidence for the theory of skill-biased technological change (SBTC) coined by Tinbergen (1975) (Acemoglu, 2002; Acemoglu & Autor, 2011; Goldin & Katz,

2008; Katz & Autor, 1999; Katz & Murphy, 1992). In the theory a race between education and technology is presumed, where technological innovations develop faster than the supply of high skilled labor (Goldin & Katz, 2008). Technological innovations would induce higher relative demands for skilled labor, since new technologies would complement high skilled workers and increase their relative productivity (Violante, 2016). Hence technological change, respectively digitalization, would not affect workers evenly, but manifests more positively in high skilled workers.

However, the explanatory scope of the SBTC model was increasingly challenged, since it lacked to account, for example, for the stabilization of wage inequality – especially between middle and low wage groups – while digitalization was ongoing in the 1990s, for wage dynamics of specific groups of workers, and polarizing labor markets (Card & DiNardo, 2002; Lemieux, 2006). Starting from this puzzle, Autor, Levy and Murnane (2003) developed a “richer version” (Autor, Katz, & Kearney, 2008, p. 301) of the SBTC approach to explain the association of digitalization and the labor market – the task-based approach (TBA)⁵. In the following years the approach was further sharpened by works of Acemoglu and Autor (2011) and Acemoglu and Restrepo (2018). In the TBA the need to focus on the task content of occupations to understand the impact of digitalization on the labor market is emphasized. It is assumed that digitalization enlarges the potential of machines in performing tasks. While some tasks, that follow explicit rules, are assumed to be automatable, other tasks (non-routine tasks) are assumed to be not automatable (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003).⁶ Since digital technologies would substitute routine tasks, but complement non-routine tasks, the demand for human labor performing non-routine tasks is assumed to increase (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003). It should be noted that, in contrast to the SBTC approach, in the TBA the task content of occupations is not interlinked automatically with the skill levels of workers (Autor, 2015; Autor & Dorn, 2013; Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018). Based on the core ideas of the TBA, a body of literature evolved explaining trends of labor market polarization with digitalization (Autor, 2015;

⁵ Other names for the TBA are prevalent in the literature, such as “task-biased technological change” (TBTC) or “routine-biased technological change” (RBTC).

⁶ Autor, Levy and Murnane (2003) distinguish between manual and cognitive routine tasks, such as calculating, repetitive customer service or repetitive assembly, and cognitive and manual non-routine tasks, such as managing, persuading, or truck driving.

Autor & Dorn, 2013; Autor, Katz, & Kearney, 2006, 2008; Dustmann, Ludsteck, & Schönberg, 2009; Goos & Manning, 2007; Goos, Manning, & Salomons, 2009; Spitz-Oener, 2006). Several studies demonstrated that the share of middle-wage employment had diminished relatively to the high or low-wage employment over the last decades (Acemoglu & Autor, 2011; Autor, 2015; Autor & Dorn, 2013; Goos & Manning, 2007; Goos, Manning, & Salomons, 2009). However, country differences in polarization patterns seem to exist, and for some European countries no clear evidence for labor market polarization was found (Antonczyk, Fitzenberger, & Leuschner, 2009; Fernández-Macías, 2012; Fernández-Macías & Hurley, 2017; Oesch & Piccitto, 2019; Oesch & Rodríguez Menés, 2011). One explanation discussed in literature are institutional differences between countries, for example, minimum wages or union representation (Oesch & Rodríguez Menés, 2011). For the German labor market, digitalization seems to be associated with employment polarization at the upper and middle part of the wage distribution, but not for the lower part (Fernández-Macías, 2012; Oesch & Rodríguez Menés, 2011).

Overall, three key messages for this dissertation can be derived from this strand of literature: First, digitalization seems to be associated with changing task contents of occupations. Second, skill demands seem to change, too. Specifically, the demand for higher skills seems to increase. And third, inequalities between different groups of workers may increase in course of digitalization, if not reined in by institutional measures. Hence, for workers themselves these developments in the working context may cause significant changes and challenges that need further investigation.

2.2.2. Job losses

Evolving from literature on labor market polarization, a number of articles on the automation of human labor due to digital technologies came up, providing quantifications of future job-losses due to automation (Bonin, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2015; Dengler & Matthes, 2018; Frey & Osborne, 2017; Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018). However, the idea of job losses due to technological innovations is not new. In early 20th century the economist John Maynard Keynes proliferated the idea of emerging “technological unemployment” due to technological innovations that outperform and substitute for human labor at high rate and on a large scale. Jobs would be automated,

and human labor would become obsolete. However, Keynes understands technological unemployment as “only a temporary phase of maladjustment” (Keynes, 2010 [1930], p. 3) until new uses are found for human labor. Building on the idea of technological unemployment, Frey and Osborne (2017) predicted in a well-recognized study that 47 percent of the employment of the United States of America would be at high risk to be automated in “perhaps a decade or two” (Frey & Osborne, 2017, p. 38) due to digital technologies. In their study Frey and Osborne build on the idea of Autor, Levy and Murnane (2003) that only some of the tasks can be substituted by digital technologies and others not. However, since the substitutability of tasks is not set in stone, but evolves with the potential of new innovations, they question the distinction between “routine cognitive or manual tasks” and “non-routine cognitive or manual tasks” proposed by Autor, Levy and Murnane (2003). Instead, and in alignment with Brynjolfson and McAfee (2011), they follow the idea of “engineering bottlenecks”, that reflect the boundaries of engineering. Based on literature and expert assessments they identify three not-automatable tasks, respectively engineering bottlenecks: 1) perception and manipulation 2) creative intelligence tasks, and 2) social intelligence (Frey & Osborne, 2017). They used O*NET data that contains detailed descriptions of the task content of occupations provided by the U.S. Department of Labor. Nine tasks were identified corresponding with the identified “engineering bottlenecks”, and hence to be not automatable. Next, the authors hand-labelled with the help of experts from the machine learning field a list of 70 occupations as automatable or not. Only if all tasks of an occupation were perceived to be automatable in near future, the occupation was labeled as fully automatable (Frey & Osborne, 2017). The authors extrapolated the assessments about an occupations automatability to a list of 702 occupations by using a Gaussian process classifier. Overall, the authors find especially workers in the transportation, logistics and production sector, as well as office and administrative support workers and workers in the service sector at high risk of job loss due to automation⁷ (Frey & Osborne, 2017). The study has evoked great attention in research as well as in public, and numerous follow-up studies transferred the approach to other

⁷ The authors set thresholds of 30% and 70% to distinguish between low, middle and high risk categories of job loss due to automation (Frey & Osborne, 2017).

countries and labor markets (Bonin, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2015; Pajarinen & Rouvinen, 2014; Pajarinen, Rouvinen, & Ekeland, 2015).

A second generation of automation-literature used a refined methodological approach and other readjustments and found far lower automation risks (Arntz, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2016; Bonin, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2015; Dengler & Matthes, 2018; Manyika et al., 2017; Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018). Basically, the approaches of the follow-up studies differ from Frey and Osborne's occupation-based approach, by focusing on the automatability of tasks in occupations and not on automatability of entire occupations (Arntz, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2016). Other modifications are, for example, the consideration of net employment effects. Meaning that not only potential job losses, but also the creation of new jobs due to digitalization are considered (Arntz, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2016; Dengler & Matthes, 2018; Manyika et al., 2017; Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018). What is consistently found in automation literature, is that social inequalities on the labor market may increase, since high educated, high wage workers seem to suffer the least from automation risks respectively substitution and also other characteristics seem to be unequally associated with digitalization in occupations (Arntz, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2016; Frey & Osborne, 2017; Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018). For comprehensive overviews of the automation literature see for example Apt and Priesack (2017) or Bühner and Hagist (2017).

However, automation literature that tries to quantify effects of digitalization on employment that is based on the assumption that some tasks are substitutable by digital technologies while others are not, has been criticized for some shortcomings (Autor, 2015; Pfeiffer, 2018; Valenduc & Vendramin, 2017). First, digital technologies may or may not substitute occupational tasks. It is not only the technical feasibility that drives the decision to substitute a task or an entire worker by digital technologies, but ethical, political, economic, and social aspects also impact the decision. And even if digital technologies are implemented, this may result in changes in the overall task profile of an occupation and alterations in the need for the worker to adapt to new demands rather than in the substitution of entire jobs or occupations. Indeed, over the last years, extensive task changes within occupations have been identified in literature (Atalay et al., 2020; Bachmann, Cim, & Green, 2019; Spitz-Oener, 2006). In addition,

automation literature is criticized for overestimating the acceptance and pace of adoption of new digital technologies in the broad economy (Valenduc & Vendramin, 2017). This critique is supported by recent findings of Dauth et al. (2021) who suggest that working in robot intensive industries is associated with higher employment stability and higher occupational mobility within the same firm, meaning that workers are not substituted by new technologies, but take over new tasks within their firms at least in Germany. In addition, robot exposure in general has no significant negative effects on total employment, albeit negative effects for single industries, such as the manufacturing sector exist (Dauth et al., 2021).

Even though there is justified criticism on automation literature, it contains valuable points of reference for this dissertation. First, it becomes clear from this body of literature, that digitalization does not affect workers equally. Some occupations are characterized by task-profiles that offer greater potential for integrating digital technologies, other occupations are characterized by task-profiles that offer little potential for the integration of digital technologies. In addition, individuals working in the same occupation share often similar individual characteristics, and such, certain groups of workers, for example, high educated workers, female workers, or part-time workers, may be particularly “exposed” to digitalization at work. Thus, automation literature point to mechanisms that may explain how new social inequalities may emerge or existing inequalities may increase due to digitalization. A second point that can be derived from automation literature, to investigate potential implications of digitalization on older workers, is the basic methodological approach that is used. Taking occupations as the determining factor for the unequal “exposedness” to digitalization at work, breaking them down into tasks to understand what workers actually do at work, and determine what elements of occupations can be influenced by digitalization.

2.2.3. Occupations and Inequalities

Occupation-based measures are commonly used in economic and sociological literature and their multifaceted information content is highly appreciated. Occupational information is not only used in the task-based approach, but also in studies on social stratification, segregation, health, or institutional characteristics (Christoph, Matthes, &

Ebner, 2020). Yet, referring to occupations to explain inequalities between individuals has been criticized for neglecting that different jobs within the same occupation may show a considerable task-variation, too (Autor & Handel, 2013; Avent-Holt et al., 2020; Cassidy, 2017; Christoph, Matthes, & Ebner, 2020). While a detailed look at the individual job level would certainly allow for a more accurate differentiation, an equally well-regarded approach is to differentiate task profiles at the occupational level (Autor & Handel, 2013; Cassidy, 2017; Christoph, Matthes, & Ebner, 2020; Leicht, 2020; Williams & Bol, 2018). Occupations are, by definition, groupings of jobs with a “high degree of similarity” (ILO, 2012, p. 11) regarding the main tasks and duties, and following from that regarding skill requirements at work. In line with that, studies found that occupations do show explanatory power for individual-level differences (Autor & Handel, 2013; Mouw & Kalleberg, 2010; Williams & Bol, 2018). In addition, using the occupational level to investigate individual outcomes has the advantage, that information about individuals’ occupations is included in many existing, high-quality data sets. This information can be easily enriched by matching additional information that is linked to specific occupations like information on the digitalization level. In addition, several studies on digitalization take only aspects of digitalization into account, such as internet use at work or robot density. While in the literature a clear-cut definition of digitalization is still missing (see section 2.1), debates on how to measure digitalization are ongoing. This lack of clarity, what digitalization at work actually is, may pose a problem for gathering information about the extent of digitalization at the individuals’ jobs with survey methodology. Respondents may have a different understanding of what digitalization means, which could also be manifested in their answers. Following from this, asking individuals directly to report the extend of digitalization in their jobs, it can be assumed that inconsistencies in response behavior may occur resulting in fuzzy data. Also, in this regard it is advantageous to use digitalization data determined over task profiles on occupational level.

2.2.4. Digital Skill Demands in Occupations

Recently, an increasing number of literature addresses the effects of digitalization in the world of work the by using data from online job advertisements (Acemoglu et al., 2022; Azar et al., 2020; Cedefop, 2019, 2021a; Deming & Noray, 2020; O’Kane et al., 2020; OECD, 2022c). The methodological approach determining the average demand

for digital skills in occupations is gaining popularity and is labelled the “digital skills approach (DSA)” hereafter (Cammeraat & Squicciarini, 2021; O’Kane et al., 2020; OECD, 2017, 2022c). In contrast to the task-based approach (TBA) used in the automation-literature, in the DSA the level of digitalization in occupations is determined over digital skills demanded in occupations. Hence the DSA reflects de facto demands for digital skills in occupations. While the TBA assumes that some tasks (routine tasks) are substitutable by digital technologies and others not (non-routine tasks), the DSA assumes that some tasks require digital skills and others not. Hence, the focus pivots further to the workers themselves in the DSA. The approach assumes that digital technologies usually complement individuals at work and are integrated in their work and do not necessarily substitute or solely co-exist with the individual at work. The DSA is determined by the average demand for digital skills in occupations based on data from online job advertisements. Like the TBA, the DSA operates on the occupational level and the assignment of categories relies on experts’ assessments. Using data from online job advertisements has the advantage, that it is up to date and provides fine grained information on skill demands in jobs. Also new, recently emerged skill demands are captured in the DSA. Therewith, the DSA contrasts with approaches based on survey methodology. Survey data on tasks or skills at work consist of self-reported information of the workers themselves. Hence, this kind of data will be biased by individual perspectives and relevance systems. In addition, if surveys use closed items, only a limited list of answer categories can be provided. It follows that granularity of such data is limited. Moreover, job-ads data reflects the employers needs for (digital) skills and is therewith slightly prospective in nature. The job-ads data is generated on an ongoing basis and is not subject to survey waves with elaborate preparation work. So, while the data from job-ads do not accurately reflect the skills currently needed to perform tasks in an occupation, they do reflect which skills are desired. In addition, job-ads data is up-to-date and can therefore keep up with the rapid pace of digitalization.

2.2.5. Digital Divides

While the importance and pervasiveness of digital technologies is increasing, the access, usage frequency and competences to use digital technologies differ between individuals. In the literature the perceived gaps in access and usage of digital skills between different groups of individuals are often labelled as “first” and “second level

digital divide” (Attewell, 2001; Compaine, 2001; Friemel, 2016; Hargittai, 2002). Predictors for such digital divides are, among other, education, gender, income, and age (Aissaoui, 2021; Scheerder, van Deursen, & van Dijk, 2017; Vasilescu et al., 2020), but also the professional context is associated with the use of digital technologies. Gainful employment, especially office jobs, appearing to have favorable effects on the use of digital technologies (Initiative D21, 2021). The “grey digital divide” refers to age-related differences in digital technology access, skills, and outcomes (Millward, 2003; Morris & Brading, 2007; Morris, Goodman, & Brading, 2007). Like in many other countries, also for Germany a grey digital divide regarding internet access and usage has been found, with older individuals showing a lower likelihood and frequency of use than younger individuals (Hunsaker & Hargittai, 2018; Huxhold, Hees, & Webster, 2020; Initiative D21, 2021). However, there is evidence that the digital divide is narrowing over the years, with older age groups showing stronger increases in the likelihood of having access to and using the internet compared to younger age groups (Huxhold, Hees, & Webster, 2020; Kortmann et al., 2022). Regarding digital skills, age differences are evidenced, too, with older individuals being less likely to hold digital skills (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2011; Vasilescu et al., 2020).⁸ Notably, such age differences in digital skills to accomplish tasks are found to be more pronounced for digital skill use in private life than in the working context (Vasilescu et al., 2020).

2.2.6. Skill Demands and Digitalization

When it comes to the world of work, literature on skill demands and digitalization shows that the overall demand for digital skills had increased over the last years and, nowadays, basic digital skills are demanded in nearly every occupation (Curtarelli et al., 2017; O’Kane et al., 2020; OECD, 2022c). Recently, in the course of the COVID-19 pandemic and the related premise of social distancing large parts of private and working life have moved to the digital realm, emphasizing even more the relevance of digital competencies (Piroșcă et al., 2021). However, a considerable proportion of

⁸ While van Deursen and van Dijk (2011) found significant negative associations with “formal” and “operational” digital skills, related with the proper usage and running of digital devices, no significant associations were found for “information” and “strategic” digital skills, referring to an individual’s ability to properly find and process information derived from digital mediums or use digital devices to reach a certain goal.

workers show gaps in digital skills to effectively use digital technologies at work (Curtarelli et al., 2017; OECD, 2016). Age seems to be negatively associated with digital skills in the working context, with older workers being less likely to hold digital skills and less confident about their digital competences (Curtarelli et al., 2017; Vasilescu et al., 2020). A lack in digital skills or a lack of confidence to use digital skills at work can hinder older individuals from reaping its benefits. Such, digital skill use at work is associated with positive wage or productivity returns (de Koning & Gelderblom, 2006; Draca, Sadun, & Van Reenen, 2007; Falck, Heimisch-Roecker, & Wiederhold, 2021; Lee, Kwak, & Song, 2022). While there seems to be little doubt that digital skills are increasingly important in private life and on the labor market, to date nonetheless no clear-cut definition of digital skills exists. In literature different terminologies are used such as digital competencies, digital literacy, digital skills, e-skills. The meaning of these different terms is only partly overlapping, and sometimes clear distinctions are made (Oberländer, Beinicke, & Bipp, 2020; Ulfert-Blank & Schmidt, 2022). However, at this point, the terminological discourse will not be addressed in greater detail. In this dissertation the term “digital skills” describes the capability of individuals to use and manipulate digital technologies for different purposes and to solve or prevent problems related to digital technology use. The spectrum of digital skills is nearly infinite and evolving, and digital skills show great differences in terms of proficiency levels required. For example, while the ability to search information on the internet requires rather basic proficiency, the writing of program code requires high proficiency. Recently, advanced digital skills, such as programming, data analysis and processing, but also social media skills are in high demand in OECD countries (OECD, 2022c). At the same time, the relevance of so called soft-skills, like emotional intelligence, cognitive flexibility, creativity, problem solving competence or negotiation skills increased over the last years on the labor market (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003; Deming, 2017; OECD, 2016, 2019b; Sousa & Wilks, 2018). This trend fits with the routinization hypothesis introduced above (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003): Since routine tasks can be substituted by digital technologies, occupational task profiles change or may become

more service oriented and require more social skills.⁹ Hence, it is important for workers not only to possess digital skills, but to hold the right skill mix (OECD, 2019b).

2.2.7. Adaption to Altered Work Environments: Job-related Training and Retirement
Overall, the evolving nature of task and skill demands in occupations leads to altered work situations for older individuals. One way to adapt workers' skills to altered work environments in times of digitalization is training. In this course, the concept of lifelong learning has gained increasingly attention over the last years. The concept refers to "all forms of skill and competency development over the lifecycle" (OECD, 2021b) and, hence, also incorporated the learning activity of workers during their career. In 1996 the European Union proclaimed the "European Year of Lifelong Learning", aiming to create awareness and more action for learning and training over the life course in the member states. Similarly, the OECD developed a "Skills Strategy" in order to support countries in building effective skill systems that promote the development of skills over the life course of individuals and contribute to an effective use of skills at work (OECD, 2019c). In Germany, the "National Skills Strategy (dt.: Nationale Weiterbildungsstrategie)" was launched in order to promote lifelong learning in general and, in view of large labor market transformations due to digitalization, to build digital skills in particular (BMBF, 2021). Generally, there is a strong consensus on the centrality of training in order to keep worker's skills up-to-date and in alignment with new demands emerging in the course of digitalization (BMBF, 2021; Goldin & Katz, 2008; OECD, 2019a, 2021a, 2021b; Oesch, 2013). Training is crucial in order to avoid skill mismatches and maintain the productivity and employability of workers (Brunello & Wruuck, 2021; Hansson, 2008). Over the last years, job-related training was increasing (Becker, 2019; BMBF, 2021; Grund & Martin, 2012). Moreover, some studies and also findings from this dissertation (see chapter 7.I) provide evidence for a positive association of workplace digitalization and training (Gashi, Pugh, & Adnett, 2010; Kortmann, Stuth, & Simonson, 2022; Lukowski, Baum, & Mohr, 2021; Wotschack, 2020). According to data from the Survey of Adult Skills (PIAAC), in the

⁹ Coming back to the illustrative example of the bank teller, that was suspected to become substituted by automated teller machines: Instead of becoming obsolete, the occupation of bank tellers changed towards a highly service-oriented occupation. Mathematic and accountancy became less important skills for bank tellers, but a high customer orientation and communication skills became focal (Bessen, 2015).

OECD on average only two in five individuals aged 25 to 65 reported that they participated in at least one job-related training or other learning format (39.7 %) (OECD, 2021b). In Germany, the average training participation was considerably higher (47.3 %), but in comparison to those countries with the highest average participation rates (Norway: 57.76 %; Denmark 56.7 %; New Zealand 56,5 %) there is still much room for improvement (OECD, 2021b).

In general, training participation seems to be beneficial for workers, as a large body of literature finds positive associations with workers' wages, job security and productivity (Albert, García-Serrano, & Hernanz, 2010; Brunello, Garibaldi, & Wasmer, 2007; Büchel & Pannenberg, 2004; Dieckhoff, 2007; Hansson, 2008; Wolter & Schiener, 2009). However, several studies also emphasize, that positive training outcomes may be biased by endogeneity problems and only exist for some groups of workers, for example, highly educated workers (Ehlert, 2017; Hansson, 2008; Icardi, 2021; Vignoles, Galindo-Rueda, & Feinstein, 2004; Wolter & Schiener, 2009). Those studies note that it is difficult to isolate training participation from other, related factors. For example, some workers may show a higher career orientation and motivation. These factors, hardly observable for the researcher but known by the employer, are likely to co-occur with training participation and to be associated with higher wages (Vignoles, Galindo-Rueda, & Feinstein, 2004). In a thorough study considering heterogeneity in wage growths before training participation Pischke (2001) does not find evidence for immediate positive wage effects of training financed by the employer in Germany. However, the author finds workers with higher earnings growths to be more likely to participate in trainings (Pischke, 2001). Career orientation or motivation of the worker were not considered in the study.

While training represents a strategy for adapting skills in order to cope with changes in the work environment due to digitalization, it is also conceivable that older workers may rather choose to leave the labor market. They may be reluctant to adapt to new demands at work or are confronted to a discriminatory work environment. In line with this expectation, Lee and colleagues found lacking digital skills and age discrimination to be most prominent barriers for older individuals to return to work after unemployment (Lee, Czaja, & Sharit, 2008). Yet, studies on digitalization and older workers' labor

market retention respectively retirement decisions are inconclusive (Ahituv & Zeira, 2011; Burlon & Vilalta-Bufí, 2016). In many studies two opposing ways are discussed by which digitalization may affect retirement decisions of workers (Ahituv & Zeira, 2011; Burlon & Vilalta-Bufí, 2016). On the one side, digitalization may stimulate wage increases that encourage workers' retention on the labor market. This positive association of digitalization and retention has been shown empirically for workers that are exposed to high extents of digitalization (Burlon & Vilalta-Bufí, 2016). On the other hand, digitalization is assumed to lead to the erosion of workers' skills, which may encourage workers to retire early. This pattern has been found in workers with low levels of exposure to digitalization (Burlon & Vilalta-Bufí, 2016). Moreover, and in line with the hypotheses of wages and erosion, opportunities for training seem to positively impact on the association of digitalization and retention in the labor market (Bartel & Sicherman, 1993; Messe, Moreno-Galbis, & Wolff, 2014; Xie et al., 2023). Here, training may counteract the erosion of workers' skills due to digitalization. In addition, studies emphasize the importance of taking into account factors like eligibility to wage replacement benefits (Yashiro et al., 2021), work-related needs, or the perceived usefulness of technologies at work (Xie et al., 2023). Overall, the association of digitalization and retirement/retention seems to be not clear cut.

2.3. Country Focus: Germany

The country focus of the three papers of this dissertation lies on Germany. Therefore, in the following section some key characteristics of the German labor market and demographic trends in Germany are sketched out. The statistics presented in the following section are based on international, public data bases, such as World Bank data or EUROSTAT data. For each presented indicator, data for the most recent year available is presented; if referring to trends, data from the most recent year available and data from the preceding five years are presented.

2.3.1. Labor market

Germany is ranked as the largest economy in Europe and among the largest economies worldwide. It's Gross Domestic Product is about 5.32 trillion US dollar¹⁰ in

¹⁰ Gross domestic based on product purchasing power parity. The GDP (PPP) depicts a country's economic growth and standard of living and suits for country comparisons. The GDP is reported in US dollar but considers the costs of local goods, services and a country's inflation rate.

2022 and the German population counts about 83.36 millions of people (International Monetary Fund, 2022). The German labor market is characterized by strong unions and employee protection laws as well as an extensive vocational training system. Also striking is the great importance of small and medium-sized enterprises, which provide work for a large portion of the German workforce. According to the varieties of capitalism approach, Germany is classified as coordinated market economy (CEM), since the market and interactions between economic actors are often regulated by formal institutions (Soskice & Hall, 2001). In addition, collective bargaining agreements, which are negotiated by unions and employer's associations and which transparently regulate working conditions at the regional or industry level, are very common in Germany. Market relations in CEMs, such as Germany, are rather long-term and cooperative and hence favor the formation of skills that are highly specialized and related to a specific company or work process (Estevez-Abe, Iversen, & Soskice, 2001). Altogether, this context is conducive for incremental innovations¹¹ and highly developed goods (Ebner, 2010). For workers the CEM context could mean that they are relatively well protected against negative impacts of digitalization at work. At least, if working in the primary labor market, where worker protection is high and working conditions are regulated by collective agreements.

When it comes to digitalization in the world of work, there are two pictures: First, on the one side, Germany is one of the leading countries when it comes to the implementation of industrial robots (Dauth et al., 2021; International Federation of Robotics, 2016). But on the other side, Germany ranks mediocre in comparison to other European countries according to the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) of the European Union (European Commission, 2022). According to DESI, the integration of digital technology in business activities, such as cloud solutions or e-commerce, as well as the digitalization of the public services are still underdeveloped,

¹¹ While radical innovations can be understood as the development of completely new products probably including disruptive or radical ideas, incremental innovations refer to the development of improved solutions for existing products (Acemoglu, Akcigit, & Celik, 2022).

even though Germany had made improvements in recent years (European Commission, 2022).

Overall, the results of this dissertation can only be transferred to other countries with great caution. In addition to the characteristics of the German labor market and the German economy highlighted above, studies point out that there are also differences between countries at the level of occupations (Tijdens, De Ruijter, & De Ruijter, 2014). This is why this dissertation uses digitalization data that is determined for the German labor market in specific. Beyond that, country specific cultures, norms, and legal regulations shape digitalization processes in the world of work as well as the working situation of individuals.

2.3.2. Demography

The German population is comparatively old. According to recent statistics, the median age is about 44.8 years (2022) and hence it is one of the highest worldwide (UNDESA, 2022a). An increasing life expectancy (from 80.0 years in 2010 to 80.9 years in 2020¹²) accompanied by a low fertility rate (1.5 births per women in 2020¹³) drives population aging in Germany. These factors cannot be offset by a positive net migration rate (1.78 migrants per 1,000 individuals in 2022), and therefore, the German population is decreasing (-0.11 % in 2022) while the proportion of older people is increasing: from 21.2 percent of the total population aged 65 years or older in 2015 to 22.9 percent in 2020 (UNDESA, 2022b).

This aging trend in the German population also affects the labor market. If countermeasures are not taken, such as increasing the labor force participation rate¹⁴ of older workers, labor force projections predict that until 2030 the German labor force will shrink remarkably (Ehing & Moog, 2013). Indeed, Germany experienced increasing employment rates over the last years (see fig. 2 & 3). This trend can at least partly be attributed to the increasing employment participation of older individuals. For individuals aged 15- to 64-years the employment rates rose from 70.3 percent of the

¹² Indicator: Life expectancy at birth, total (years) (The World Bank, 2022b).

¹³ Indicator: Fertility rate, total (births per woman) (The World Bank, 2022a).

¹⁴ The labor force participation rate indicates a country's active workforce and is determined by the share of individuals aged 15 years and above that are working or actively looking for work in the total working-age population of a country (ILO, 2016).

working age population in 2010 to 76.2 percent in 2020, for individuals aged 55- to 64-years employment rates increased from 57.0 percent of the working age population from the same subgroup in 2010 to 71.8 percent in 2020 (OECD, 2022a) (see fig. 2 & 3). This trend of particularly pronounced increasing employment rates among older age groups is in line with average developments in the European Union and the OECD (OECD, 2022a).

Figure 2: Employment Rate, 15-to-64-Year Old's.

Note. Own figure based on OECD (2022a).

Figure 3: Employment Rate, 55-to-64-Year Old's.

Note. Own figure based on OECD (2022a).

Nonetheless, demographic trends are expected to cause grave financing problems in pension, health and long-term care systems (Harper, 2014). Particularly for Germany that has a pay-as-you-go financed¹⁵ statutory pension scheme with defined benefits, population aging represents a severe challenge (Artige, Cavenaile, & Pestieau, 2014; Honekamp, 2007). While the share of beneficiaries in the German welfare system is expected to rise further, the share of contributors is expected to shrink. Over the last years, the demographic trend caused a dramatic increase of the old-age dependency ratio¹⁶ in Germany. The ratio increased from 34.4 percent in 2010 up to 36.5 percent

¹⁵ The pay-as-you-go statutory pension scheme relies on an intergenerational contract: pension benefits are covered by contributions of current taxpayers. Civil servants or self-employed are regularly not part of this public retirement insurance but rely on a separate pension system or are self-insured.

¹⁶ The old-age dependency ratio is defined as “the number of individuals aged 65 and over per 100 people of working age defined as those at ages 20 to 64” (OECD, 2022b).

in 2020 indicating that one person in retirement age faces approximately three persons of working age (OECD, 2022b) (see fig. 4).

Projections predict that in 2030 it will be only two individuals in working age for every one individual of retirement age (ratio: about 47 percent in 2030) (OECD, 2022b). This places Germany clearly above the EU28 and OECD average (OECD, 2022b) (see fig. 4). On the labor market the outlined demographic trend further aggravates the shortages for skilled labor. In some occupations, industries or regions these shortages are particularly apparent, such as in the care sector or regions in East Germany (Bundesagentur für Arbeit Statistik/Arbeitsmarktberichterstattung, 2022). These intensifying bottlenecks can pose serious problems for the German economy and society.

Figure 4: Old-age Dependency Ratio (in %).

Note. Own figure based on OECD (2022b).

2.4. Relevance and Gap

Digitalization processes in the world of work come along with changing task profiles of occupations and changing skill demands. While understanding potential effects of digitalization on older workers is crucial, research on that topic is still scarce and well-founded theoretical concepts or frameworks are lacking (Komp-Leukkunen et al., 2022; Sheng et al., 2022; Trenerry et al., 2021).

In accordance with Trenerry et al. (2021), taking into account the perspective of workers is a central aspect to reach effective digital transformation in organizations. They name workers to be “a crucial part of the digital transformation process’s success” and emphasize that “understanding their perceptions and attitudes toward technological change is important, alongside other strategies to enhance their digital capabilities” (Trenerry et al., 2021, p. 17). Based on an extensive review of recent literature they elaborated a multilevel framework defining key factors for digital

transformation processes. Next to factors on the group and organizational level, they point out the importance of five factors on the individual level: (1) technology acceptance and adoption of workers, (2) perceptions and attitudes, (3) skills and training, (4) workplace resilience and adaptability, and (5) work-related stress and wellbeing. This dissertation contributes empirical findings on individual level factors, namely training, perceived stress and job satisfaction, as well as perceptions on age and aging in the context of workplace digitalization. In that course, this dissertation helps to further understand mechanisms of effective digital transformation processes in organizations.

While demands in occupations have been changing all along, digitalization is characterized by the broad scope and high speed at which new technologies develop and are spread. To keep employees' occupational skills up-to-date and to cope with challenges of adapting to the rapidly changing world of work, further training is broadly considered as a key measure (BMAS & BMBF, 2019; BMBF, 2021; Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018; OECD, 2016, 2019c; Vasilescu et al., 2020). In the National Skills Strategy – implemented in Germany in 2019 – it is a declared goal to strengthen digital training for those in employment (BMAS & BMBF, 2019). Training is understood as an “investment in social participation and equal opportunities” for workers (BMAS & BMBF, 2019). Indeed, literature provides evidence that training participation can prevent workers from reduced productivity or employability due to digitalization and can positively impact on retention decisions (Bartel & Sicherman, 1993; Cedefop, 2018; Lee, Kwak, & Song, 2022; Xie et al., 2023). In addition, workers using (advanced) digital skills at work are evidenced to gain higher wages (Acemoglu et al., 2022; Alekseeva et al., 2021; OECD, 2015; Sostero & Tolan, 2022). When it comes to older workers, training participation is a particularly important topic in times of digitalizing workplaces. Older workers are no digital natives and have not encountered digital issues during their initial educational phase. In addition, in the context of demographic trends, a larger proportion of the workforce will consist of older workers. At the same time, the working population will be of particular importance in view of the increasing proportion of people receiving pensions or other welfare benefits. Maintaining and enabling the employability and a good job-fit for older workers by training is therefore an important goal. To prevent the emergence or aggravation of

social inequalities on the labor market, participation in job-related training needs to be accessible for all workers at a low threshold. Training offers should be oriented at training demands and be organized in accordance with the target groups. To date, little is known about digitalization in the world of work and training behavior of older workers.

While job-related training represents a strategy of how workers can adapt to or shape changes at work in course of digitalization, this dissertation is also interested in how workers assess and perceive their occupational situation in times of digitalization. If the occupational situation changed due to digitalization, workers' job satisfaction may be affected as well. While digitalization processes at work could improve flexibility, by facilitating communication or other work processes, substitute for monotonous routine work or alleviate from physically demanding work. On the other side, digitalization may lead to an acceleration of working processes and relatedly to higher levels of stress at work. If workers face poor job quality, they show lower productivity and are more inclined to retire early (Royuela & Suriñach, 2013; Siegrist et al., 2006). The link between digitalization at work and perceived job quality must therefore be monitored to be effective in counteracting negative effects of digitalization.

It is not only important to investigate how workers assess their occupational situation in view of the changes brought about by digitalization, but also whether and how their self-images are affected. Individual's self-perceptions are impacted by contextual factors, such as the working context (Bandura, 1986). Per day, individuals spend a large part of their time at work. Therefore, the working context can be assumed to substantially impact on workers' self-perceptions. When it comes to older individuals at work in the context of digitalization there are numerous negative stereotypes (Bal et al., 2011; Posthuma & Campion, 2009). For example, older workers are perceived to be unwilling or unable to learn new things, or to be resistant to changes and not open for new technologies (Petery et al., 2020; Posthuma & Campion, 2009). Embodied age stereotypes impact on individuals self-views (Levy, 2009). Negative views on individual's own age and aging are related with work-related outcomes, such as early retirement intentions or lower work engagement, but also with outcomes concerning the own constitution, such as detrimental effects on individual's health or cognitive functioning (Tully-Wilson et al., 2021; Weber, Angerer, & Müller, 2019). As outlined

above, in view of demographic trends, it is sought to retain older workers on the labor market. Related to that, it is crucial to understand the effects of digitalization on older workers and to shed light on detrimental effects for some groups within the workforce. Therefore, the question is, how older workers' self-perceptions of aging are affected in digitalizing workplaces and whether adverse effects are to be expected for some groups of older workers.

Overall, this dissertation contributes to gain a better understanding of implications of digitalization processes in the world of work on the group of older workers. The literature field on digitalization in the world of work is still evolving, albeit heavily expanding over the last years. This refers to the thematic exploration of the field, but also to the operationalization of digitalization and the acquisition of reliable data, as well as theory development. This dissertation contributes to the genesis and enhancement of knowledge on that topic. It helps to further understand potential implications of workplace digitalization on different aspects of the occupational situation of older workers. In general, it contributes to the questions of how older workers fare in context of digitalization and which groups of older workers might be affected negatively by digitalization. Thus, the dissertation offers a well-founded starting point for political measures or human resource management programs that aim at accompanying digitalization processes and steering them in a productive direction for all groups of workers. In addition, this dissertation can help to advance the theorization of the field.

3. Design of the Dissertation

The overarching research design of the publication-based dissertation includes several commonalities in the conceptualization of each paper that should be introduced in the following. In addition to the fact that the three papers share the same objective of contributing to answering the overarching research question (What are potential positive/negative implications of digitalization in the world of work for older workers in Germany?), there is a joint overarching theoretical and methodological umbrella, which leads to the fact that the analyses of all three papers show similarities regarding the following points:

- the theoretical approach

- the data that is used
- the study samples
- and the variables considered in the analyses

3.1. The Theoretical Approach

While sound theoretical approaches in the field of digitalization and older workers are still lacking (Komp-Leukkunen et al., 2022), this dissertation is guided by two theoretical approaches. The first general theoretical approach, that all three papers are based on, is the task-based approach (TBA) coined by Autor and colleagues (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003). As already outlined in the literature section (chapter 2.2.), the general idea of the TBA is to view digitalization in respect of single tasks. Digital devices and applications are programmed algorithms that are designed to implement a specific task in an automated manner. And while some tasks can be automated by digital technologies, others are not automatable. In occupations, the working individual performs a set of different tasks that is typical for the related occupation. And since different occupations show different task profiles, occupations differ in the potential for the implementation of digital technologies. While a task can be understood as a piece of work that a worker has to do and that produces an output, a skill describes a worker's capability to run a task (Acemoglu & Autor, 2011). The three papers of this dissertation integrate the TBA's idea of breaking down occupations into its tasks or skill demands and deriving the degree of digitalization of an occupation from this.

Moreover, the different aspects of older workers' occupational situation that are addressed in the three papers of this dissertation, represent important determinants in Kooij and colleagues' process model of successful aging. The approach builds on the life course perspective and the person-environment fit theory (Caplan & Van Harrison, 1993) and relates them to the idea of successful aging in the working context. In Kooij et al.'s (2020) process model successful aging is defined as workers intention to continue working (Kooij et al., 2020). The fit between a worker and his/her working situation is changing and evolving over time, since individuals' resources, priorities and perceptions are dynamic such as work environments. The maintenance of a good fit between a worker and his or her work environment is seen as central for successful aging at work (Kooij et al., 2020). In this dissertation it is assumed, that digitalization

comes with changes in the work context of individuals. Hence, the person-environment fit is assumed to be impaired. In Kooij et al.'s (2020) process model, training represents an adaption strategy of individuals to altered work environments. Moreover, a good person-environment fit is established, when a worker is satisfied with his or her job and is not burdened. A positive experience of one's own age and aging may result from successful maintenance or adaption of one's person-environment fit.

3.2. The Data

In all three papers of this dissertation data from the German Aging Survey (DEAS) is used. The DEAS is a large-scale cross sectional and longitudinal survey on the living situation and attitudes of individuals in their second half of life, meaning in the age of 40 years and older (Klaus et al., 2017). The survey is representative for the German community-dwelling population aged 40 to 85 years. It is funded by the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth (BMFSFJ). The responsibility of the DEAS lies at the German Centre of Gerontology (DZA); interviews are conducted by the Institute for Applied Social Sciences (infas). Regularly, a new cross-sectional baseline sample that is stratified for age, gender and residency is drawn every six years from registration data. If participants of the baseline sample give their consent, they participate in the panel survey that is regularly conducted every three years. The survey consists of a computer-assisted personal interview (CAPI) at the participants' homes and is followed by a digital or paper-based questionnaire for self-completion. The first baseline survey was conducted in 1996, followed by survey waves in 2002, 2008 and 2014. In 2011 and 2017 panel surveys were conducted. Due to the COVID-19-pandemic the regular survey design was interrupted and the planned baseline survey for 2020 could not take place. Therefore, a computer-assisted telephone survey (CATI) with panel participants was conducted in 2020/21. In the papers of this dissertation data from the survey waves 2014 and 2017 are used. When needed, specific respondent information was obtained from previous waves (2011, 2008, 2002, 1996). The DEAS provides a wealth of information on the living situation of individuals in their second half of life, as well as on their attitudes and desires.¹⁷ Among other

¹⁷ For example, the DEAS contains information on socio-demographic variables (e.g., gender, health, education), household composition (e.g., living with partner, number of children), or self-perceptions of aging.

thematic fields, the working situation of respondents is surveyed in detail and information on individuals' occupation is provided.¹⁸ Therefore, the DEAS offers high-quality and suitable micro-data for this dissertation focusing on training behavior, subjective job quality, and self-perceptions of aging of older workers in Germany. Other high-quality data sets, such as the BIBB/BAuA Employment Survey (ETB) or the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP), were also inspected to determine whether they could be used as a data source for this dissertation.

While the ETB offers detailed information on individuals' working life, such as insights into individuals' job tasks, requirements, or further trainings, it lacks information on one central variable of this dissertation: self-perceptions of aging. In addition, the survey is conducted as repeated cross-sectional study every six years only, which comes with two additional shortcomings for the study goals of this dissertation. First, due to the data structure of the EPS, only cross-sectional or trend analyses can be conducted, with no opportunity to track trajectories within or between individuals. And second, six years is a rather broad time span to investigate potential effects of digitalization on individuals. The SOEP constitutes other high-quality survey data that allows to investigate associations between the working context and individuals' behavior. However, SOEP data does not provide information on different domains of self-perceptions of ageing.

Since the DEAS does not contain any data on digitalization in occupations, corresponding data was taken from external data sources and matched over occupational information to DEAS data. Hence, the strengths of a high-quality data set with detailed information on individual work and life situations as well as attitudes and desires are combined with up-to-date digitalization data from different sources. For the studies on training behavior and self-perceptions of aging digitalization data from Burning Glass Technologies and Bertelsmann are used (O'Kane et al., 2020). The data provides information on the digitalization level of occupations and the relative increase in this level over time. Importantly, in this data the level of digitalization refers to the

¹⁸ For example, the DEAS provides information on individuals' occupation, the work context (e.g., company size, leading position, sector), working conditions (e.g., income, working hours), professional experience, training behavior, or job satisfaction.

extent that digital skills are demanded in recent job advertisements of occupations. The data is based on job advertisements scraped from online job boards and other online job markets in Germany. The informative value about the actual labor market in Germany is assessed as good and has been tested by benchmarking the potentially selective and non-random job advertisement data against official employment data from EUROSTAT (O'Kane et al., 2020). However, while job advertisement data and EUROSTAT data on the employment distribution in Germany are significantly correlated, the comparisons obviate slight deviations. The observed differences are explained by the prospective character of the job advertisements data that does not depict the current employment distribution on the labor market, but vacancies to be filled (O'Kane et al., 2020). Over the last years, such big data approaches based on job postings are increasingly used in labor market research (Acemoglu et al., 2022; Carnevale, Jayasundera, & Repnikov, 2014; Cedefop, 2019, 2021b; Cedefop et al., 2021; O'Kane et al., 2020). The advantage of this kind of data is the high actuality and the possibility to uniformly collect fine grained information on skill demands and other aspects without defining broad demand categories prior to data collection (Cedefop et al., 2021).

For the study on subjective job satisfaction, digitalization data provided by the Institute for Employment Research (IAB) was used (Dengler & Matthes, 2018; Dengler, Matthes, & Paulus, 2014). This data is based on task descriptions for occupations provided by the expert data base BERUFENET from the Federal Employment Agency and is used to determine the substitution potential of occupations by digital technologies. As sketched out in chapter 2.2.2, the digitalization data determined by Dengler and Matthes (2018) relies on experts' assessments on the automatability respectively substitutability of tasks. However, in line with critique on automation literature, it is assumed that routine intensive occupations will not be substituted by new technologies but that workers in such occupations will face changes in the occupational task profiles. While digitalization data from Bertelsmann and Burning Glass Technologies points to the need for digital skill demands in occupations, digitalization data from the Institute for Employment Research is interpreted as indicating the potential for changes in occupations' task profiles due to digitalization.

3.3. The Sample

Older workers. All papers of this dissertation use a sample of older individuals living in Germany and actively participating in the labor force. The term “older workers” is used to refer to the age group of 40- to 65-year-old workers. This specification corresponds with a definition of older workers coined by an OECD paper and the “Age Discrimination in Employment Act” of the United Nations in 1967 (ADEA; 29 U.S.C. § 621 to 29 U.S.C. § 634) (Belbin, 1967). Yet, in literature there is a lack of uniformity about the age-range at that a worker is considered as “old worker”. An alternate and newer specification coined by the OECD that is common in recent literature considers individuals aged 50 and older to be older workers (OECD, 2006). However, this dissertation builds on the broader OECD definition and refers to individuals aged 40 to 65 years when speaking of “older workers”. Using this broader definition allows for a more inclusive approach that considers a wider range of individuals who may be affected by digitalization and aging in the workplace. It should be noted that in contrast to both OECD definitions the upper cut at the age range was made at the regular statutory pension age of 65¹⁹ in this dissertation.

Employees or Workers. The sample composition is similar but differs in some respects between the three papers of this dissertation. In the studies focusing on training behavior and job quality the sample comprises older employees only, the study focusing on self-perceptions of aging comprises older workers in general (including the self-employed). These differences in the samples are reasonable, since when it comes to job-related training behavior or job quality it probably makes a big difference if an individual is in an employment relationship and hence bound by instructions to an employer, or not. Or if an individual works together with colleagues or if he or she is self-employed. For the self-employed, it can be assumed that training participation is their own responsibility. Similarly, the subjective job quality of self-employed probably depends on other factors than that of employees. They have a certain degree of control over their working conditions and enjoy a different scope for shaping them. In the study

¹⁹ In course of a pension reform from 2007 the statutory pension age in Germany is increasing since 2012 gradually from 65 years to 67 years (§ 7a SGB II). However, for the individuals from birth cohorts considered in the analyses of this dissertation the statutory pension age still was 65 years (and in some cases a few month).

on self-perceptions of aging in times of digitalization in the world of work, the sample comprises workers in total. Of course, there may be significant differences between employees and the self-employed here as well, but the outcome variable is not an aspect of work (training), or an assessment of aspects of work (subjective job quality), but an assessment of the worker his- or herself (self-perceptions of aging).

4. Publications

In the context of this publication-based dissertation, three scientific papers are written and published in peer-reviewed journals. The design of the analyses and salient findings of the papers are briefly summarized below (4.1). An overview table of the papers is presented to provide most important information at a glance (4.2). The published versions of the full papers are presented in the appendix (7. I-III).

4.1. Summary of the Papers

4.1.1. Paper 1: Digitalization, Gender, and Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

In a first study, my co-authors and I shed light on the highly relevant topic of digitalization in occupations and job-related training of older employees. Despite of investigating the question whether digitalization in occupations is associated with a higher likelihood of training participation respectively a higher likelihood to desire training, the focus of this paper is on potential gender-training differences. The article links to recent feministic digitalization-literature, where digitalization is discussed as *window of opportunity* for a renegotiation of gender-power relations. To ensure that both genders can participate and benefit equally from digitalization in the world of work, it is important to give both genders equal opportunities to build and enhance digital capabilities. The study reveals significant gender differences in training participation the more pronounced the change in the digitalization level of occupations. For occupations that experienced high rises in the digitalization level over the last years, the training participation was significantly higher for men than for women. For occupations that experiences low or no rises in the digitalization levels, training participation was higher among women. These gender differences cannot be explained by differences related to the human capital of male and female workers, nor to

differences related to the gender composition of occupations. In addition, no gender differences in the desire for training are found.

The results of the paper can be seen as a reminder that a successful digitalization in the world of work is not taken for granted, but that monitoring and targeted measures are essential to avoid disadvantages for some social groups of workers. The study reveals imbalances in training participation between male and female employees in dependence of the change in the digitalization level of occupations. Further research is needed to find the underlying drivers of these gender inequalities. Conceivable is that employers prefer to make training investments for male rather than for female employees when working in occupations that experienced a digitalization push. Or that female employees in such occupations want to participate in job-related training offers, but existing training offers do not suit their needs and expectations.

4.1.2. Paper 2: Digitalization and Employees' Subjective Job Quality in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

The second paper addresses the question how digitalization relates to subjective job quality of older employees. While there is a rich body of literature on potential benefits but also some adverse effects of digitalization in the workplace for employees, my co-authors and I aimed to reveal how older employees assess it. Therefore, in the second study, it was investigated if older employees in more digital occupations are more/less satisfied and more/less stressed by different aspects of their work in contrast to other employees. Findings reveal that older employees are more satisfied with their job in general if working in a more digitalized occupation. In detail, they are more satisfied with working hours and earnings and less stressed due to tight schedules. However, older employees in more digitalized occupations are also more likely to report higher levels of stress due to adverse environmental factors. The analyses also indicate that differences in opportunities to participate in job-related training may exist among certain groups of employees.

This work contributes to recent debates about whether digitalization can be seen as a curse or blessing for employees. However, instead of analyzing employment or wage-effects, this work is interested in potential effects for the older employee themselves. It offers insights in older employees' perceptions of their working environments and

reveals differences between certain groups of employees. The paper demonstrates the importance of a differentiated analysis of the working situation of older employees, in which specific aspects of job quality are examined separately. Lastly, it takes digitalization fully into account, not only aspects of digitalization, such as computer use.

4.1.3. Paper 3: Digitalization in Occupations and Self-Perceptions of Aging of Workers in their Middle and Late Adulthood.

In the third study of this dissertation, me and my co-authors investigated the question if and how digitalization at work impacts on older workers self-perceptions of aging (SPA). Several negative age stereotypes exist and are widely known when it comes to digitalization and older people. For example, older people are often stereotyped as not willing and incompetent to deal with digital technologies, or as not capable of learning and adapting to changes. The findings reveal that older workers show significant differences in their baseline levels of SPA and that there are interindividual differences in changes in all domains of SPA. Higher digitalization levels in occupations older individuals are working in are found to be associated with improvements in the workers' SPA domains of ongoing development and self-knowledge.

The findings demonstrate that digitalization in the world of work does not necessarily have a negative connotation for older workers. Digitalization can have positive impacts on older workers SPA. Therefore, compassionate ageism should be avoided when it comes to the topic of digital technologies at work and older workers. Employers should not shy away from involve and challenge workers in digital work processes or settings due to their advanced age. Policymakers should create good conditions for development paths in old age through continuing education and learning opportunities for older worker. These offerings should be appropriate for the target group but should not replicate negative age stereotypes and for example assume a lower learning ability or motivation of older individuals.

4.2. Overview Table of the Papers

Table 1: Overview Table of Papers of my Publication-based Dissertation.

	Paper 1	Paper 2	Paper 3
Title	Digitalization, Gender, and Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.	Digitalization and Employees' Subjective Job Quality in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.	Digitalization in Occupations and Self-Perceptions of Aging of Workers in their Middle and Late Adulthood.
Topic	digitalization, gender, and training	digitalization and subjective job quality	digitalization and self-perceptions of aging
Journal	Soziale Welt	Social Indicators Research	The Journal of Aging & Social Change
Co-authors	Stuth, S.; Simonson, J.	Vogel, C., Simonson, J., Huxhold, O.	Henning, G.; Huxhold, O.
Status	published	published	published
Research Questions	(1) Is training participation higher among employees working in occupations with a higher degree of digitalization? (2) Does training participation differ between men and women in relation to the degree of digitalization in occupations?	(1) Is working in more digitalized occupations associated with lower job satisfaction? (2) Is working in more digitalized occupations associated with higher levels of stress?	(1) Is the digitalization level of workers' occupations associated with their SPA? (2) Is the digitalization level of workers' occupations associated with changes in their SPA? (3) Is the change in the digitalization level of workers' occupations associated with changes in their SPA?
Hypotheses	(H1) The higher the extent of digitalization in an occupation, the greater the likelihood of training participation. (H2) Women experience a flatter increase in the likelihood of training participation than men do with increasing degrees of digitalization in an occupation.	(H1) The higher the degree of digitalization in occupations the lower an employees' level of job satisfaction (H2) The higher the degree of digitalization in occupations the higher an employees' level of stress	(H1) The higher the digitalization level in workers' occupations the more negative their SPA. (H2) Working in occupations with higher digitalization levels is associated with stronger decreases in the SPA of workers over time. (H3) Working in occupations with more pronounced changes in the digitalization level is associated with stronger decreases in the SPA of workers over time.
Data	German Ageing Survey 2017	German Ageing Survey 2014	German Ageing Survey 2014 and 2017
Design	cross-sectional, pseudo panel	cross-sectional	longitudinal
Sample	Employees aged 43 to 65 y. n = 1,020	Employees aged 40 to 65 y. n = 1,541	Workers aged 40 to 65 y. n ₂₀₁₄ = 2,722, n ₂₀₁₇ = 1,567

	Paper 1	Paper 2	Paper 3
Method	logistic regressions	multiple logistic regressions	structural equation modelling: latent chance score
Dependent variable(s)	training participation (over last 3 years), desire to participate training in future	job satisfaction (6 items), occupational stress (4 items)	self-perceptions of aging (4 items)
Predictor variable(s)	digitalization level, change in digitalization level, gender	degree of digitalization	digitalization level, change in digitalization level
Control variables	region, age, education, working hours, company size, sector, years till end of work, career interruptions, occupational change, housework, young child in same household, gender composition of occupations	gender, region, age, education, working hours, company size, sector, wage, job insecurity, self-rated health	gender, region, age, education, self-rated health
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For female employees the likelihood of training participation decreases the stronger the change in their occupations' digitalization level; for men it increased - female employees experienced high changes in their occupations' digitalization level show a lower likelihood of training participation compared to male; vice versa for small or negatively directed changes - higher changes in the digitalization level are associated with increased desire for training participation - no significant gender differences regarding the desire for training participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - higher general job satisfaction if working in occupation with higher degree of digitalization - more satisfied with working time, earnings, opportunities for career development in occupation with higher degree of digitalization - higher stress due to negative environmental factors, less stress due to tight schedules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - less negative self-perceptions of aging in the domain of social losses and more positive self-perceptions of aging in the domain of ongoing development if working in occupations with higher digitalization levels in 2014 - working in occupations with higher digitalization levels associated with higher improvements in their self-perceptions of aging regarding ongoing development & self-knowledge

Full references of the papers:

Paper 1 Kortmann, L. K., Stuth, S., & Simonson, J. (2024). Digitalization, Gender and Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany. *Soziale Welt*, 74(4), 589–613. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0038-6073-2023-4-589>

Paper 2 Kortmann, L. K., Simonson, J., Vogel, C., & Huxhold, O. (2021). Digitalization and Employees' Subjective Job Quality in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany. *Social Indicators Research*, 162(2), 577–597. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-021-02854-w>

Paper 3 Kortmann, L. K., Henning, G., & Huxhold, O. (2023). Digitalization in Occupations and Self-Perceptions of Ageing of Older Workers. *The Journal of Aging and Social Change*, 13(2): 129–156. <https://doi.org/10.18848/2576-5310/CGP/v13i02/129-156>

5. Discussion

In the concluding section of this dissertation, the limitations of this work are pointed out (5.1). Moreover, the overarching strengths, the overall contribution and relevance of this work is elaborated (5.2). In addition, outlooks for future research and policy implications are given (5.3).

5.1. Limitations

Any scientific work comes with limitations. Also, this dissertation contains limitations, which are pointed out and transparently discussed below. While specific shortcomings of the three papers of this dissertation have been reported in the related papers (see 7.1, I-III), the following paragraphs are about overarching limitations that concern the overall dissertation.

One shortcoming of this dissertation on digitalization and older workers is, that due to data restrictions it does not allow for comparisons with groups of younger workers, aged 39 and below. The sample of the German Ageing Survey used in all three papers of this thesis is restricted to individuals in the second half of life aged 40 years and above. While the data provides a detailed understanding of the living and working conditions, attitudes, and (self) assessments of older workers, it cannot be concluded whether the same findings would apply to younger workers or not. An age comparison would be of interest to determine differences in occupational situations between older and younger workers in context of digitalization. Yet, such a comparison between younger and older workers was not sought in this dissertation. Younger workers may be attributed by some very specific characteristics related to working life. They may stand just at the beginning of their careers respectively their working life and have been born into world where digitalization is just gaining momentum. In sum, younger workers are likely to represent a group distinct from older workers regarding many aspects. While this dissertation considers individuals in their second half of working life – or more precisely individuals between the ages of 40 and 65 – as older workers, several other studies are based on a narrower definition and consider workers aged 50 and above as older workers. To further account for the relevance of age in this dissertation chronological age is included as control variable.

A second limitation of this dissertation is that two papers are based on cross-sectional data. Such, findings are only a snapshot of the situation of older workers in times of rapidly evolving digitalization in the world of work. However, in one of the papers based on cross sectional data, retrospective and prospective items are used. Hence, analyses are based on pseudo panel data. The third paper of this dissertation does use a longitudinal approach including two time points (2014 and 2017). A longitudinal approach is useful to reveal changes on the individual level induced by digitalization in the working context. The data of the German Ageing Survey used in this dissertation provides great potential regarding longitudinal analyses and even cohort analyses. Yet, the lack of reliable digitalization data for more timepoints has constituted a restricting factor for the analyses. So, the informative value of the results of this dissertation is linked to the selected years of investigation. Currently, little is known about the pace of digital transformation in the work context. However, the results of the papers provide indications of existing associations or effects of digitalization and therefore they provide valuable starting points for follow-up studies that investigate developments over longer periods of time. In recent years the rapid expansion of artificial intelligence in the world of work illustrates the necessity to continue the analyses. As the theoretical framework and digitalization measures used in this work understand or capture digitalization dynamically, they also offer potential for future research. As elaborated before, the TBA coined by Autor, Levy and Murnane (2003) distinguishes between "non routine" or "not substitutable" and "routine" tasks or tasks that are substitutable by digital technologies. The assignment of a task to one of the two categories is therefore always linked to the current state of technological development. If, for example, artificial intelligence opens new application possibilities for digital technologies, the categorization in the TBA approach shifts accordingly. However as also pointed out above the TBA can also be transferred to other units, such as skills. How AI can be operationalized best and how the impact of AI on the labor market and on the workforce can be measured well is the subject of the current debates in research (Acemoglu et al., 2022; Colombo, Mercorio, & Mezzanzanica, 2019; Felten, Raj, & Seamans, 2021; Frank et al., 2019; OECD, 2023).

A third point that should be acknowledged is, that differences within occupations regarding digitalization are not captured in this dissertation, since digitalization measures are aggregated on the occupational level. What a worker actually does in his or her job and what skills are demanded differs not only between different occupations, but also between jobs within the same occupation. This limitation of occupation-based measures is well-known and extensively discussed in literature (Autor & Handel, 2013; Avent-Holt et al., 2020; Cassidy, 2017; Christoph, Matthes, & Ebner, 2020). Differences on the job-level could be inspected by using task- or skill-data on the level of individuals, such as PIAAC data or BiBB/BauA data. However, this dissertation makes use of digitalization data on the occupational level. As elaborated in section 2.2.3, analyses based on occupational level-data do likewise provide valuable findings and are characterized by good data availability.

A fourth limitation of this dissertation is that only some operational characteristics are considered in the analyses. However, current literature has emphasized the importance of operational or team characteristics when it comes to adaption and implementation strategies of digital technologies (Kooij et al., 2020; Meyer, 2011). How workplace digitalization impacts on the working situation of older individuals is likely to depend on management strategies of the enterprise, respectively how and to what extent digital technologies are introduced in the enterprise. In addition, characteristics of the enterprise, or the composition of teams impact on digital technology adaption. Such, several studies find an older workforce to be associated with lower probabilities of innovative behavior (Pfeifer & Wagner, 2014; Rouvinen, 2002; Schneider, 2008). A study of Meyer (2011) indicates, that small or medium-sized service firms with a relatively age-homogenous workforce and intensive use of teamwork show higher probabilities to adapt digital technologies. Mothe and Nguyen-Thi (2021) show, that a polarized age structure in firms is negatively associated with innovation while a broad age distribution in the workforce is positively associated with innovation. In view of these findings on digitalization and operational specificities, future research on digitalization and older workers that incorporates the operational level into their research, as suggested by Kooij et al. (2020), is needed.

5.2. Strengths, Contribution, and Relevance

Besides the limitations discussed above, this dissertation has some notable strengths and makes some valuable contributions to existing literature. One overarching strength of this dissertation is the database underlying the three papers, with the innovative linkage of survey data and information on the digitalization of occupations. This dissertation combines high quality, representative survey data from the German Ageing Survey with recent digitalization data on the occupational level. Digitalization data is not limited to the use of one specific digital technology, such as computer use at work. In addition, information on digitalization in occupations is not based on subjective assessments and thus data is not biased by varying understandings of individuals of what digitalization encompasses. It is an objective measure based on the relative share of digital tasks respectively skills in occupations. Thus, this dissertation can contribute empirical findings based on sound quantitative analyses to the nascent and rapidly developing research topic of digitalization in the working context. In contrast to case studies or studies focusing on single industries, enterprises, or technologies the data base of this dissertation allows to draw conclusions about overall digitalization in the world of work and large parts of the German workforce.

Another asset of this dissertation is, that it contributes new empirical findings to the existing literature on three key aspects of older individuals' working lives in times of digitalization: training, job quality, and self-perceptions of ageing. Regarding job-related training behavior and attitudes toward training this dissertation demonstrated that older employees are more likely to desire job-related training participation if they are working in more digital occupations, but no significant differences between the genders were found. Moreover, working in an occupation where the digitalization level increased strongly over the last years comes with higher training participation. Yet, while an occupations' digitalization level comes only in tendence with a higher likelihood of training participation in general, significant gender differences were found in that regard. While the average likelihood of training participation was higher for women than for men when occupations show low or moderate digitalization levels, it is higher for men when the digitalization level in occupations is high. Differences in older individuals' available time resources, job- and career-related differences, and

sociodemographic differences are controlled for. Even if no cause for the discovered gender difference can be named beyond doubt, this dissertation is an important pointer to potentially problematic dynamics of digitalization. Digitalization in the world of work may be a(nother) driver for gender inequalities in the world of work, since male employees seem to be better off, when it comes to training in digital occupations. Future research needs to investigate this topic in more detail. Existing literature provides ambivalent findings on the existence of a general gender training gap in Germany (Wotschack, 2019). Studies on digitalization and training participation suggest a positive association (Becker, 2019; BMBF, 2021; Gashi, Pugh, & Adnett, 2010; Lukowski, Baum, & Mohr, 2021; Wotschack, 2020). Hence, findings of this dissertation are broadly in line with existing literature but provide more granular insights to some regards. Such, the findings support existing evidence on a positive association of digitalization and training. However, the dissertation emphasizes the importance to differentiate between the actual digitalization level and how strong/weak the digitalization level evolved over a certain time. In addition, findings of this dissertation obviate that, also under consideration of digitalization and focusing on the group of older employees, there is no clearcut association of training participation and gender. In contrast, opposing associations for male and female employees are found. Taken together, this dissertation contributes empirical evidence to the association of digitalization in occupations and older employees' (openness for) job-related training participation.

In addition, this dissertation investigates the relation of digitalization and older employees' perceived job quality. Different aspects of job satisfaction and stress are considered. Under consideration of several job-related and sociodemographic control variables it is shown that older individuals working in more digitalized occupations show higher job satisfaction in general and regarding working hours, earnings, career perspectives and promotions specifically. In addition, employees in more digital occupations show lower levels of stress due to tight schedules. But on the other side higher stress levels regarding negative environmental factors are found for older employees in more digitalized occupations. The educational level of older employees is identified as important control variable for job related stress with a higher educational

level being associated with higher stress levels. Regarding job satisfaction and stress the individual's health status and wages as well as the company size are influential factors. In most part, good health and higher wages correspond to higher aspects of job quality, while working in bigger companies corresponds to lower levels of job quality regarding multiple aspects. Importantly, employees that feel at risk to lose their job in near future assess their job quality lower, overall. However, controlling for employees' fear of losing their job doesn't change the associations between digitalization and (aspects) of job quality greatly. The findings are in line with studies, that concluded that effects of digitalization in the world of work are twofold, beneficial but also detrimental (Anderson-Connolly et al., 2002). To sum this up, this dissertation contributes empirical evidence on digitalization and older employees' perceived job quality. Since job quality is broken down into different aspects of job satisfaction and stress, a detailed picture of how digitalization is related older employees' perceived job quality is drawn.

Regarding the topic of self-perceptions of aging, digitalization is identified as relevant predictor. More positive self-perceptions of aging regarding ongoing development and less negative self-perceptions related to social losses are found for older individuals working in occupations with higher digitalization levels. Attitudes toward own aging in the domain of social losses are related to older workers' perceived appreciation and role in interactions with other people. The domain of ongoing development is related to older workers ongoing skills growth and learning ability, as well as to their ability to implement their ideas and plans. Hence, older individuals working in more digital occupations are more positive about feeling needed and respected by others and don't feel bored or lonely very often. And they are more confident about their competencies and their ability to learn. In addition, higher improvements in older individuals' self-perceptions of aging in the domains of self-knowledge and ongoing development are preceded by working in occupations with higher digitalization levels three years earlier. The domain of self-knowledge refers to the knowledge of the own abilities and needs. However, changes in the digitalization level of occupations between 2014 and 2017 are not significantly associated with older workers self-perceptions of aging. The findings of this dissertation are in line with existing evidence that suggests a positive association of digitalization and self-perceptions of aging (Köttl, Cohn-Schwartz, &

Ayalon, 2021; Mariano et al., 2021a, 2021b). However, beyond existing literature this work provides evidence for the group of older workers. In addition, this work uses detailed self-perceptions of aging measures, and the digitalization measure is not limited to specific uses or applications of digital technologies. Therefore, this dissertation is adding to the literature on self-perceptions of aging and digitalization. Contrary to the common age stereotypes but in line with existing literature, this dissertation shows that digitalization comes with beneficial effects for older workers' self-perceptions.

Overall, the findings of this dissertation indicate that digitalization in the world of work comes with several positive effects for older workers regarding the aspects under investigation. Such, digitalization is not only associated with higher training participation, but older individuals also seem to be more open for job-related trainings if working in more digital occupations. However, older employees' job satisfaction regarding the provision of training was not associated with digitalization in occupations if compositional effects in the workforce were controlled for. Though, older employees seem to be more satisfied with their working hours, their earnings, career prospectives and promotions and are less stressed due to tight schedules if working in more digital occupations. In line with the positive association of digitalization and older workers' training behaviors and their assessments regarding career development and working hours, this dissertation shows that older workers' self-perceptions of aging regarding personal development and own competences as well as self-perceptions of aging regarding self-knowledge show higher improvements if working in more digital occupations three years earlier.

In the synopsis of all results, the following interpretations are suggested. Overall, digitalization at work is beneficial for older workers' further development and personal growth in the professional context and for older workers job satisfaction in general. Among older individuals working in more digital occupations there seems to be a higher practice and commitment to learning and further development, compared to older workers in less digital occupations. Digitalization seems to open career and development prospects for older workers and to come with a satisfying remuneration.

In addition, digitalization positively impacts on older workers' views on their own aging regarding their competences and their self-knowledge. New demands and challenges at work due to digitalization processes may stipulate older workers learning behavior. Positive learning experiences and successful adaptation processes to new challenges at work may, in turn, positively affect a worker's self-knowledge and competence related self-efficacy. Older workers may experience that they are able to keep up with the times and adjust their resources to an altered environment. The adaptation and expansion of one's resources, may be rewarded by good wages and development prospects in the work context. Contrary to the general expectation that accelerating work processes would burden older workers, older individuals working in more digital occupations are more satisfied with time structures at work and they report lower levels of stress due to tight schedules compared to workers in less digital occupations. One possible explanation is that life and work experience of older workers counteract stress due accelerating working processes, such they do not feel particularly burdened. Another conceivable explanation is that digitalization in occupations is indeed associated with greater time pressure and accelerating work processes, but that digital structures at work offer a greater autonomy and flexibility to workers in the allocation of their working time, too. In line with that, Bolli and Pusterla (2022) find that greater working time flexibility and simplified communication in the working context due to digitalization are associated with higher levels of workers' job satisfaction. The overall results also indicate some unfavorable facets of digitalization for (groups of) older workers. The dissertation suggests that one should be particularly vigilant against aggravating or emerging gender and educational inequalities among older workers. Female employees seem to be disadvantaged or discouraged from taking part in job-related trainings when working in in occupations that experienced a steep digitalization push over the last years. Thus, female employees might have poorer opportunities to adapt their skills to new challenges at work through further training – whether by being disadvantaged or by other hurdles. This could lead to female employees not equally benefiting from some advantages of digitalization discussed above. Moreover, older individuals working in more digital occupations are found to report higher stress levels due to negative environmental factors. This may result from the expectation that all negative environmental impacts at work will be eliminated by digitalization. However,

digital tools and processes themselves can create negative environmental influences. Such older workers may feel burdened by the exposure to screens or signal tones.

In times of an aging workforce the promotion of staying longer in the labor market is a declared policy goal. To unravel and understand drivers of older workers' retirement respectively retention decisions, it is also important to look at how older workers fare in the occupational context. As major changes are taking place in the world of work in course of digitalization, most older workers are exposed to altering working environments. Against this backdrop, it is particularly relevant to keep an eye on the occupational situation of older workers. However, there is not much literature with focus on the individual level so far. This dissertation approaches this gap and provides empirical findings on the occupational situation of older workers in the context of digitalization. The findings and related interpretations of this dissertation can be discussed in the context of the process model of successful aging (Rowe & Kahn, 1997) that was applied to the workplace by Kooij and colleagues (2020) (see chapter 3.1). According to Kooij and colleagues (2020), successful aging in the workplace involves the behavior of individuals aiming at maintaining or adapting his or her ability and motivation to continue working. Hence, it would require self-regulation processes of the workers in order to adapt to altered work environments (Kooij et al., 2020). Digitalization at work can constitute a profound change of an individual's work environment. And it can cause a devaluation of a worker's personal resources, since it impacts on the task composition of and skill demands in a worker's occupation. Participation in training constitutes one self-regulation strategy to maintain or restore a worker's person-environment fit by adjusting personal skills to new demands at work. A good person-environment fit is related with outcomes like higher job satisfaction, lower strain, or higher organizational commitment (Kristof-Brown, Zimmerman, & Johnson, 2005; Oh et al., 2014). Taking the findings against Kooij and colleagues' process model, it can be assumed that digitalization has a positive impact on older workers decision to continue working. However, the concept of "successful aging" must be used carefully, since it simplifies aging processes of individuals by distinguishing between two categories only, that are also normatively afflicted: successful / not successful (respectively: continue working / not continue working). There are large

differences in the ageing processes of individuals that are accumulating and often aggravating over the life course (Baltes, Lindenberger, & Staudinger, 2007; Dannefer, 2003). Importantly, such differences are not only results of individual decisions, but are shaped from an individual's early years on by contextual factors and personal resources. Therefore, it is certainly neither a throughout individual and free decision, nor a necessary condition for older workers to adapt skills to new digital demands in a job in order to age successfully (respectively to continue working). Regardless of the criticism of the concept of successful aging, Kooij and colleague's (2020) process model represents a valid starting point for this dissertation to understand the link between digitalization and the individual level.

The process of digitalization can significantly alter job tasks, required skills, and work processes, which may require older workers to acquire new knowledge and skills to remain employable, productive, and motivated. By examining job-related training behavior, researchers can better understand how older workers respond to digitalization processes at work and how training opportunities may affect their ability to remain competitive in the labor market. Moreover, perceived job quality is important to examine as digitalization may also affect job characteristics such as work pace, exposure to physically demanding work, or job demands. These changes are likely to come with implications for perceived job satisfaction and stress, and following for the older workers work engagement, and overall well-being. Finally, studying self-perceptions of aging is important as negative images on the own aging can be detrimental for workers' health and self-efficacy. By examining self-perceptions of aging, researchers can better understand how digitalization in occupations impacts on older workers experiences of different facets of their own age and aging process.

Altogether, this dissertation contributes to a better understanding of the situation of older workers in digitalizing occupations. This helps enterprises and politicians to develop and implement targeted measures in order to shape digitalization processes effectively and in a way that older workers don't need to experience negative impacts. One important goal that should be constantly reviewed and permanently strived for certainly is gender equal participation in job-related training. In support of realizing

more gender equal labor markets, opportunities to take up new skills by job related training must be equally accessible and attractive for all older workers. In these years the female employment rate is still lower than that of men, and the share of women working in highly digital sectors, such as the ICT sector, is comparably low. In addition, this dissertation has shown that female employees also are less likely to participate in training if working in strongly digitalizing occupations. Other studies indicated that women perceive their digital competencies lower than men do, albeit no differences regarding their actual skills were found (Hargittai & Shafer, 2006; Sieverding & Koch, 2009). Therefore, women that already work or are interested to work in digital occupations should be supported by political and operational training measures. For example, this could be accomplished by offering training courses that address women's needs regarding digitalization at work or barriers they face. Courses could be led by female instructors to help to tackle the barrier of underrepresentation. Or mentorship programs could be established to assist women overcoming barriers and access influential networks at work. Despite the previously discussed point, this dissertation may help to overcome negative stereotypes of older workers related to digitalization. The findings of this work suggest that the picture of older workers being unwilling to learn or not being open for changes at work is not accurate. In contrast, it is shown, that a large share of older workers desires to take part in job related training, especially if they are working in more digital occupations. Moreover, working in digital occupations was found to precede higher improvements in competence and self-knowledge related attitudes toward one's own ageing.

In sum, disclosing the studied associations of digitalization and aspects of older individuals' occupational situation, this dissertation reveals beneficial but also some detrimental effects for older workers. However, as discussed above, positive effects prevail for those who work in digitalizing occupations. This dissertation contributes to a better understanding of the interplay between digitalization in occupations and individual situations and attitudes of older workers. However, research on this topic is still evolving and further research on this topic is needed. Especially studies that cover effects in the overall population of older workers are needed to understand and identify effects of digitalization on this group as a whole. However, research must take into

account that “the older workers” is not a homogeneous group, but it is characterized by heterogeneous and diverse life situations. Such, older workers with poor health conditions may be affected quite differently by digitalization in the world of work than workers with good health. Health limitations that previously led to withdrawal from the labor market may now be overcome thanks to digital technologies. On the other hand, health limitations may hinder the operation and use of digital technologies. In addition, future studies on digitalization in the world and effects on older individuals should also pay attention to the organizational level. Factors such as firm size or the sector of employment have been identified as important control variables in this dissertation, but also management strategies or the financial capacities of an enterprise may impact on how digitalization processes are introduced and guided in an enterprise. In total, the potential of digitalization in the world of work may be fully exploited for older workers if negative effects in general or for specific groups of older workers are identified by research and then controlled by political and operational measures. Moreover, older individuals should not be seen as a risk group when it comes to digitalization. They should rather be seen as a group with different but individually unique prerequisites.

6. References

- Acemoglu, D. (2002). Technical Change, Inequality, and the Labor Market. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 40(1), 7-72. <https://doi.org/10.1257/0022051026976>
- Acemoglu, D., Akcigit, U., & Celik, M. A. (2022). Radical and Incremental Innovation: The Roles of Firms, Managers, and Innovators. *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 14(3), 199-249. <https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20170410>
- Acemoglu, D., Autor, D., Hazell, J., & Restrepo, P. (2022). Artificial Intelligence and Jobs: Evidence from Online Vacancies. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 40(S1), 293-340. <https://doi.org/10.1086/718327>
- Acemoglu, D., & Autor, D. H. (2011). Skills, tasks and technologies: Implications for employment and earnings. In D. Card & O. Ashenfelter (Eds.), *Handbook of Labor Economics* (Vol. 4B, pp. 1043-1171). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7218\(11\)02410-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7218(11)02410-5)
- Acemoglu, D., & Restrepo, P. (2018). The Race between Man and Machine: Implications of Technology for Growth, Factor Shares, and Employment. *American Economic Review*, 108(6), 1488-1542. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20160696>
- Ahituv, A., & Zeira, J. (2011). Technical progress and early retirement. *The Economic Journal*, 121(551), 171-193. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0297.2010.02392.x>
- Aissaoui, N. (2021). The digital divide: A literature review and some directions for future research in light of COVID-19. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 71(8/9), 686-708. <https://doi.org/10.1108/gkmc-06-2020-0075>
- Albert, C., García-Serrano, C., & Hernanz, V. (2010). On-the-job training in Europe: Determinants and wage returns. *International Labour Review*, 149(3), 315-341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1564-913X.2010.00089.x>
- Alekseeva, L., Azar, J., Giné, M., Samila, S., & Taska, B. (2021). The demand for AI skills in the labor market. *Labour Economics*, 71, 102002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2021.102002>
- Amankwah-Amoah, J., Khan, Z., Wood, G., & Knight, G. (2021). COVID-19 and digitalization: The great acceleration. *Journal of Business Research*, 136, 602-611. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.08.011>
- Anderson-Connolly, R., Grunberg, L., Greenberg, E. S., & Moore, S. (2002). Is Lean Mean? Workplace Transformation and Employee Well-being. *Work, Employment and Society*, 16(3), 389-413. <https://doi.org/10.1177/095001702762217407>
- Antonczyk, D., Fitzenberger, B., & Leuschner, U. (2009). Can a Task-Based Approach Explain the Recent Changes in the German Wage Structure? *Jahrbücher für*

Nationalökonomie und Statistik, 229(2-3), 214-238. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/jbnst-2009-2-309>

Apt, W., & Priesack, K. (2017). KI und Arbeit – Chance und Risiko zugleich [AI and work - opportunity and risk at the same time]. In V. Wittpahl (Ed.), *Künstliche Intelligenz. Technologie - Anwendung - Gesellschaft* (pp. 221-238). Springer.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-58042-4_13

Arntz, M., Gregory, T., & Zierahn, U. (2016). The Risk of Automation for Jobs in OECD countries. A Comparative Analysis. *OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jlz9h56dvq7-en>

Artige, L., Cavenaile, L., & Pestieau, P. (2014). The Macroeconomics of PAYG Pension Schemes in an Aging Society. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.

<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2438689>

Atalay, E., Phongthientham, P., Sotelo, S., & Tannenbaum, D. I. (2020). The Evolution of Work in the United States. *American Economic Journal Applied Economics*, 12(2), 1-34.

<https://doi.org/10.1257/app.20190070>

Atkinson, A. B. (2008). *The changing distribution of earnings in OECD countries*. In Oxford University Press eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199532438.001.0001>

Attewell, P. (2001). The first and second digital divides. *Sociology of Education*, 74(3), 252-259. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2673277>

Autor, D. H. (2015). Why are there still so many jobs?. The history and future of workplace automation. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 29(3), 3-30.

<https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.29.3.3>

Autor, D. H., & Dorn, D. (2013). The growth of low-skill service jobs and the polarization of the US labor market. *The American Economic Review*, 103(5), 1553-1597.

<http://doi.org/10.1257/aer.103.5.1553>

Autor, D. H., & Handel, M. J. (2013). Putting Tasks to the Test: Human Capital, Job Tasks, and Wages. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 31(S1), 59-96.

<https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1086/669332>

Autor, D. H., Katz, L. F., & Kearney, M. S. (2006). The Polarization of the U.S. Labor Market. *The American Economic Review*, 96(2), 189-194.

<https://doi.org/10.1257/000282806777212620>

Autor, D. H., Katz, L. F., & Kearney, M. S. (2008). Trends in U.S. Wage Inequality: Revising the Revisionists. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 90(2), 300-323.

<https://doi.org/10.1162/rest.90.2.300>

- Autor, D. H., Levy, F., & Murnane, R. J. (2003). The skill content of recent technological change: An empirical exploration. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, *118*(4), 1279-1333. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003355303322552801>
- Avent-Holt, D., Henriksen, L. F., Hägglund, A. E., Jung, J., Kodama, N., Melzer, S. M., Mun, E., Rainey, A., & Tomaskovic-Devey, D. (2020). Occupations, workplaces or jobs?: An exploration of stratification contexts using administrative data. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, *70*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2019.100456>
- Azar, J., Marinescu, I., Steinbaum, M., & Taska, B. (2020). Concentration in US labor markets: Evidence from online vacancy data. *Labour Economics*, *66*, 101886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2020.101886>
- Bachmann, R., Cim, M., & Green, C. (2019). Long-Run Patterns of Labour Market Polarization: Evidence from German Micro Data. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, *57*(2), 350-376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjir.12419>
- Bäcker, G., Schmitz-Kießler, J., Sommer, P., & Zink, L. (2023). Dauerbaustelle Sozialstaat 2022 [Permanent construction site welfare state 2022]. [duepublico2.uni-due.de. https://doi.org/10.17185/duepublico/77348](https://doi.org/10.17185/duepublico/77348)
- Bal, A. C., Reiss, A. E. B., Rudolph, C. W., & Baltes, B. B. (2011). Examining Positive and Negative Perceptions of Older Workers: A Meta-Analysis. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, *66B*(6), 687-698. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbr056>
- Baltes, P. B., Lindenberger, U., & Staudinger, U. M. (2007). Life Span Theory in Developmental Psychology. In W. Damon & R. M. Lerner (Eds.), *Handbook of Child Psychology* (6 ed., Vol. 6). John Wiley & Sons, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470147658.chpsy0111>
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action. A social cognitive theory*. Prentice Hall.
- Bartel, A. P., & Sicherman, N. (1993). Technological Change and Retirement Decisions of Older Workers. *Journal of Labor Economics*, *11*(1, Part 1), 162-183. <https://doi.org/10.1086/298321>
- Becker, R. (2019). Economic change and continuous vocational training in the work history: a longitudinal multilevel analysis of the employees' participation in further training and the effects on their occupational careers in Germany, 1970–2008. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, *11*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-019-0079-x>
- Belbin, R. M. (1967). *Training methods for older workers*. OECD Publishing.
- Bessen, J. (2015). Toil and Techology. *Finance & Development*, *52*(1), 16-19.

- Bolli, T., & Pusterla, F. (2022). Decomposing the effects of digitalization on workers' job satisfaction. *International Review of Economics*, 69(2), 263-300.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12232-022-00392-6>
- Bonin, H., Gregory, T., & Zierahn, U. (2015). Übertragung der Studie von Frey/Osborne (2013) auf Deutschland: Endbericht [Transfer of the study by Frey/Osborne (2013) to Germany: Final report.]. In *www.bmas.de* (No. 57, p. 44). BMAS. Retrieved September 15, 2022, from
https://www.bmas.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Publikationen/Forschungsberichte/fb-455.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=2
- Börsch-Supan, A., Heiss, F., Ludwig, A., & Winter, J. (2003). Pension Reform, Capital Markets and the Rate of Return. *German Economic Review*, 4(2), 151-181.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0475.00077>
- Brunello, G., Garibaldi, P., & Wasmer, E. (2007). *Education and Training in Europe*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199210978.001.0001>
- Brunello, G., & Wruuck, P. (2021). Skill Shortages and Skill Mismatch in Europe: A Review of the Literature. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 35(4), 1125-1167.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/joes.12424>
- Brynjolfsson, E., & McAfee, A. (2014). *The second machine age. Work, progress, and prosperity in a time of brilliant technologies*. Norton & Company.
- Büchel, F., & Pannenberg, M. (2004). Berufliche Weiterbildung in West- und Ostdeutschland: Teilnehmer, Struktur und individueller Ertrag [Further vocational training activities in West and East Germany: participants, structure and individual effects]. *Zeitschrift für ArbeitsmarktForschung - Journal for Labour Market Research*, 37(2), 73-126.
- Buchholz, S., Rinklake, A., Schilling, J., Kurz, K., Schmelzer, P., & Blossfeld, H.-P. (2011). Aging populations, globalization and the labor market. Comparing late working life and retirement in modern societies. In Blossfeld, Hans-Peter, S. Buchholz, K. Kurz (Eds.), *Aging Populations, Globalization and the Labor Market: Comparing Late Working Life and Retirement in Modern Societies* (pp. 3-32). Edward Elgar.
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781849805858>
- Bührer, C., & Hagist, C. (2017). The Effect of Digitalization on the Labor Market. In H. Ellermann, P. Kreutter, & W. Messner (Eds.), *The Palgrave Handbook of Managing Continuous Business Transformation* (pp. 115-137). Palgrave Macmillan UK.
https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-60228-2_5

- Bundesagentur für Arbeit Statistik/Arbeitsmarktberichterstattung. (2022). *Berichte: Blickpunkt Arbeitsmarkt – Fachkräfteengpassanalyse 2021 [Reports: Focus on the labour market - Skilled labour shortage analysis 2021]*. <https://statistik.arbeitsagentur.de/>
- Bundesministerium für Arbeit und Soziales - BMAS, & Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung - BMBF. (2019). *Nationale Weiterbildungsstrategie [National Skills Strategy]*. https://www.bmas.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Aus-Weiterbildung/strategiepapier-nationale-weiterbildungsstrategie.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3
- BMBF. (2021). *Nationale Weiterbildungsstrategie [National Skills Strategy]*. <https://www.bmbf.de/de/nationale-weiterbildungsstrategie-8853.html>
- BMBF. (2021). *Weiterbildungsverhalten in Deutschland 2020 [Continuing education behaviour in Germany 2020]*. https://www.bmbf.de/SharedDocs/Publikationen/de/bmbf/1/31690_AES-Trendbericht_2020.pdf
- Burlon, L., & Vilalta-Bufí, M. (2016). A new look at technical progress and early retirement. *IZA Journal of Labor Policy*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40173-016-0058-9>
- Cammeraat, E., & Squicciarini, M. (2021). Burning Glass Technologies' data use in policy-relevant analysis: An occupation-level assessment. (OECD Science, Technology and Industry Working Papers No. 2021/05). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/cd75c3e7-en>
- Caplan, R. D., & Van Harrison, R. (1993). Person-Environment Fit Theory: Some History, Recent Developments, and Future Directions. *Journal of Social Issues*, 49(4), 253-275. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.1993.tb01192.x>
- Card, D., & DiNardo, J. E. (2002). Skill Biased Technological Change and Rising Wage Inequality. Some Problems and Puzzles. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 20(4), 733–783. <https://doi.org/10.1086/342055>
- Carnevale, A. P., Jayasundera, T., & Repnikov, D. (2014). Understanding online job ads data. A technical report. In *Centre on Education and the Workforce. Report Website*. Georgetown University. Retrieved September 15, 2022, from https://cew.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/OCLM.Tech_Web_.pdf
- Cassidy, H. (2017). Task Variation Within Occupations. *Industrial Relations: A Journal of Economy and Society*, 56(3), 393-410. <https://doi.org/10.1111/irel.12179>
- Cedefop. (2018). *Insights into skill shortages and skill mismatch. Learning from Cedefop's European skills and jobs survey*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/645011>

- Cedefop. (2019). *Online job vacancies and skills analysis. A Cedefop pan-European approach*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/097022>
- Cedefop. (2021a). *Understanding technological change and skill needs: Big data and artificial intelligence methods: Cedefop practical guide 2*. Publications Office. <http://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/144881>
- Cedefop. (2021b). *Understanding technological change and skill needs: technology and skills foresight*. Publications Office. <http://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/307925>
- Cedefop, European Commission, ETF, ILO, OECD, & UNESCO. (2021). *Perspectives on policy and practice: tapping into the potential of big data for skills policy*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/25160>
- Christoph, B., Matthes, B., & Ebner, C. (2020). Occupation-Based Measures. An Overview and Discussion. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 72(1), 41-78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-020-00673-4>
- Colombo, E., Mercorio, F., & Mezzanzanica, M. (2019). AI meets labor market: Exploring the link between automation and skills. *Information Economics and Policy*, 47, 27-37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infoecopol.2019.05.003>
- Compaine, B. M. (2001). *The Digital Divide: Facing a Crisis or Creating a Myth?* The M.I.T. Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/2419.001.0001>
- Curtarelli, M., Gualtieri, V., Jannati, M. S., & Donlevy, V., & European Commission (2017). *ICT for work: Digital skills in the workplace: Final report*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/498467>
- Czaja, S. J., Charness, N., Fisk, A. D., Hertzog, C., Nair, S. N., Rogers, W. A., & Sharit, J. (2006). Factors Predicting the Use of Technology: Findings From the Center for Research and Education on Aging and Technology Enhancement (CREATE). *Psychology and Aging*, 21(2), 333-352. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0882-7974.21.2.333>
- Dannefer, D. (2003). Cumulative Advantage/Disadvantage and the Life Course: Cross-Fertilizing Age and Social Science Theory. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 58(6), S327-S337. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/58.6.S327>
- Dauth, W., Findeisen, S., Suedekum, J., & Woessner, N. (2021). The Adjustment of Labor Markets to Robots. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 19(6), 3104-3153. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeea/jvab012>
- de Koning, J., & Gelderblom, A. (2006). ICT and older workers: no unwrinkled relationship. *International Journal of Manpower*, 27(5), 467-490. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437720610683967>

- Deming, D. J. (2017). The growing importance of social skills in the labor market [Aufsatz in Zeitschrift, Article in journal]. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 132(4), 1593-1640. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjx022>
- Deming, D. J., & Noray, K. (2020). Earnings Dynamics, Changing Job Skills, and STEM Careers. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 135(4), 1965-2005. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjaa021>
- Dengler, K., & Matthes, B. (2018). The impacts of digital transformation on the labour market: Substitution potentials of occupations in Germany. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 137, 304-316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.09.024>
- Dengler, K., Matthes, B., & Paulus, W. (2014). Berufliche Tasks auf dem deutschen Arbeitsmarkt. Eine alternative Messung auf Basis einer Expertendatenbank [Occupational tasks on the German labour market. An alternative measurement based on an expert database]. In *FDZ-Methodenreporte* (No. 12/2014). Forschungsdatenzentrum der Bundesagentur für Arbeit. Retrieved September 8, 2022, from http://doku.iab.de/fdz/reporte/2014/MR_12-14.pdf
- Dieckhoff, M. (2007). Does it Work? The Effect of Continuing Training on Labour Market Outcomes: A Comparative Study of Germany, Denmark, and the United Kingdom. *European Sociological Review*, 23(3), 295-308. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcm002>
- Draca, M., Sadun, R., & Van Reenen, J. (2007). Productivity and ICTs: a review of the evidence. In R. Mansell, C. Avgerou, D. Quah, & R. Silverstone (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of information and communication technologies* (online edn, pp. 100-147). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199548798.001.0001>
- Dustmann, C., Ludsteck, J., & Schönberg, U. (2009). Revisiting the German wage structure. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 124(2), 843-881. <https://doi.org/10.1162/qjec.2009.124.2.843>
- Ebner, A. (2010). Varieties of Capitalism and the Limits of Entrepreneurship Policy: Institutional Reform in Germany's Coordinated Market Economy. *Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade*, 10(3-4), 319-341. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10842-010-0086-x>
- Ehing, D., & Moog, S. (2013). Erwerbspersonen- und Arbeitsvolumenprojektionen bis ins Jahr 2060 [Labour force and labour volume projections up to 2060]. *Journal for Labour Market Research*, 46(2), 167-182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12651-012-0126-6>
- Ehlert, M. (2017). Who Benefits from Training Courses in Germany? Monetary Returns to Non-formal Further Education on a Segmented Labour Market. *European Sociological Review*, 33(3), 436-448. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcx042>

- Estevez-Abe, M., Iversen, T., & Soskice, D. (2001). Social Protection and the Formation of Skills: A Reinterpretation of the Welfare State. In P. A. Hall & D. Soskice (Eds.), *Varieties of Capitalism: The Institutional Foundations of Comparative Advantage* (online edn, pp. 145–183). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/0199247757.003.0004>
- Eurofond. (2018). *Automation, digitalisation and platforms: Implications for work and employment*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2806/090974>
- European Commission. (2022). Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2021. Germany. 1-17. Retrieved 07.12.2022, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-economy-and-society-index-desi-2021>
- Falck, O., Heimisch-Roecker, A., & Wiederhold, S. (2021). Returns to ICT skills. *Research Policy*, 50(7), 104064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104064>
- Felten, E., Raj, M., & Seamans, R. (2021). Occupational, industry, and geographic exposure to artificial intelligence: A novel dataset and its potential uses. *Strategic Management Journal*, 42(12), 2195-2217. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.3286>
- Fernández-Macías, E. (2012). Job Polarization in Europe? Changes in the Employment Structure and Job Quality, 1995-2007. *Work and Occupations*, 39(2), 157-182. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888411427078>
- Fernández-Macías, E., & Hurley, J. (2017). Routine-biased technical change and job polarization in Europe. *Socio-Economic Review*, 15(3), 563-585. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mww016>
- Frank, M., Autor, D., Bessen, J. E., Brynjolfsson, E., Cebrian, M., Deming, D. J., Feldman, M., Groh, M., Lobo, J., Moro, E., Wang, D., Youn, H., & Rahwan, I. (2019). Toward understanding the impact of artificial intelligence on labor. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1900949116>
- Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation? *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 114, 254-280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.08.019>
- Friemel, T. N. (2016). The digital divide has grown old: Determinants of a digital divide among seniors. *New Media & Society*, 18(2), 313-331. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444814538648>
- Gashi, A. N., Pugh, G., & Adnett, N. (2010). Technological change and employer-provided training: Evidence from UK workplaces. *International Journal of Manpower*, 31(4), 426-448. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437721011057010>
- Goel, A. (2010). *Computer Fundamentals*. Pearson Education India.

- Goldin, C. D., & Katz, L. F. (2008). *The Race Between Education and Technology*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjf9x5x>
- Goos, M., & Manning, A. (2007). Lousy and Lovely Jobs: The Rising Polarization of Work in Britain. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 89(1), 118-133. <https://doi.org/10.1162/rest.89.1.118>
- Goos, M., Manning, A., & Salomons, A. (2009). Job polarization in Europe. *The American Economic Review*, 99(2), 58-63. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.99.2.58>
- Grund, C., & Martin, J. (2012). Determinants of further training. Evidence for Germany. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(17), 3536–3558. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2011.654347>
- Hansson, B. M. (2008). *Job-Related Training and Benefits for Individuals: A Review of Evidence and Explanations* (OECD Education Working Papers No. 19). <https://doi.org/10.1787/237755412637>
- Hargittai, E. (2002). Second-Level Digital Divide: Differences in People's Online Skills. *First Monday*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v7i4.942>
- Hargittai, E., & Shafer, S. (2006). Differences in Actual and Perceived Online Skills: The Role of Gender*. *Social Science Quarterly*, 87(2), 432-448. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6237.2006.00389.x>
- Harper, S. (2014). Economic and Social Implications of Aging Societies. *Science*, 346(6209), 587-591. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1254405>
- Henseke, G., Hetze, P., & Tivig, T. (2009). Ageing in German Industry. In M. Kuhn & C. Ochsen (Eds.), *Labour Markets and Demographic Change* (pp. 12-30). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-91478-7_1
- Hirsch-Kreinsen, H., & Wienzek, T. (2019). Arbeit 4.0. Segen oder Fluch [Work 4.0. blessing or curse]? In B. Badura, A. Ducki, H. Schröder, J. Klose, & M. Meyer (Eds.), *Fehlzeiten-Report 2019* (pp. 17-28). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-59044-7>
- Honekamp, I. (2007). PAYG in an ageing society: The case of Sweden versus Germany. *Pensions: An International Journal*, 12(3), 138-153. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.pm.5950052>
- Hunsaker, A., & Hargittai, E. (2018). A review of Internet use among older adults. *New Media & Society*, 20(10), 3937-3954. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818787348>
- Huxhold, O., Hees, E., & Webster, N. J. (2020). Towards bridging the grey digital divide: changes in internet access and its predictors from 2002 to 2014 in Germany. *European Journal of Ageing*, 17(3), 271-280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-020-00552-z>

- Icardi, R. (2021). Returns to Workplace Training for Male and Female Employees and Implications for the Gender Wage gap: A Quantile Regression Analysis. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 8(1), 21-45. <https://doi.org/10.13152/ijrvet.8.1.2>
- International Labour Organization - ILO. (2012). *International Standard Classification of Occupations - ISCO-08*. International Labour Office. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_172572.pdf
- ILO. (2016). Labour Force Participation Rate. In *Key Indicators of the Labour Market* (9th ed., pp. 51-54). International Labour Office. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---stat/documents/publication/wcms_498929.pdf
- Initiative D21. (2021). *D21-Digital-Index 2020/ 2021. Jährliches Lagebild zur Digitalen Gesellschaft*. https://initiated21.de/app/uploads/2021/02/d21-digital-index-2020_2021.pdf
- International Federation of Robotics. (2016). *Executive Summary World Robotics 2016 Industrial Robots*. World Robotics. <https://ifr.org/worldrobotics/>
- International Monetary Fund. (2022). *World Economic Outlook: Countering the Cost-of-Living Crisis*. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/Issues/2022/10/11/world-economic-outlook-october-2022>
- Katz, L., & Autor, D. (1999). Changes in the wage structure and earnings inequality. In O. C. Ashenfelter & D. Card (Eds.), *Handbook of Labor Economics* (Vol. 3, pp. 1463-1555). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1573-4463\(99\)03007-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1573-4463(99)03007-2)
- Katz, L. F., & Murphy, K. M. (1992). Changes in Relative Wages, 1963–1987: Supply and Demand Factors. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107(1), 35-78. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2118323>
- Keynes, J.M. (2010). Economic Possibilities for Our Grandchildren. In: *Essays in Persuasion*. Palgrave Macmillan, London. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-59072-8_25
- Klaus, D., Engstler, H., Mahne, K., Wolff, J. K., Simonson, J., Wurm, S., & Tesch-Römer, C. (2017). Cohort Profile: The German Ageing Survey (DEAS). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 46(4), 1105-1105g. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw326>
- Komp-Leukkunen, K., Poli, A., Hellevik, T., Herlofson, K., Heuer, A., Norum, R., Solem, P. E., Khan, J., Rantanen, V., & Motel Klingebiel, A. (2022). Older Workers in Digitalizing Workplaces: A Systematic Literature Review. *The Journal of Aging and Social Change*, 12(2), 37-54. <https://doi.org/10.18848/2576-5310/CGP/v12i02/37-59>

- Kooij, D. T. A. M., Zacher, H., Wang, M., & Heckhausen, J. (2020). Successful aging at work: A process model to guide future research and practice. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology, 13*(3), 345-365. <https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2020.1>
- Kortmann, L. K., Hagen, C., Endter, C., Riesch, J., & Tesch-Römer, C. (2022). Internet Use by People in the Second Half of Life during the Covid-19 Pandemic: Social Inequalities Persist. In J. Simonson, J. Wünsche, & C. Tesch-Römer (Eds.), *Ageing in Times of the COVID-19 Pandemic*. Springer VS (pp. 235–253). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-40487-1_13
- Kortmann, L. K., Henning, G., & Huxhold, O. (2023). Digitalization in Occupations and Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers. *The Journal of Aging and Social Change, 13*(2): 129–156. <https://doi.org/10.18848/2576-5310/CGP/v13i02/129-156>
- Kortmann, L. K., Simonson, J., Vogel, C., & Huxhold, O. (2021). Digitalization and Employees' Subjective Job Quality in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany. *Social Indicators Research, 162*(2), 577–597. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-021-02854-w>
- Kortmann, L. K., Stuth, S. & Simonson, J. (2023). Digitalisation, Gender, and Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany. *Soziale Welt, 74*(4), 589–613. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0038-6073-2023-4-589>
- Köttl, H., Cohn-Schwartz, E., & Ayalon, L. (2021). Self-Perceptions of Aging and Everyday ICT Engagement: A Test of Reciprocal Associations. *The Journals of Gerontology Series B, 76*(9), 1913-1922. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbaa168>
- Kristof-Brown, A. L., Zimmerman, R. D., & Johnson, E. C. (2005). Consequences of Individuals' Fit at Work: A Meta-Analysis of Person-Job, Person-Organization, Person-Group, and Person-Supervisor Fit. *Personnel Psychology, 58*(2), 281-342. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2005.00672.x>
- Kubicek, B., Paškvan, M., & Korunka, C. (2015). Development and validation of an instrument for assessing job demands arising from accelerated change: The intensification of job demands scale (IDS). *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology, 24*(6), 898-913. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432x.2014.979160>
- Lee, C. C., Czaja, S. J., & Sharit, J. (2008). Training Older Workers for Technology-Based Employment. *Educational Gerontology, 35*(1), 15-31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601270802300091>
- Lee, J.-W., Kwak, D. W., & Song, E. (2022). Can older workers stay productive? The role of ICT skills and training. *Journal of Asian Economics, 79*, 101438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asieco.2021.101438>

- Leicht, K. T. (2020). Occupations and Inequalities in the 21st Century: What's in your Wallet? *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 70, 100550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2020.100550>
- Lemieux, T. (2006). Increasing Residual Wage Inequality: Composition Effects, Noisy Data, or Rising Demand for Skill? *The American Economic Review*, 96(3), 461-498. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.96.3.461>
- Levy, B. (2009). Stereotype Embodiment: A Psychosocial Approach to Aging. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 18(6), 332-336. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2009.01662.x>
- Lukowski, F., Baum, M., & Mohr, S. (2021). Technology, tasks and training – evidence on the provision of employer-provided training in times of technological change in Germany. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 43(2), 174-195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037x.2020.1759525>
- Manyika, J., Chui, M., Miremadi, M., Bughin, J., George, K., Willmott, P., & Dewhurst, M. (2017). *A future that works: automation, employment, and productivity*. McKinsey Global Institute. Accessed at 10th October 2022, from <https://cica.org.au/wp-content/uploads/MGI-A-future-that-works-Full-report.pdf>
- Mariano, J., Marques, S., Ramos, M. R., & de Vries, H. (2021a). Cognitive functioning mediates the relationship between self-perceptions of aging and computer use behavior in late adulthood: Evidence from two longitudinal studies. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 121, 106807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106807>
- Mariano, J., Marques, S., Ramos, M. R., & de Vries, H. (2021b). Internet use by middle-aged and older adults: Longitudinal relationships with functional ability, social support, and self-perceptions of aging. *Psychology and Aging*, 36(8), 983–995. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pag0000643>
- Messe, P.-J., Moreno-Galbis, E., & Wolff, F.-C. (2014). Retirement intentions in the presence of technological change: theory and evidence from France. *IZA Journal of Labor Economics*, 3(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-8997-3-8>
- Meyer, J. (2011). Workforce age and technology adoption in small and medium-sized service firms. *Small Business Economics*, 37(3), 305-324. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-009-9246-y>
- Millward, P. (2003). The 'grey digital divide': Perception, exclusion and barriers of access to the Internet for older people. *First Monday*, 8(7). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v8i7.1066>

- Moore, G. (2021). Cramming More Components onto Integrated Circuits (1965). In H. R. Lewis (Ed.), *Ideas That Created the Future: Classic Papers of Computer Science* (pp. 261–266). The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12274.003.0027>
- Morris, A., & Brading, H. (2007). E-literacy and the grey digital divide: A review with recommendations. *Journal of Information Literacy*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.11645/1.3.14>
- Morris, A., Goodman, J., & Brading, H. (2007). Internet use and non-use: views of older users. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 6(1), 43-57. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-006-0057-5>
- Mothe, C., & Nguyen-Thi, T. U. (2021). Does age diversity boost technological innovation? Exploring the moderating role of HR practices. *European Management Journal*, 39(6), 829-843. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2021.01.013>
- Mouw, T., & Kalleberg, A. L. (2010). Occupations and the Structure of Wage Inequality in the United States, 1980s to 2000s. *American Sociological Review*, 75(3), 402-431. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0003122410363564>
- Murawski, M., & Bick, M. (2017). Digital competences of the workforce – a research topic?. *Business Process Management Journal*, 23(3), 721-734. <https://doi.org/10.1108/bpmj-06-2016-0126>
- Nagel, L. (2020). The influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on the digital transformation of work. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 40(9/10), 861-875. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijssp-07-2020-0323>
- Nedelkoska, L., & Quintini, G. (2018). *Automation, skills use and training* (OECD Social Employment and Migration Working Papers No. 125). <https://doi.org/10.1787/2e2f4eea-en>
- O'Kane, L., Narasimhan, R., Nania, J., & Taska, B. (2020). *Digitalization in the German Labor Market: Analyzing Demand for Digital Skills in Job Vacancies* (TD/TNC 142.690). Bertelsmann Stiftung. <http://aei.pitt.edu/id/eprint/103213>
- Oberländer, M., Beinicke, A., & Bipp, T. (2020). Digital competencies: A review of the literature and applications in the workplace. *Computers & Education*, 146, 103752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103752>
- Oesch, D. (2013). *Occupational Change in Europe : How Technology and Education Transform the Job Structure*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199680962.001.0001>
- Oesch, D., & Piccitto, G. (2019). The Polarization Myth: Occupational Upgrading in Germany, Spain, Sweden, and the UK, 1992–2015. *Work and Occupations*, 46(4), 441–469. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888419860880>

- Oesch, D., & Rodríguez Menés, J. (2011). Upgrading or polarization? Occupational change in Britain, Germany, Spain and Switzerland, 1990–2008. *Socio-Economic Review*, 9(3), 503-531. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwq029>
- Oh, I.-S., Guay, R. P., Kim, K., Harold, C. M., Lee, J.-H., Heo, C.-G., & Shin, K.-H. (2014). Fit Happens Globally: A Meta-Analytic Comparison of the Relationships of Person-Environment Fit Dimensions with Work Attitudes and Performance Across East Asia, Europe, and North America. *Personnel Psychology*, 67(1), 99-152. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12026>
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development – OECD. (2006). *Live Longer, Work Longer*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264035881-en>
- OECD. (2015). *Does having digital skills really pay off?*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5js023r0wj9v-en>
- OECD. (2016). *New Skills for the Digital Economy*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jlwnkm2fc9x-en>
- OECD. (2017). *Getting Skills Right: Skills for Jobs Indicators*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264277878-en>
- OECD. (2019a). *OECD Employment Outlook 2019: The Future of Work*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/19991266>
- OECD. (2019b). *OECD Skills Outlook 2019. Thriving in a Digital World*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/e11c1c2d-en>
- OECD. (2019c). *OECD Skills Strategy 2019*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264313835-en>
- OECD. (2020). *OECD Digital Economy Outlook 2020*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/bb167041-en>
- OECD. (2021a). *Continuing Education and Training in Germany: Getting Skills Right*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1f552468-en>
- OECD. (2021b). *OECD Skills Outlook 2021. Learning for Life*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/0ae365b4-en>
- OECD. (2022a). *Employment rate* [indicator]. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1de68a9b-en>
- OECD. (2022b). *Old-age dependency ratio* [indicator]. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/e0255c98-en>
- OECD. (2022c). *Skills for the Digital Transition. Assessing Recent Trends Using Big Data*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/38c36777-en>

- OECD. (2023). Setting the stage: Approaches to assessing AI's impact. In OECD (Ed.), *Is Education Losing the Race with Technology?: AI's Progress in Maths and Reading*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/8ee0810f-en>
- Pajarinen, M., & Rouvinen, P. (2014). *Computerization Threatens One Third of Finnish Employment* (ETLA Briefs No. 22). <http://pub.etla.fi/ETLA-Muistio-Brief-22.pdf>
- Pajarinen, M., Rouvinen, P., & Ekeland, A. (2015). *Computerization Threatens One-Third of Finnish and Norwegian Employment* (ETLA Briefs No. 34). <http://pub.etla.fi/ETLA-Muistio-Brief-34.pdf>
- Petery, G. A., Wee, S., Dunlop, P. D., & Parker, S. K. (2020). Older workers and poor performance: Examining the association of age stereotypes with expected work performance quality. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 28(4), 510-521. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijisa.12309>
- Pfeifer, C., & Wagner, J. (2014). Is innovative firm behavior correlated with age and gender composition of the workforce? Evidence from a new type of data for German enterprises. *Journal for Labour Market Research*, 47(3), 223-231. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12651-013-0137-y>
- Pfeiffer, S. (2018). Die Quantifizierung von Nicht-Routine. *Arbeit*, 27(3), 213. <https://doi.org/10.1515/arbeit-2018-0018>
- Phillipson, C. (2008). Understanding the Baby Boom Generation: Comparative Perspectives. *International Journal of Ageing and Later Life*, 2(2), 7-11. <https://doi.org/10.3384/ijal.1652-8670.07227>
- Piroșcă, G. I., Șerban-Oprescu, G. L., Badea, L., Stanef-Puică, M.-R., & Valdebenito, C. R. (2021). Digitalization and Labor Market - A Perspective within the Framework of Pandemic Crisis. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(7), 2843-2857. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16070156>
- Pischke, J.-S. (2001). Continuous Training in Germany. *Journal of Population Economics*, 14(3), 523-548. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001480000040>
- Posthuma, R. A., & Campion, M. A. (2009). Age Stereotypes in the Workplace: Common Stereotypes, Moderators, and Future Research Directions. *Journal of Management*, 35(1), 158-188. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206308318617>
- Rifkin, J. (2011). *The Third Industrial Revolution: How Lateral Power Is Transforming Energy, the Economy, and the World*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Rouvinen, P. (2002). Characteristics of product and process innovators: some evidence from the Finnish innovation survey. *Applied Economics Letters*, 9(9), 575-580. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504850110108102>

- Rowe, J. W., & Kahn, R. L. (1997). Successful aging. *The Gerontologist*, 37(4), 433-440.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/37.4.433>
- Royuela, V., & Suriñach, J. (2013). Quality of Work and Aggregate Productivity. *Social Indicators Research*, 113(1), 37-66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-012-0081-1>
- Scheerder, A., van Deursen, A., & van Dijk, J. (2017). Determinants of Internet skills, uses and outcomes. A systematic review of the second- and third-level digital divide. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(8), 1607-1624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2017.07.007>
- Schneider, L. (2008). Alterung und technologisches Innovationspotential [Ageing and technological innovation potential]. *Zeitschrift für Bevölkerungswissenschaft*, 33(1), 37-54.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12523-008-0004-z>
- Schwab, K. (2017). *The fourth industrial revolution*. Penguin.
- Sheng, N., Fang, Y., Shao, Y., Alterman, V., & Wang, M. (2022). The Impacts of Digital Technologies on Successful Aging in Non-Work and Work Domains: An Organizing Taxonomy. *Work, Aging and Retirement*, 8(2), 198-207.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/workar/waac008>
- Siegrist, J., Wahrendorf, M., von dem Knesebeck, O., Jürges, H., & Börsch-Supan, A. (2006). Quality of work, well-being, and intended early retirement of older employees. Baseline results from the SHARE Study. *European Journal of Public Health*, 17(1), 62-68.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckl084>
- Sieverding, M., & Koch, S. C. (2009). (Self-)Evaluation of computer competence: How gender matters. *Computers & Education*, 52(3), 696-701.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2008.11.016>
- Soskice, D., & Hall, P. (2001). *Varieties of Capitalism: The Institutional Foundations of Comparative Advantage*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30040740>
- Sostero, M., & Tolan, S. (2022). *Digital skills for all? From computer literacy to AI skills in online job advertisements* (JRC Working Papers on Labour, Education and Technology, No. JRC130291). European Commission. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-11/JRC130291_Digital%20skills%20for%20all.pdf
- Sousa, M. J., & Wilks, D. (2018). Sustainable Skills for the World of Work in the Digital Age. *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 35(4), 399-405.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/sres.2540>
- Spitz-Oener, A. (2006). Technical Change, Job Tasks, and Rising Educational Demands: Looking outside the Wage Structure. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 24(2), 235-270.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/499972>

- The World Bank. (2022a). *Fertility rate, total (births per woman)* [indicator]. The World Bank. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.DYN.TFRT.IN>
- The World Bank. (2022b). *Life expectancy at birth, total (years)* [indicator]. The World Bank. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.DYN.LE00.IN>
- Tijdens, K. G., De Ruijter, E., & De Ruijter, J. (2014). Comparing tasks of 160 occupations across eight European countries. *Employee Relations*, 36(2), 110-127. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-05-2013-0046>
- Tinbergen, J. (1975). *Income Distribution: Analysis and Policies*. Elsevier.
- Trenerry, B., Chng, S., Wang, Y., Suhaila, Z. S., Lim, S. S., Lu, H. Y., & Oh, P. H. (2021). Preparing Workplaces for Digital Transformation: An Integrative Review and Framework of Multi-Level Factors. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.620766>
- Tully-Wilson, C., Bojack, R., Millear, P. M., Stallman, H. M., Allen, A., & Mason, J. (2021). Self-perceptions of aging: A systematic review of longitudinal studies. *Psychology and Aging*, 36(7), 773-789. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pag0000638>
- Ulfert-Blank, A.-S., & Schmidt, I. (2022). Assessing digital self-efficacy: Review and scale development. *Computers & Education*, 191, 104626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104626>
- United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs; Population Division - UNDESA. (2022a). Median age of population [indicator]. United Nations. <https://population.un.org/dataportal/home?df=2b49f1c0-f20c-4164-a595-05122ca51b65>
- UNDESA. (2022b). Population ages 65 and above (% of total population) [indicator]. United Nations. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.65UP.TO.ZS?locations=DE>
- Valenduc, G., & Vendramin, P. (2017). Digitalisation, between disruption and evolution. *Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research*, 23(2), 121-134. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1024258917701379>
- Van Dalen, H. P., Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. (2009). Dealing with older workers in Europe: a comparative survey of employers' attitudes and actions. *Journal of European Social Policy*, 19(1), 47-60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958928708098523>
- van Deursen, A., & van Dijk, J. (2011). Internet skills and the digital divide. *New Media & Society*, 13(6), 893-911. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444810386774>
- Vasilescu, M. D., Serban, A. C., Dimian, G. C., Aceleanu, M. I., & Picatoste, X. (2020). Digital divide, skills and perceptions on digitalisation in the European Union—Towards a smart labour market. *PloS one*, 15(4), e0232032. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0232032>

- Vignoles, A., Galindo-Rueda, F., & Feinstein, L. (2004). The Labour Market Impact of Adult Education and Training: A Cohort Analysis. *Scottish Journal of Political Economy*, 51(2), 266-280. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0036-9292.2004.00306.x>
- Violante, G. L. (2016). Skill-Biased Technical Change. In *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics*. Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-349-95121-5_2388-1
- Weber, J., Angerer, P., & Müller, A. (2019). Individual consequences of age stereotypes on older workers: A systematic review. *Zeitschrift für Gerontologie und Geriatrie*, 52(S3), 188-205. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00391-019-01506-6>
- Wegman, L. A., Hoffman, B. J., Carter, N. T., Twenge, J. M., & Guenole, N. (2018). Placing Job Characteristics in Context: Cross-Temporal Meta-Analysis of Changes in Job Characteristics Since 1975. *Journal of Management*, 44(1), 352-386. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206316654545>
- Williams, M., & Bol, T. (2018). Occupations and the wage structure: The role of occupational tasks in Britain. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 53, 16-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2017.11.003>
- Wolter, F., & Schiener, J. (2009). Einkommenseffekte beruflicher Weiterbildung. Empirische Analysen auf Basis des Mikrozensus-Panels [Income effects of vocational further training – Empirical analyses based on german mikrozensus panel data]. *Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 61(1), 90-117. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-009-0043-z>
- Wotschack, P. (2019). Exploring the (Missing) Gender Training Gap in Germany: The Role of Organizations and Sectors in Continuing Training Participation. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 26(3), 444-474. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/ixy021>
- Wotschack, P. (2020). Drivers of training participation in low skilled jobs: the role of 'voice', technology, innovation and labor shortages in German companies. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 24(3), 245-264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijtd.12195>
- Xie, H., Fang, Y., Wang, M., Liu, J., & Lv, A. (2023). Providing Digital Technology Training as a Way to Retain Older Workers: The Importance of Perceived Usefulness and Growth Need. *Work, Aging and Retirement*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/workar/waad004>
- Yashiro, N., Kyyrä, T., Hwang, H., & Tuomala, J. (2021). *Technology, labour market institutions and early retirement: Evidence from Finland* (IZA Discussion Paper No. 13990). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3758691>

7. Appendices

7.1. Publications

In section 7.1 the full papers of this publication-based dissertation are presented. The supplemental material of the papers can be found in section 7.2 in the appendix of this dissertation. Please note that in sake of the readability of this dissertation some linguistic and formatting adjustments have been made. Consequently, the papers presented here are not fully congruent with the published or submitted papers. The minor adjustments include the adaptation from British English to American English, the numbering of the sections, figures, tables, and footnotes.

I. Digitalization, Gender and Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

Authors: Lisa Katharina Kortmann, Stefan Stuth, Julia Simonson

Accepted: July 2023 / Published online: January 2024

Journal: Soziale Welt (2024) 74(4): 589–613

Abstract: Digitalization places new demands on employees working in changing occupations. To undertake the adaptation to new requirements further training is one central strategy of updating and building new skills – especially for older employees. Digitalization in the world of work has been shown to affect male and female employees differently. However, little is known about the interrelationship between digitalization in occupations and training. This gap is addressed by investigating (1) the association of training participation and the extent of digitalization in their occupations of employees in the second half of working life and (2) whether there is a gender difference in this association. In addition, these questions are investigated regarding the employee's desire to participate in future training. Using data from the German Ageing Survey, logistic regressions are applied to control for sociodemographic, labour market and work-related characteristics of employees aged 43 to 65 in Germany. Positive associations between a change in the level of digitalization in occupations and (the desire for) training participation are found. The more pronounced the change in the digitalization level in occupations, the more female employees seem to be disadvantaged in training participation compared to men.

Keywords: Digitalization; Gender; German Ageing Survey; Older Employees; Skills and Training

1. Introduction

Digitalization has and continuously will alter the world of work, placing new occupational demands on employees (Acemoglu & Autor, 2011; Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003; Frey & Osborne, 2017). In view of rapidly changing skill demands due

to digitalisation²⁰ further training becomes increasingly important to avoid skill mismatches in order to maintain employees' productivity and employability (Brunello & Wruuck, 2021). This particularly affects employees in their second half of working life, since their skillset is more likely to become obsolete or misfit new requirements compared to younger employees, because digital skills were not a regular part of their initial occupational education and training. Indeed, digital skills seem to be negatively associated with age (Curtarelli et al., 2017; Hargittai, 2002; Morris & Brading, 2007; Vasilescu et al., 2020). Moreover, older workers assess their digital skills worse compared to younger workers (Czaja et al., 2006; Vasilescu et al., 2020). Employers hold a similar assessment of older and younger employees' digital skills (Van Dalen, Henkens, & Schippers, 2009). However, investments in building new skills may be less attractive for older employees in light of impending retirement.

In addition to digitalisation, the demographic trend of an increasingly ageing workforce puts the German welfare state and labour market under pressure, as the share of labour market participants in the total population decreases, the average age of labour market participants increases and shortages of skilled workers in certain industries or occupations rise (Buchholz et al., 2011). To counteract these developments, the German government has implemented some political measures to prevent early retirement and promote lifelong learning (e. g. the gradual increase of the statutory retirement age (§ 7a SGB II) or the launching of the national skills strategy (BMBF, 2021)). However, such political measures will fall short, if opportunities for training participation are not equally distributed among employees and job-related training is often discussed as an important factor in persisting gender differences in the labour market (Dämmrich, Kosyakova, & Blossfeld, 2016; Havet & Sofer, 2008).

If training is paramount to address challenges of digitalisation of work and the aging workforce it is important to shed light on whether male and female employees in their second half of working life have equal opportunities to adapt their skills to new

²⁰ The world of work has been transformed by technological progress ever since. However, the recent process of technological transformation, namely digitalisation, is characterised by its extraordinarily high speed of innovations and the wide range of tasks that can be substituted or changed by new, digital technologies (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). In the literature, digitisation is even regarded as having a disruptive or revolutionary character (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; Hirsch-Kreinsen & Wienzek, 2019; Murawski & Bick, 2017; Schwab, 2017).

requirements. From a gender-perspective, current research views digitalisation and related transformation processes in the world of work as a 'window of opportunity' for a renegotiation of gender power relations and as a risk of exacerbating gender differences (Carstensen, 2020a; Howcroft & Rubery, 2019; Kohlrausch & Weber, 2021; Krieger-Boden & Sorgner, 2018; Piasna & Drahokoupil, 2017; Wajcman, 2004, 2009). On the one hand, digitalisation is viewed as an opportunity to empower women and de-segregate labour markets. Digital communication tools may enable and facilitate the reconciliation of paid and unpaid labour, possibly paving the way for women to enter new employment forms or occupations (Carstensen, 2020a). However, childcare responsibilities are found to be negatively associated with training participation for female but not for male employees (Dieckhoff & Steiber, 2011). On the other hand, digitalisation may exacerbate gender differences in the labour market. New jobs, employment forms or working conditions that raised in course of digitalisation, like 'gig' or 'platform work' and 'working from home', may additionally disadvantage women (Piasna & Drahokoupil, 2017), if they are similar to non-standard employment, which provides poor job quality, low employment security, missing working time regulations, low wages, and low training participation (Brehmer & Seifert, 2008; Grund & Martin, 2012). To date, women are more often engaged in non-standard employment than men, which is often attributed to their greater involvement in unpaid work compared to their male counterparts (Bachmann, Felder, & Tamm, 2020). In addition, if a woman in a household is working from home, the unequal distribution of care work responsibilities is even found to increase (Carstensen, 2020b). Irrespective of the previous researchers take on digitalisation as a chance or as a risk for women in the labour market, there is a broad consensus that training is the central strategy in adapting employees' skills to new and changing demands (BMBS, 2021; Goldin & Katz, 2008; OECD, 2019, 2021; Oesch, 2013).

Digitalisation processes affect employees differently as only some occupational tasks can be substituted by digital technologies, while others can be complemented or are

not affected at all by digitalisation (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003).²¹ Indeed, the task content within occupations has changed remarkably over the last years (Atalay et al., 2020; Spitz-Oener, 2006). In particular, employees in occupations that strongly rely on advanced technologies seem to have experienced more changes in their task profiles (Spitz-Oener, 2006). Studies on automation risks respectively the share of routine-tasks in occupations find lower training participation among workers with high automation risks respectively a high share of routine tasks in their occupations (Görlitz & Tamm, 2015; Ioannidou & Parma, 2021; Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018; OECD, 2019). Literature examining training participation over time finds increasing participation rates in Germany (Becker, 2019; BMBF, 2021). However, it is not clear if this trend is induced by digitalisation. Literature that directly examines the association between the penetration of digital technologies in occupations and training suggests a positive association between employees' training participation and digital technologies in the company (Gashi, Pugh, & Adnett, 2010; Lukowski, Baum, & Mohr, 2021; Wotschack, 2020). Lukowski, Baum and Mohr (2021) report that a higher share of digital technology users in firms is associated with higher training provision. Gashi, Pugh and Adnett (2010) observed higher training intensity when new technologies are introduced to the workplace, and when workplaces have experienced difficulties recruiting skilled workers. Wotschack (2020) finds investments in information and communication technologies (ICTs) and modern production or service technologies associated with a higher probability of firms to invest in training. However, he also finds that higher training participation rates are not to be found among low skilled workers. These findings complement the more general findings that lower education or lower skills of employees are related with lower training participation (Cedefop, 2016; Grund & Martin, 2012; OECD, 2021). Moreover, we are not aware of a study directly examining digitalisation and gender differences in training participation.

In the literature on training in general there is no consensus on whether there is a gender-training gap or not (Wotschack, 2019). Some studies find that women are more

²¹ It is important to highlight, that digital technologies are not implemented whenever technical feasibility for task substitution is given (Dengler & Matthes, 2018; Valenduc & Vendramin, 2017). Other factors such as ethical considerations, the relative advantage of human labour, or legal issues can hinder the introduction of digital technologies.

likely than men to participate in training (BMBF, 2021 (GER); Cedefop, 2016 (EU); Jones, Latreille, & Sloane, 2008 (GBR)), some find that women are less likely to participate in training (Aisa, Gonzalez-Alvarez, & Larramona, 2016 (ESP); Burgard, 2012 (GER); Dieckhoff & Steiber, 2011 (EU); Pischke, 2001 (GER); Wozny & Schneider, 2014 (EU)), and other studies find no gender training gap at all (BMBF, 2019 (GER)).²²

In recent literature the importance of organisational characteristics, like firm size or presence of human resource strategies, as determinants for training participation is emphasized (Grund & Martin, 2012; Wotschack, 2020). Large enterprises may profit from larger financial and personal resources and may therefore be able to provide employees better with structured internal training programmes. Also working in the public sector is related with higher training participation compared to working in the private sector (Schömann & Becker, 1995). In Germany women are more often employed in the public sector than men (DBB Beamtenbund und Tarifunion, 2021). However, highly digitalised occupations – like occupations in the ICT sector – are associated with a higher training provision but are predominantly male-dominated (O'Kane et al., 2020; OECD, 2018).

Therefore, this article aims to answer the following questions: (1.a) is participation in training higher among employees aged 43 to 65 years working in occupations with a higher degree of digitalisation? And (1.b) does participation in training differ between men and women in relation to the degree of digitalisation in occupations? Furthermore, regarding employees' preferences for training participation: 2.a) is there a greater desire for training among employees in the second half of working life working in occupations with a greater degree of digitalisation? And 2.b) do male and female employees differ in this regard?

In this article, training is defined as job-related continuing vocational training or retraining of any kind, regardless of financing source, duration or time frame. This includes courses, seminars or other events serving employees' continuing vocational training or retraining. It does not include learning activities that are part of an

²² These varying findings – even for Germany – may result from varying definitions, operationalisations and analyses of employees' participation in training.

educational programme or learning on the job. The focus is on employees in their second half of working life, which is defined by the age range 40 to 65 years, to focus on employees whose initial education and training is probably outdated with regard to the digital technologies in their occupations.

To investigate training participation, it is necessary to look at employees' and employers' perspectives. One theoretical approach that does that is the human capital theory (HCT). For employees, training is interpreted in HCT as an investment in their human capital – their economically viable skills and knowledge (Becker, 1975; Lewis et al., 2008). Employee training improves or maintains productivity and increases wages and job security. To avoid decreasing or stagnating productivity and skills shortages, employers should provide their employees with opportunities for training when employees' occupations become more digitalised. Similarly, employees should be interested in counteracting a devaluation of their human capital that is likely to progress faster in more digital occupations. However, educational decisions are not solely the result of rational cost-benefit considerations, because cost-benefit considerations are heavily influenced by employees' social class and class-specific lifestyles and dispositions (Boudon, 1974; Bourdieu & Passeron, 1971; Breen & Goldthorpe, 1997; Esser, 1999). Class-related normative values, privileges or constraints related to successful participation in training may shape employees' training decisions and aspirations. For the abovementioned reasons, it can be assumed that training participation and willingness to participate in training is higher for employees working in occupations that are digitalised to a greater extent.

(H1.a) The higher the extent of digitalisation in an occupation, the greater the likelihood of training participation.

(H2.a) The likelihood of desiring training participation increases, the higher the degree of digitalisation in an employees' occupation.

Furthermore, the HCT assumes different investment rationales for men and women due to differences in time allocation (Becker, 1975). Women in Germany are (still) mainly responsible for the majority of unpaid house- and care-work. This imbalance in the provision of unpaid care work still exists among men and women in the second half of life (Ehrlich & Kelle, 2019; Klaus & Vogel, 2019). Hence, they have less time

available for paid work, training and experience more care-related career interruptions. Employers might therefore be less inclined to invest in the human capital of female employees because of the lower probability and longer amortisation periods until investments in training will pay off, compared to men. Taste-based or statistical discrimination may reinforce employers' gendered training preferences (Arrow, 1974; Becker, 1971; Phelps, 1972), which may also be reinforced if the training includes digital skills. Therefore, HCT expects women to show weaker (desire for) training participation. A lower probability for women to participate in employer-provided training might also have its origin in women's preferences. Due to the higher probability of career interruptions, women tend to invest in general skills which are applicable in diverse settings and have low decay rates (Becker, 1991; Estevez-Abe, 2005; Polachek, 1981). Some studies indicate that embodied gender stereotypes cause women to have a lower assessment of their digital competencies and to be less open to new technologies (Cai, Fan, & Du, 2017; Initiative D21, 2021). Therefore, women's willingness to participate in training in highly digitalised occupations is assumed to be lower than men's.

(H1.b) Women experience a flatter increase in the likelihood of training participation than men do with increasing digitalisation in an occupation.

(H2.b) The increase in the likelihood of the desire to participate in training is flatter for women than for men with increasing digitalisation in an occupation.

2. Method

2.1. Data and Sample

To answer the research questions, data from the 2017 wave of the German Ageing Survey (Deutscher Alterssurvey; DEAS) was used (Klaus et al., 2017). The DEAS is a cross-sectional and longitudinal survey based on computer-assisted personal interviews and is representative for the population aged 40 and above living in Germany. It contains rich information on the living and working situations, as well as attitudes or wishes regarding different aspects of life of people in the second half of life aged 40 years and above. Information on the extent of digitalisation in employees' occupations came from an external source and was matched with DEAS using the

International Standard Classification of Occupations 2008 (ISCO-08). Digitalisation was measured in two ways: first, the relative level of digitalisation of employees' occupations in 2018 and second, the change in the digitalisation level of employee's occupations experienced between 2014 and 2018, determined by Bertelsmann and Burning Glass Technologies for Germany (O'Kane et al., 2020).

The sample contained employees aged 43 to 65 working full- or part-time or in irregular or marginal employment in Germany at the time of the interview. Therefore, self-employed people, civil servants²³, liberal professions, farmers and foresters were excluded from the sample.²⁴ Employees who had missing information on variables considered in the analysis were also excluded. The final sample comprised $n = 1,020$ employees, whereof 47.53 percent were women, 40.29 percent had a high educational level and the mean age was 52 years ($SD_{age} = 5.469$) (see tab. 1).²⁵

2.2. Analyses

Logistic regression models with maximum likelihood estimations were applied, and partial regression coefficients in log odds metric were reported. The log odds metric enables the interpretation of the direction and significance of the coefficients. To consider whether the results for employees working within the same occupations are more similar than those for employees working in different occupations, clustered standard errors for occupations (ISCO-08, 4 digit) were applied. Associations were reported as statistically significant at a 95 percent confidence level. To determine gender and digitalisation's role in the (desire) for training participation, three models were estimated. (1) The first model controlled for compositional effects by considering several control variables. (2) In the second model, an interaction term for gender and the digitalisation level was included, as gender differences were assumed to be more pronounced in more digitalised occupations. (3) The third model additionally controlled for an interaction effect of gender and the change in the digitalisation level. For the

²³ In Germany civil servants are not regular employees because they are subject to special working conditions rooted in the Basic Law (Art. 33 para. 4 & 5 GG). Analyses including the group of civil servants have led to similar findings to those presented in this article.

²⁴ Since the DEAS 2017 is a panel wave only and the last refreshment sample was drawn in 2014, the youngest employees in the sample are 43 years old.

²⁵ The final sample to analyse the employees' desire to participate in training comprised $n = 1,018$. For the sake of clarity and since there are no major differences, the sample description refers to the analysis sample for training participation ($n = 1,020$).

interaction terms, marginal effects were calculated and plotted (as suggested in Brambor, Clark and Golder (2006)) to illustrate the effect of gender in dependence of the (change in the) digitalisation level on employees' (desire for) training participation.²⁶

Table 1: Sample Description.

Variable	Range	Categories	Mean / %	SD
participation in training	0 1	no	36.48	0.019
		yes	63.52	
desire to participate in training in future ^a	0 1	no	30.90	0.018
		yes	69.10	
digitalisation level	0–97		52.93	16.837
change in digitalisation level	-13–32		14.74	6.989
gender	0 1	male	52.47	0.019
		female	47.53	
age (years)	43–65		51.86	5.470
residency	0 1	West	85.49	0.010
		East	14.51	
high education	0 1	no	59.70	0.019
		yes	40.19	
gender composition of occupations	1 2 3	female dominated	23.81	0.016
		mixed	39.55	0.019
		male dominated	36.64	0.019
responsible for major part of housework ^b	0 1	no	55.28	0.019
		yes	44.72	
young children in same household ^b	0 1	no	83.52	0.016
		yes	16.48	
working time (h/week)	2–70		37.86	10.982
small enterprise	0 1	no	78.41	0.015
		yes	21.59	
public service	0 1	no	79.63	0.015
		yes	20.37	
years till planned end of work (residuals from regression on age)	-11.5–35.3		-0.27	4.197
career interruption ^b (years)	0–25		2.07	3.820
occupational change during the last 3 years	0 1	no	75.26	0.017
		yes	24.74	

Note: SD = standard deviation. ^a n = 1,018. ^b information from DEAS 2014.

Source: DEAS 2017 (weighted); n = 1,020.

²⁶ An extensive variable description and regression diagnostics are reported in the appendix (see tab. 4, 7–9 & figure 5 in the appendix).

To facilitate interpretation, and in line with Mayerl and Urban (2019), all independent variables were mean centred, except gender and the change in the digitalisation level which already contained a meaningful 0 point. Moreover, all continuous variables were standardised. Whereas most variables were based on the 2017 DEAS wave, some control variables, such as responsibility for the major part of housework, were taken from the 2014 DEAS wave, because they were not time-invariant and might have been decisive in employees' training participation in the following years.²⁷ Additional analyses were performed (1) using a randomly drawn subsample (80%), (2) a subsample of 50- to 65-year-old employees, (3) excluding five occupations with the highest digitalization levels, (4) and excluding five occupations with the highest changes in the digitalization levels. The additional analyses confirming the robustness of the findings from model 3 (see tab. 11 & 12 in the appendix).

2.3. Dependent Variables

The first dependent variable measures whether employees *participated in at least one training* over the previous three years. Training encompasses all kinds of training that are job or occupation-related. The second dependent variable is the employees' *desire to participate in training in the future*. Similar to the first dependent variable, this only refers to job- or occupation-related training. Nearly two thirds of employees (63.5 percent) stated that they had participated in at least one training during the previous three years. More than two thirds (69.1 percent) of employees wished to participate in training in the future (see tab. 1).

2.4. Predictor Variables

Digitalisation and gender were central predictor variables. Digitalisation was measured by two variables: the relative *digitalisation level* of occupations in 2018 and by the *change in the digitalisation level* in the occupations between 2014 and 2018. The digitalisation level indicates, for example, in which occupations the most / least digital skills were demanded by employers in 2018. The change in the digitalisation level

²⁷ Find correlation matrixes and cross tabulations of the dependent variables separated for gender in the appendix (tab. 7–9).

indicates which occupations experienced an increase or decrease in the digitalisation level between 2014 and 2018.^{28,29}

The digitalisation measures are based on job postings scraped from online job boards and company websites (O'Kane et al., 2020).³⁰ A machine-learning model was used to derive data from the job posting text, such as information on occupations or skills. Duplicate postings were removed. The scraped data contains information on 3,111 distinct skills assigned to five skill types ranging from “not digital skills” to “ICT technical skills”. To acknowledge differences in digital proficiency among skills, weights were assigned to the skill types. Based on this data, the digitalisation level was built by summing up the average recall for every weighted skill for each occupation, taking the logarithm, and normalising the values to range between 0 and 100. The change in the digitalisation level ranges from -13 to 33, with 0 indicating no relative change in the digitalisation level between 2014 and 2017.³¹ The average digitalisation level in the sample is 52.76 (SD_{DL} : 16.85) and the average change in the digitalisation level is 14.84 (SD_{CDL} : 7.13) (see tab. 1). The digitisation data were provided by Bertelsmann and Burning Glass Technologies (O'Kane et al., 2020) and matched to DEAS data using the information on employees' occupations (ISCO-08, 4 digit).³² In recent years, scientific interest in job ads data has increased (Mezzanzanica & Mercorio, 2019) and is already used in numerous studies (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2020; APEC, 2020; Azar et al., 2020; Deming & Noray, 2020; Nania et al., 2019).

²⁸ To ensure the comparability over time, the 2014 digitalisation value was scaled to be in terms of the 2018 value (see O'Kane et al., 2020).

²⁹ For an overview of occupations in the analysis sample with the highest/lowest (change in the) DL see table 13 in the appendix. For the distribution of women and men across occupations' DL and CDL see figure 6 in the appendix.

³⁰ The job postings have been found to be comparable to EUROSTAT data on the total employment distribution by occupation, industry and region for 2014 and 2017 in Germany (O'Kane et al., 2020).

³¹ For details on sensitivity tests ran for the skill weights and the construction of the digitisation measures see (Cammeraat & Squicciarini, 2021; Colombo, Mercorio, & Mezzanzanica, 2019; O'Kane et al., 2020).

³² If occupational information of employees was not available on a four-digit level, the average digitalisation levels for the corresponding occupational major groups were linked to the data.

Employees' *gender* is based on interviewer's assessments during the face-to-face interviews and added to the analyses as variable that differentiates between "0" for "male" and "1" for "female".^{33,34}

2.5. Control Variables

Besides the DEAS-sampling variables, age and region, it is controlled for individuals' education, household responsibilities and several occupational and work-related characteristics. *Age* was measured in years and added as a continuous variable. The employees' *place of residence* was added as a binary variable, with "0" as "living in East Germany" and "1" as "living in West Germany".

The choice of the other control variables was based on theoretical considerations and the existing literature mentioned above. The educational level of employees was considered by adding a binary variable, with "1" for high education (ISCED 5–6) and "0" for low or middle levels of education (ISCED 0–4). Medium and low levels of education could not be differentiated as too few employees reported a low education (ISCED 0–2). To control for gendered differences in care responsibilities, it was considered whether *young children below the age of 13 lived in the same household (1) or not (0)*. To control for a second gendered domain of time use beyond time spent at paid work, a dummy variable with information on *housework responsibilities* was added. All respondents who are either living with other persons in a household but state that they are responsible for the majority of housework, or respondents living alone, were coded as "1". *Working hours* per week including overtime was added as continuous variable to the analyses. Data on the *gender composition of occupations* in Germany was derived from (Stuth, 2022), and is originally based on the 2015 German micro-census. The gender composition of occupations is introduced as a categorical variable using mixed-occupations as the base category. In this article, an occupation is defined as female-dominated if the overall share of male employees is below 30 percent, and as male-dominated if the share of female employees is below 30

³³ In the few cases where the interviewers were not sure about the gender of the respondents, the interviewers asked the respondents directly and the respondents self-reported their gender.

³⁴ Starting with the 2020 survey wave the German Ageing Survey offers a more distinct gender differentiation in "male/female/diverse".

percent.³⁵ *Company size* was considered by a dummy variable with “1” for small enterprises with no more than 20 employees. To distinguish between employment in the public or in the private sector a dummy variable with “1” for working in the public sector was added.

The intended remaining time horizon of employees in the labour market was controlled for by employees’ *planned number of years till the end of work*. To avoid correlation with age, the residuals from regressing the stated years till the end of work on age were determined and used as a control variable. Employees’ *career interruptions* were indicated in years and added as continuous control variable. Lastly, a dummy variable indicating if an employee had *changed his or her job* during the previous three years was added, with “1” indicating professional changes.

3. Results

No association between training and the digitalisation level and no gender differences were obtained in model 1, controlling for compositional effects underlying the workforce (see tab. 2).³⁶ For an extensive overview of the results including all control variables, see table 5 in the appendix.

The included interaction effect of gender and digitalisation level was not significant in model 2 or in model 3, but a significant negative interaction effect of the change in the digitalisation level and gender was found in model 3 ($b = -0.418$; $p = 0.017$; $SE = 0.175$) (see tab. 2, fig. 1 and 2).³⁷ For average female employees, the likelihood of training participation decreased if the change in the digitalisation level increased about one standard deviation. An average woman working in an occupation that

³⁵ These thresholds are commonly used in other studies with a focus on the German labour market (Busch, 2013; Dengler & Tisch, 2020).

³⁶ A model containing no control variables except the DEAS sampling variables of age and residency was estimated for employees’ training participation as well as for their desire to participate in training. The model predicting training participation was not significant. The model predicting employees’ desire for training indicated a positive association with the digitalisation level ($b = 0.198$; $SE = 0.095$; $p = 0.037$) and a negative association with age ($b = -0.562$; $SE = 0.086$; $p = 0.000$); a negative association for gender was found at 90% confidence level ($b = -0.264$; $SE = 0.154$; $p = 0.086$).

³⁷ While the coefficient of DL is not significant, the direction is positive. For the interaction of gender and DL the coefficient is not significant and close to zero (see tab. 2 & 5). A larger sample could shed light on possible associations.

experienced a negative or low change in the digitalisation level had a higher likelihood of training participation than men; however, for high changes in the digitalisation level in occupations, women had a lower likelihood of training participation than men (see fig. 2, left)³⁸. The more pronounced the change in the digitalisation level in occupations, the lower the likelihood of training participation for average female employees; for average male employees it increased. For the main effects of the change in the digitalisation level ($b = 0.270$; $p = 0.038$; $SE = 0.130$) and gender ($b = 1.011$; $p = 0.026$; $SE = 0.455$), positive associations with training participation were found (see tab. 2).

Table 2: Digitalisation and Participation in Training of Employees in Their Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Digitalisation Level	0.134 (0.122)	0.154 (0.124)	0.148 (0.120)
Gender (ref.: male)	0.109 (0.205)	0.111 (0.206)	1.012 (0.455)
Female		-0.039 (0.213)	0.003 (0.195)
Gender # Digitalisation Level			0.270 (0.130)
Change in Digitalisation Level			-0.418 (0.175)
Gender # Change in Digitalisation Level			
Constant	0.528 (0.183)	0.525 (0.178)	-0.065 (0.357)
n	1,020	1,020	1,020
Prob. $>\chi^2$	0.000	0.000	0.000
R ² _{Adj. McFadden}	0.078	0.078	0.085
AIC	1,274.595	1,276.512	1,271.043

Note: Control variables: age, residency, education, housework, young child in same household, gender composition of occupations, working hours, small enterprise, public service, years till end of work, career interruptions, occupational change.

b = partial logistic regression coefficients (log odds). SE = clustered standard errors (by occupation). Bold: significant at 95% level.

Source: DEAS 2017.

³⁸ Confidence intervals (CI) are not reported in fig 1–4 for the margins-plots on the left. The computation of CIs on predicted values for the groups of men and women would be misleading, since overlapping CIs do not necessarily imply that there are no significant differences (Cumming & Finch, 2005; Tan & Tan, 2010). As suggested in Tan and Tan (2010), the use of CIs is more intuitive if they are computed for the difference between two groups (see fig 1–4, right). Here the difference between men and women is significant if the CIs do not include the value 0.

Figure 1: Interaction Between Digitalisation Level and Gender on Training Participation.

Source: DEAS 2017.

Figure 2: Interaction Between the Change in the Digitalisation Level and Gender on Training Participation.

Source: DEAS 2017.

Regarding employees' desire to participate in future training, in the first model controlling for compositional effects, no significant association for the digitalisation level was found for the average male employee and no gender differences were found regarding the desire to participate in training. The added interaction terms of the

digitalisation level and gender in the second and third model were also not significant (see fig. 3).³⁹

Table 3: Digitalisation and the Desire to Participate in Training of Employees in Their Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
digitalisation level	0.151 (0.089)	0.127 (0.107)	0.126 (0.110)
gender (ref.: male)	-0.171 (0.206)	-0.172 (0.207)	0.347 (0.367)
female		0.048 (0.170)	-0.006 (0.178)
gender # digitalisation level			0.383 (0.115)
change in digitalisation level			-0.225 (0.138)
gender # change in digitalisation level			
constant	0.836 (0.178)	0.838 (0.177)	-0.063 (0.315)
n	1,018	1,018	1,018
Prob. > χ^2	0.000	0.000	0.000
R ² _{Adj. McFadden}	0.103	0.103	0.113
AIC	1,217.473	1,219.360	1,209.529

Note: Control variables: age; residency; education; housework; young child in same household; gender composition of occupations; working hours; small enterprise; public service; years till end of work; career interruptions; occupational change.

b = partial logistic regression coefficients (log odds). SE = clustered standard errors (by occupation). Bold: significant at 95% level.

Source: DEAS 2017.

Likewise, the interaction term of the change in the digitalisation level and gender (added in the third model) and the main effect for gender were not significant (see fig. 4). However, the main effect of the change in the digitalisation level was positively associated with the desire for training participation (b = 0.383; p = 0.001; SE = 0.115) (see tab. 3). The more pronounced the change in the digitalisation level in employees' occupations, the greater the desire for male employees to participate in training. Complete results are available in table 6 in the appendix.

³⁹ Albeit not significant, the direction of the coefficient of DL is positive, whereas the coefficients of the interaction the CDL with gender are not significant, but negative. The interaction of gender and DL is not significant and close to zero.

Figure 3: Interaction Between the Digitalisation Level and Gender on Employees' Desire to Participate in Training.

Source: DEAS 2017.

Figure 4: Interaction Between the Change in the Digitalisation Level and Gender on Employees' Desire to Participate in Training.

Source: DEAS 2017.

4. Discussion

Overall, the findings suggest that the likelihood of training participation increases for male employees if their occupations had experienced a more pronounced change in the digitalisation level over previous years. This finding for male employees is in line with hypothesis H1.a. It can be assumed that changes in the digitalisation level in occupations are associated with changing occupational requirements for employees. Training could be one measure to adapt the skills and knowledge of employees in their second half of working life to such altered requirements. However, in comparison to

their male counterparts, female employees show a decreasing likelihood of training participation if their occupation was subject to a strong increase in the digitalisation level over previous years. Furthermore, the more pronounced a change in the digitalisation level in occupations is, the greater seems the decrease in women's likelihood of participating in training to be. These findings are not in line with hypotheses H1.a and H1.b. In order to explain the lower likelihood of training participation among women working in occupations with high changes in the digitalisation level it seems not sound to draw on HCT or segregation theories, since gender differences in several aspects of time allocation, education and segregation effects in the labour market are controlled for. Gender stereotypes and role models appear to be potential explanations for the findings. Female employees might be regarded as less capable in acquiring new digital skills or their self-efficiency regarding digital competencies might be regarded as lower than that of male employees. However, conclusions have to be drawn carefully, since the reasons for non-participation in training are unknown. A higher digitalisation level was not associated with a higher likelihood of training participation, and no gender differences were found to that regard. Therefore, hypotheses H1.a and H1.b were inconsistent with the findings regarding the digitalisation level. One possible explanation is that digital skills were a criterion in hiring decisions in these occupations or that digital skills were acquired on the job.

However, in contrast to the theoretical considerations, a higher training participation was found for women in occupations that experienced a low or small change in the digitalisation level. This reversed gender training gap has also been found in some previous studies (BMBF, 2021; Cedefop, 2016; Jones, Latreille, & Sloane, 2008). In this context it is often highlighted that the female employment rate is still considerably lower than the male employment rate, and female employees might be characterised by some factors not considered in this analysis, such as high career orientation. Furthermore, the analysis levels out differences, such as in working hours, care responsibilities, sector or education. Since employees' desire for future training participation was also examined, some implications can be derived to explain the gender difference in relation to the change in the digitalisation level in training.

Employees working in occupations that have experienced a more pronounced change in the digitalisation level seem to be more likely to express the desire for training participation. For the digitalisation level, no significant effect was found. Therefore, the findings are consistent with hypothesis H2.a with regard to the change in the digitalisation level, but not the digitalisation level. Employees' willingness to participate in training might be higher in occupations with more pronounced changes in the digitalisation level since they might have experienced a skill mismatch. In addition, transformation processes in occupations due to digitalisation may especially affect older employees, since their initial vocational education or training is likely to be longer ago than that of younger employees, and skill mismatches have had more time to grow. The findings do not reveal gender differences in the desire to participate in training, nor in relation to the digitalisation level or change in the digitalisation level. Therefore, the findings are inconsistent with H2.b. These findings, along with the findings on gender differences in training participation, allow for different explanations. They may indicate that employers disadvantage women working in occupations that have experienced a strong increase in the demand for digital skills. Another possible explanation is that women desire to participate in training in general but are not appealed by existing training offers.⁴⁰

As it is usual, also this study comes with some potential limitations that have to be mentioned. Unfortunately, it was not possible to control for whether training was financed by the employer, the state, the employee, or by a mixed source. The financing source, however, has been found to differ systematically among the genders. While women are found to be more likely than men or equally likely to participate in training that is not financed by the employer (e. g. self-financed or state-financed), they are less likely to participate in employer-financed training (Aisa, Gonzalez-Alvarez, & Larramona, 2016; Dämmrich, Kosyakova, & Blossfeld, 2016). Nonetheless, it can be assumed that the majority of job-related training was employer-funded, as statistics for

⁴⁰ In an additional analysis, model 3 assessing the likelihood of training participation was re-estimated adding a control variable depicting the employees' desire to participate in future training expressed in 2014 (see tab. 10 in the appendix). The findings reveal a significant and substantial positive association of the employees' desire to participate in future training with the likelihood of training participation. The coefficients of all other variables showed patterns comparable to those in the analyses presented above.

Germany suggest (Cedefop, 2016). In addition, the data provides no information on potentially relevant control variables, such as the employment contract or the employees' career orientation. Furthermore, the data contains no information on the training context and content. This means that it is not possible to conclude that training courses or seminars were focused on improvement or provision of employees with digital skills. Also, the data contains no information on the training length or if it took place during working time. This could affect men and women differently. Lastly, a conceptual shortcoming should be mentioned. Since the digitalisation measures used in the analyses are determined on occupational level, they do not account for within-occupation heterogeneity regarding the demand for digital skills (for a general discussion on this issue see: Autor & Handel, 2013; Avent-Holt et al., 2020; Cassidy, 2017; Christoph, Matthes, & Ebner, 2020). Even while working in similar occupations, female and male employees may show systematic differences in what they actually do in their jobs (Martin-Caughey, 2021). Job-level data could offset these shortcomings accounting for within-occupation heterogeneity. Data that offers fine-grained insights into the task content of individuals' jobs are PIAAC data (OECD) or the BIBB/BAuA employment survey (Germany). Since skill demands are closely related to job tasks, such data could be used in future studies. However, deriving work tasks respectively skill demands from occupations is likewise assessed as valuable approach for two reasons: 1) Information derived from occupations is easily available and usually of high quality. 2) Occupations provide high explanatory power for individual-level differences (Autor & Handel, 2013; Mouw & Kalleberg, 2010; Williams & Bol, 2018). An important characteristic of the data on digitalization used in the analyses is, that they are based on online job advertisements. This is linked to some drawbacks that are discussed more in detail in works from Carnevale, Jayasundera and Repnikov (2014); Cedefop (2021); O'Kane et al. (2020). Data from job advertisements rather depict future skill demands for open positions that do not necessarily match skill demands that employees actually face. However, this slightly forward-looking demand perspective in the digitalization data is not necessarily inappropriate for analyses on job-related training. Lastly, the number of employees for occupations in the lowest and highest marginal areas of the digitalisation level and the change in the digitalisation level is rather low. A larger sample could further substantiate our results. Nevertheless,

robustness checks that are presented in the appendix are confirming the findings of the main analysis (see tab. 11 & 12 in the appendix).

5. Conclusion

In summary, three conclusions can be derived. First, it is important to differentiate between the digitalisation level of occupations and the extent of the change in the digitalisation level that occupations experience over a given time period. Both measures depict digitalisation in a broader sense but focus on different aspects of digitalisation. Second, a pronounced change in the digitalisation level in occupations is associated with a higher likelihood of training participation in their second half of working life for men than women, and an increase in the desire for training participation for both men and women. The digitalisation level of occupations is neither associated with the likelihood of training participation nor with the likelihood of the desire for training participation. One explanation might be that digital competencies are a job requirement for occupations with a high digitalisation level and need not be refreshed or acquired by additional training of employees in their second half of working life. In contrast, an average older employee working in an occupation that has experienced a pronounced change in the digitalisation level might face greater skill mismatches in their job. Entrance requirements today might differ considerably from entrance requirements experienced by older employees. Third, the likelihood of training participation decreases more for female employees the more pronounced the change in the digitalisation level in the occupation they are working in. For male employees it increases. Along with the finding that there are no gender differences in the desire to participate in training, the findings suggest that employers might disadvantage women in the provision of suitable training opportunities in occupations that have experienced a pronounced change in the digitalisation level, or that female employees feel less compelled to take up existing training offers in such occupations or assess them as not suitable for themselves.

In sum, future research on digitalisation in work should distinguish between the digitalisation level and the change in the digitalisation level in occupations, as both aspects of digitalisation have different implications. Furthermore, while training is often

discussed as a key measure for changing skill requirements, it is important to be aware of potential differences in the access to and participation in training. The Federal Government has formulated the goal of “shaping digitali[s]ation” in order to make the potentials of digitisation accessible to all population groups and avoid an exacerbation of social inequalities. At the same time, equality between men and women is demanded by law (Art. 3 para. 3 GG). In view of the revealed gender differences, public and operational training measures and strategies must aim to offset this imbalance. Increased awareness of this imbalance, as well as a reduction in gender stereotypes regarding digital competencies, could mitigate the digitalisation-gender gap in training participation. Training offers for digital competencies that explicitly address women could lower barriers for training participation among female employees. In addition, state legislation should (further) encourage gender-sensitive training offers from employers through financial support that is only granted if employers’ training offers are linked to gender equality goals.

6. Literature

- Acemoglu, D., & Autor, D. H. (2011). Skills, tasks and technologies: Implications for employment and earnings. In D. Card & O. Ashenfelter (Eds.), *Handbook of Labor Economics* (Vol. 4B, pp. 1043-1171). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7218\(11\)02410-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7218(11)02410-5)
- Acemoglu, D., & Restrepo, P. (2020). Robots and Jobs: Evidence from US Labor Markets. *Journal of Political Economy*, 128(6), 2188-2244. <https://doi.org/10.1086/705716>
- Aisa, R., Gonzalez-Alvarez, M. A., & Larramona, G. (2016). The Role of Gender in Further Training for Spanish Workers: Are Employers Making a Difference? *Feminist Economics*, 22(3), 154-182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2015.1101520>
- APEC. (2020). *APEC Closing the Digital Skills Gap Report: Trends and Insights* (APEC#220-HR-01.1). A.-P. E. Cooperation. <https://www.apec.org/Publications/2020/12/APEC-Closing-the-Digital-Skills-Gap-Report>
- Arrow, K. J. (1974). *The limits of organization*. Norton.
- Atalay, E., Phongthientham, P., Sotelo, S., & Tannenbaum, D. I. (2020). The Evolution of Work in the United States. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 12, 1-34. <https://doi.org/10.1257/app.20190070>

- Autor, D. H., & Handel, M. J. (2013). Putting Tasks to the Test: Human Capital, Job Tasks, and Wages. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 31(S1), 59-96.
<https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1086/669332>
- Autor, D. H., Levy, F., & Murnane, R. J. (2003). The skill content of recent technological change: An empirical exploration. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(4), 1279-1333. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003355303322552801>
- Avent-Holt, D., Henriksen, L. F., Hägglund, A. E., Jung, J., Kodama, N., Melzer, S. M., Mun, E., Rainey, A., & Tomaskovic-Devey, D. (2020). Occupations, workplaces or jobs?: An exploration of stratification contexts using administrative data. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 70, 100456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2019.100456>
- Azar, J., Marinescu, I., Steinbaum, M., & Taska, B. (2020). Concentration in US labor markets: Evidence from online vacancy data. *Labour Economics*, 66, 101886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2020.101886>
- Bachmann, R., Felder, R., & Tamm, M. (2020). Atypical employment over the life cycle. *Evidence-based HRM*, 8(2), 195-213. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBHRM-08-2019-0073>
- Becker, G. S. (1971). *The Economics of Discrimination* (2. ed.). University of Chicago Press.
- Becker, G. S. (1975). *Human capital. A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education* (2. ed.). Columbia University Press.
- Becker, G. S. (1991). *A Treatise on the Family*. Harvard University Press.
- Becker, R. (2019). Economic change and continuous vocational training in the work history: a longitudinal multilevel analysis of the employees' participation in further training and the effects on their occupational careers in Germany, 1970–2008. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 11(1), 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-019-0079-x>
- Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung - BMBF. (2021). Nationale Weiterbildungsstrategie [National Skills Strategy]. 1-80. <https://www.bmbf.de/de/nationale-weiterbildungsstrategie-8853.html>
- BMBF. (2019). *Weiterbildungsverhalten in Deutschland 2018* [Continuing education behaviour in Germany 2018]. https://www.bmbf.de/upload_filestore/pub/Weiterbildungsverhalten_in_Deutschland_2018.pdf
- BMBF. (2021). *Weiterbildungsverhalten in Deutschland 2020* [Continuing education behaviour in Germany 2020]. https://www.bmbf.de/SharedDocs/Publikationen/de/bmbf/1/31690_AES-Trendbericht_2020.pdf

- Boudon, R. (1974). *Education, opportunity, and social inequality. Changing prospects in Western society*. Wiley.
<https://external.dandelon.com/download/attachments/dandelon/ids/CH001AEABB3E1DC7B3FE7C1257BC000369516.pdf>
- Bourdieu, P., & Passeron, J.-C. (1971). *Die Illusion der Chancengleichheit. Untersuchungen zur Soziologie des Bildungswesens am Beispiel Frankreichs*. Klett.
- Brambor, T., Clark, W. R., & Golder, M. (2006). Understanding Interaction Models: Improving Empirical Analyses. *Political Analysis*, 14(1), 63-82.
<https://doi.org/10.1093%2Fpan%2Fmpi014>
- Breen, R., & Goldthorpe, J. H. (1997). Explaining Educational Differentials: Towards a Formal Rational Action Theory. *Rationality and Society*, 9(3), 275-305.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/104346397009003002>
- Brehmer, W., & Seifert, H. (2008). Sind atypische Beschäftigungsverhältnisse prekär? Eine empirische Analyse sozialer Risiken [Are atypical employment relationships precarious? An empirical analysis of social risks]. *Journal for Labour Market Research*, 41(4), 501-531.
http://doku.iab.de/zaf/2008/2008_4_zaf_Brehmer_Seifert.pdf
- Brunello, G., & Wruuck, P. (2021). Skill Shortages and Skill Mismatch in Europe: A Review of the Literature. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 35(4), 1125-1167.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/joes.12424>
- Brynjolfsson, E., & McAfee, A. (2014). *The second machine age. Work, progress, and prosperity in a time of brilliant technologies* (E. Brynjolfsson & A. McAfee, Eds.). Norton & Company.
- Buchholz, S., Rinklake, A., Schilling, J., Kurz, K., Schmelzer, P., & Blossfeld, H.-P. (2011). Aging populations, globalization and the labor market. Comparing late working life and retirement in modern societies. In Blossfeld, Hans-Peter, S. Buchholz, K. Kurz (Eds.), *Aging Populations, Globalization and the Labor Market: Comparing Late Working Life and Retirement in Modern Societies* (pp. 3-32). Edward Elgar.
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781849805858>
- Burgard, C. (2012). *Gender Differences in Further Training Participation. The Role of Individuals, Households and Firms* (Ruhr Economic Paper No. 320).
<https://doi.org/10.4419/86788369>
- Busch, A. (2013). Der Einfluss der beruflichen Geschlechtersegregation auf den „Gender Pay Gap“. Zur Bedeutung geschlechtlich konnotierter Arbeitsinhalte [The impact of occupational sex segregation on the „Gender Pay Gap“]. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für*

- Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 65(2), 301-338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-013-0201-1>
- Cai, Z., Fan, X., & Du, J. (2017). Gender and attitudes toward technology use: A meta-analysis. *Computers & Education*, 105, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2016.11.003>
- Cammeraat, E., & Squicciarini, M. (2021). Burning Glass Technologies' data use in policy-relevant analysis: An occupation-level assessment. *OECD Science (Technology and Industry Working Papers No. 2021/05)*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/cd75c3e7-en>
- Carnevale, A. P., Jayasundera, T., & Repnikov, D. (2014). Understanding online job ads data. A technical report. In *Centre on Education and the Workforce. Report Website*. Georgetown University. Retrieved September 15, 2022, from https://cew.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/OCLM.Tech_Web.pdf
- Carstensen, T. (2020a). Neuverhandlung oder Verfestigung von Geschlechterungleichheiten? Effekte digitalisierter und mobiler Arbeit auf die Vereinbarkeit von Beruf und Familie, Anwesenheitskulturen und die Veränderung von Tätigkeiten. In V. Bader & S. Kaiser (Eds.), *Arbeit in der Data Society. Zukunftsvisionen für Mitbestimmung und Personalmanagement* (pp. 227-242). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-32276-2_14
- Carstensen, T. (2020b). Orts- und zeitflexibles Arbeiten: Alte Geschlechterungleichheiten und neue Muster der Arbeitsteilung durch Digitalisierung. *Zeitschrift für Arbeitswissenschaft*, 74(3), 195-205. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41449-020-00213-y>
- Cassidy, H. (2017). Task Variation Within Occupations. *Industrial Relations: A Journal of Economy and Society*, 56(3), 393-410. <https://doi.org/10.1111/irel.12179>
- Cedefop. (2016). *Job-related adult learning and continuing vocational training in Europe : a statistical picture*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/doi/10.2801/392276>
- Cedefop. (2021). *Understanding technological change and skill needs: technology and skills foresight*. Publications Office. <http://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/307925>
- Christoph, B., Matthes, B., & Ebner, C. (2020). Occupation-Based Measures. An Overview and Discussion. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 72(1), 41-78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-020-00673-4>
- Colombo, E., Mercurio, F., & Mezzanzanica, M. (2019). AI meets labor market: Exploring the link between automation and skills. *Information Economics and Policy*, 47, 27-37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infoecopol.2019.05.003>

- Cumming, G., & Finch, S. (2005). Inference by Eye: Confidence Intervals and How to Read Pictures of Data. *The American Psychologist*, *60*(2), 170-180.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066x.60.2.170>
- Curtarelli, M., Gualtieri, V., Jannati, M. S., & Donlevy, V., & European Commission (2017). *ICT for work: Digital skills in the workplace: Final report*. Publications Office.
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/498467>
- Czaja, S. J., Charness, N., Fisk, A. D., Hertzog, C., Nair, S. N., Rogers, W. A., & Sharit, J. (2006). Factors predicting the use of technology: findings from the Center for Research and Education on Aging and Technology Enhancement (CREATE). *Psychology and Aging*, *21*(2), 333-352. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0882-7974.21.2.333>
- Dämmrich, J., Kosyakova, Y., & Blossfeld, H.-P. (2016). Gender and job-related non-formal training: A comparison of 20 countries. *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, *56*(6), 433-459. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020715215626769>
- DBB Beamtenbund und Tarifunion. (2021). *Monitor öffentlicher Dienst 2021*.
<https://www.dbb.de/mediathek/broschueren.html>
- Deming, D. J., & Noray, K. (2020). Earnings Dynamics, Changing Job Skills, and STEM Careers. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, *135*(4), 1965-2005.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjaa021>
- Dengler, K., & Matthes, B. (2018). The impacts of digital transformation on the labour market: Substitution potentials of occupations in Germany. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, *137*(2018), 304-316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.09.024>
- Dengler, K., & Tisch, A. (2020). Examining the Relationship Between Digital Transformation and Work Quality: Substitution Potential and Work Exposure in Gender-Specific Occupations. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, *72*(S1), 427-453. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-020-00674-3>
- Dieckhoff, M., & Steiber, N. (2011). A Re-Assessment of Common Theoretical Approaches to Explain Gender Differences in Continuing Training Participation. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, *49*(1), 135-157. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8543.2010.00824.x>
- Ehrlich, U., & Kelle, N. (2019). Pflegende Angehörige in Deutschland: Wer pflegt, wo, für wen und wie? [Family Caregivers in Germany: Who cares, where, who, and why?]. *Zeitschrift für Sozialreform*, *65*(2), 175-203. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zsr-2019-0007>
- Esser, H. (1999). *Situationslogik und Handeln*. Campus-Verlag.
- Estevez-Abe, M. (2005). Gender Bias in Skills and Social Policies: The Varieties of Capitalism Perspective on Sex Segregation. *Social Politics*, *12*(2), 180-215.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxi011>

- Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation? *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 114, 254-280.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.08.019>
- Gashi, A. N., Pugh, G., & Adnett, N. (2010). Technological change and employer-provided training: Evidence from UK workplaces. *International Journal of Manpower*, 31(4), 426-448. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437721011057010>
- Goldin, C. D., & Katz, L. F. (2008). *The Race Between Education and Technology*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjf9x5x>
- Görlitz, K., & Tamm, M. (2015). Revisiting the complementarity between education and training – the role of job tasks and firm effects. *Education Economics*, 24(3), 261-279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09645292.2015.1006182>
- Grund, C., & Martin, J. (2012). Determinants of further training. Evidence for Germany. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(17), 3536–3558. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2011.654347>
- Hargittai, E. (2002). Second-Level Digital Divide: Differences in People's Online Skills. *First Monday*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v7i4.942>
- Havet, N., & Sofer, C. (2008). Why Do Women's Wages Increase so Slowly Throughout Their Career? A Dynamic Model of Statistical Discrimination. *Labour*, 22(2), 291-314. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9914.2008.00409.x>
- Hirsch-Kreinsen, H., & Wienzek, T. (2019). Arbeit 4.0. Segen oder Fluch? In B. Badura, A. Ducki, H. Schröder, J. Klose, & M. Meyer (Eds.), *Fehlzeiten-Report 2019* (pp. 17-28). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-59044-7>
- Howcroft, D., & Rubery, J. (2019). 'Bias in, Bias out': gender equality and the future of work debate. *Labour & Industry*, 29(2), 213-227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10301763.2019.1619986>
- Initiative D21. (2021). *D21-Digital-Index 2020/ 2021. Jährliches Lagebild zur Digitalen Gesellschaft*. https://initiated21.de/app/uploads/2021/02/d21-digital-index-2020_2021.pdf
- Ioannidou, A., & Parma, A. (2021). Risk of Job Automation and Participation in Adult Education and Training: Do Welfare Regimes Matter? *Adult Education Quarterly*, 72(1), 84-109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07417136211026635>
- Jones, M. K., Latreille, P. L., & Sloane, P. J. (2008). Crossing the tracks? Trends in the training of male and female workers in Great Britain. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 46(2), 268-282. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8543.2008.00677.x>

- Klaus, D., Engstler, H., Mahne, K., Wolff, J. K., Simonson, J., Wurm, S., & Tesch-Römer, C. (2017). Cohort Profile: The German Ageing Survey (DEAS). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 46(4), 1105-1105g. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw326>
- Klaus, D., & Vogel, C. (2019). Unbezahlte Sorgetätigkeiten von Frauen und Männern im Verlauf der zweiten Lebenshälfte. In C. Vogel, M. Wettstein, & C. Tesch-Römer (Eds.), *Frauen und Männer in der zweiten Lebenshälfte: Älterwerden im sozialen Wandel* (pp. 91-112). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-25079-9_6
- Kohlrausch, B., & Weber, L. (2021). Gender Relations at the Digitalised Workplace: The Interrelation Between Digitalisation, Gender, and Work. *Gender a výzkum / Gender and Research*, 21(2), 13-31. <https://doi.org/10.13060/gav.2020.010>
- Krieger-Boden, C., & Sorgner, A. (2018). Labor market opportunities for women in the digital age. *Economics*, 12(2018–28), 1-8. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.5018/economics-ejournal.ia.2018-28>
- Lewis, J., Knijn, T., Martin, C., & Ostner, I. (2008). Patterns of Development in Work/Family Reconciliation Policies for Parents in France, Germany, the Netherlands, and the UK in the 2000s. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State and Society*, 15(3), 261-286. <https://doi.org/10.1093/SP/JXN016>
- Lukowski, F., Baum, M., & Mohr, S. (2021). Technology, tasks and training – evidence on the provision of employer-provided training in times of technological change in Germany. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 43(2), 174-195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037x.2020.1759525>
- Martin-Caughey, A. (2021). What's in an Occupation? Investigating Within-Occupation Variation and Gender Segregation Using Job Titles and Task Descriptions. *American Sociological Review*, 86(5), 960-999. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000312242111042053>
- Mayerl, J., & Urban, D. (2019). Vorsicht (!) bei Regressionsanalysen mit Interaktionsvariablen [Be Cautious When Estimating Regression Models with Interaction Variables]. *Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 71(1), 135-156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-019-00590-1>
- Mezzanzanica, M., & Mercurio, F. (2019). Big Data for labour market intelligence: an introductory guide. 58. Retrieved 23.05.2022, from <https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2019-06/Big%20data%20for%20LMI.pdf>
- Morris, A., & Brading, H. (2007). E-literacy and the grey digital divide: A review with recommendations. *Journal of Information Literacy*, 1(3), 13-28. <https://doi.org/10.11645/1.3.14>

- Mouw, T., & Kalleberg, A. L. (2010). Occupations and the Structure of Wage Inequality in the United States, 1980s to 2000s. *American Sociological Review*, 75(3), 402-431.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0003122410363564>
- Murawski, M., & Bick, M. (2017). Digital competences of the workforce – a research topic? *Business Process Management Journal*, 23(3), 721-734. <https://doi.org/10.1108/bpmj-06-2016-0126>
- Nania, J., Bonella, H., Restuccia, D., Taska, B., & Burning Glass Technologies. (2019). No longer optional: Employer demand for digital skills. In Burning Glass Technologies & Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS), Burning Glass Technologies. [https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5cfe713fed915d097daca4b5/No Longer O
ptional Employer Demand for Digital Skills.pdf](https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5cfe713fed915d097daca4b5/No_Longer_Optional_Employer_Demand_for_Digital_Skills.pdf)
- Nedelkoska, L., & Quintini, G. (2018). Automation, skills use and training (*OECD social, employment and migration working papers* 125). <https://doi.org/10.1787/2e2f4eea-en>
- O'Kane, L., Narasimhan, R., Nania, J., & Taska, B. (2020). *Digitalization in the German Labor Market: Analyzing Demand for Digital Skills in Job Vacancies* (TD/TNC 142.690). Bertelsmann Stiftung. <http://aei.pitt.edu/id/eprint/103213>
- Oesch, D. (2013). *Occupational change in Europe : how technology and education transform the job structure*. Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199680962.001.0001>
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development - OECD. (2018). *Bridging the Digital Gender Divide: Include, Upskill, Innovate* [Report]. <http://www.oecd.org/going-digital/bridging-the-digital-gender-divide.pdf>
- OECD. (2019). OECD Employment Outlook 2019: The Future of Work. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/employment/oecd-employment-outlook-2019_9ee00155-en
- OECD. (2021). *Continuing Education and Training in Germany* (Getting Skills Right, Issue. <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/content/publication/1f552468-en>
- Phelps, E. S. (1972). The Statistical Theory of Racism and Sexism. *The American Economic Review*, 62(4), 659-661.
- Piasna, A., & Drahokoupil, J. (2017). Gender inequalities in the new world of work. *Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research*, 23(3), 313-332.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1024258917713839>
- Pischke, J.-S. (2001). Continuous Training in Germany. *Journal of Population Economics*, 14(3), 523-548. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001480000040>

- Polachek, S. W. (1981). Occupational Self-Selection: A Human Capital Approach to Sex Differences in Occupational Structure. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 63(1), 60-69. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1924218>
- Schömann, K., & Becker, R. (1995). Participation in Further Education over the Life Course: A Longitudinal Study of Three Birth Cohorts in the Federal Republic of Germany. *European Sociological Review*, 11(2), 187-208. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.esr.a036356>
- Schwab, K. (2017). *The fourth industrial revolution*. Penguin.
- Spitz-Oener, A. (2006). Technical Change, Job Tasks, and Rising Educational Demands: Looking outside the Wage Structure. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 24(2), 235-270. <https://doi.org/10.1086/499972>
- Stuth, S. (2022). *Occupational Environments - An Activity-Based Approach Based on Holland Version 1.0.0* [Data Set]. WZB - Wissenschaftszentrum Berlin für Sozialforschung. <https://doi.org/10.7802/2502>
- Tan, S. H., & Tan, S. B. (2010). The Correct Interpretation of Confidence Intervals. *Proceedings of Singapore healthcare*, 19(3), 276-278. <https://doi.org/10.1177/201010581001900316>
- Valenduc, G., & Vendramin, P. (2017). Digitalisation, between disruption and evolution. *Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research*, 23(2), 121-134. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1024258917701379>
- Van Dalen, H. P., Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. (2009). Dealing with older workers in Europe: a comparative survey of employers' attitudes and actions. *Journal of European Social Policy*, 19(1), 47-60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958928708098523>
- Vasilescu, M. D., Serban, A. C., Dimian, G. C., Aceleanu, M. I., & Picatoste, X. (2020). Digital divide, skills and perceptions on digitalisation in the European Union—Towards a smart labour market. *PloS one*, 15(4), e0232032. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0232032>
- Wajcman, J. (2004). *TechnoFeminism*. Polity Press.
- Wajcman, J. (2009). Feminist theories of technology. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, 34(1), 143-152. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cje/ben057>
- Williams, M., & Bol, T. (2018). Occupations and the wage structure: The role of occupational tasks in Britain. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 53, 16-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2017.11.003>
- Wotschack, P. (2019). Exploring the (Missing) Gender Training Gap in Germany: The Role of Organizations and Sectors in Continuing Training Participation. *Social Politics*:

International Studies in Gender, State & Society, 26(3), 444-474.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxy021>

Wotschack, P. (2020). Drivers of training participation in low skilled jobs: the role of 'voice', technology, innovation and labor shortages in German companies. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 24(3), 245-264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijtd.12195>

Wozny, C., & Schneider, M. R. (2014). A matter of degree: The continuing training gap for women in Europe. *Socio-Economic Review*, 12(2), 353-379.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwu008>

II. Digitalization and Employees' Subjective Job Quality in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

Authors: Lisa Katharina Kortmann, Julia Simonson, Claudia Vogel, Oliver Huxhold

Accepted: 19 November 2021 / Published online: 1 December 2021

Journal: *Social Indicators Research* (2022) 162:577–597

Abstract: Since digitalization alters occupational task profiles via automation processes, job quality is also likely to be affected. While existing literature mainly focusses on objective job quality, this study asks if and how digitalization is associated with employees' subjective job quality in the second half of working life in Germany. Analyses are based on the German Ageing Survey 2014. Our sample includes $n = 1541$ employees aged 40–65 years who are subject to social insurance contributions. Subjective job quality is operationalized with regards to job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress in general, and ten aspects of job quality in detail. Digitalization is approximated by substitution potentials of occupations. We control the association for compositional effects in the workforce, as well as for the moderating effect of perceived job insecurity. The results indicate that digitalization is predominantly beneficial but also unfavorable in a few other respects for employees' subjective job quality. The higher the degree of digitalization, the higher is the employee's general job satisfaction on average; for general perceived occupational stress, we find no significant association. Regarding single aspects of subjective job quality, employees working in more digitalized occupations are found to report on average higher satisfaction with working hours and earnings, and lower levels of stress due to tight schedules. However, they also report higher levels of stress due to negative environmental factors.

Keywords: Job satisfaction; Occupational stress; Subjective job quality; Digitalization; German Ageing Survey

1. Introduction

In recent decades, there has been a considerable increase in the adoption of new technologies in the labor market, which have automated occupational tasks. As a consequence, occupational profiles have changed and will continue to change profoundly. These changes may have had and will have substantial and far-reaching impacts on job quality. However, most empirical studies thus far have focused either on single, objective aspects of job quality (e.g. wages; Fernández-Macías, 2012), on specific sectors (e.g. manufacturing; Körner et al., 2019) or specific technologies (e.g. computer and internet-use; Kirchner, 2015). The technostress literature does investigate several aspects of subjective job quality, but its focus lies on the negative effects of technology usage (Bondanini et al., 2020). Currently, there is a lack of empirical studies that incorporate a comprehensive perspective. This is surprising in many respects. First, politicians at the international and national level are paying increasing attention to job quality. In the OECD's Job Strategy, launched in 2018, job quality is a central policy priority. At the national level, the German Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs recently put the quality of jobs in the political spotlight by initiating the expert dialogue *Arbeiten 4.0* [work 4.0]. Second, research has shown that low job quality is associated with outcomes such as lower productivity, poorer health and early retirement plans (Henseke, 2018; Royuela & Suriñach, 2013; Siegrist et al., 2006). Third, there is a broad consensus in the literature that job quality is a multidimensional concept (Cascales Mira, 2021; Muñoz de Bustillo et al., 2011), so any comprehensive analysis of job quality in light of digitalization needs to consider multiple positive and negative job-related aspects. Fourth, most existing studies use only objective measures for job quality and do not capture individual preferences and subjective job assessments. Subjective measures of job quality can, however, provide valuable information about the employee's well-being at work. Finally, for several labor market-related decisions like job changes or the retirement transition, the employee's subjective evaluation is of importance. This study examines the potential impact of digitalization on employees' subjective job quality in the second half of working life in Germany. Specifically, we aim to answer the question: is working in more digitalized occupations associated with lower subjective job quality? To answer this question, we use representative data from the 2014 wave of the German Ageing Survey (DEAS,

Deutscher Alterssurvey). The degree of digitalization is indexed by the substitution potential—the ratio of potentially automatable tasks that are part of a particular occupation in relation to all tasks included in this occupational profile. We see the substitution potential as an approximation of the de facto degree of digitalization in occupations. Subjective job quality is captured by job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress. We control for characteristics of the employee and the employee's job that may be differentially affected by digitalization to account for composition effects. Since job insecurity is one important aspect of job quality, and because it may be highly affected by the introduction of new technologies, we control for subjective job insecurity as well. The main contributions of this work to the existing literature are: while an overwhelming number of studies on the implications of digitalization for job quality focus on objective, one-dimensional, or one-sided measures, this study provides a subjective, multidimensional perspective on job quality, considering positive and negative aspects. Furthermore, we use a comprehensive measure for digitalization that contains all new technologies, not only computer use or robot density. Finally, we focus on employees in the second half of working life. Thus, we investigate a group that might be particularly vulnerable to digitalization as their skill sets may have a higher likelihood of becoming fully or partly outdated due to digitalization. Younger employees who recently entered the labor market are typically better educated, more digitally savvy and may possess better skills to deal with new technologies. Most importantly, in recent years there have been a number of policy measures aimed at prolonging working life. These policies aim to cope with challenges to the labor market and pension system due to the ongoing process of demographic change. Poor job quality could counteract these efforts. In comparison with the OECD average (9%), the share of employees working in occupations with a high automation potential⁴¹ was among the highest in Germany in 2012 (12%) (Arntz, Gregory, & Zierahn, 2016). Furthermore, in 2014 every second employee in Germany (52%) used a computer with internet access at work—which was above the European average (46%) (OECD, 2021).

⁴¹ The automation potentials determined by Arntz, Gregory and Zierahn (2016) for OECD countries are similar to substitution potentials determined by Dengler and Matthes (2018) for Germany.

2. Previous Research

2.1. Digitalization and the Labor Market

In this study, we use the term “digitalization” to refer to the spread of digital devices, applications and machines that started in the second half of the twentieth century. One theoretical perspective on digitalization’s impact on employment is the task-based approach (TBA), coined by Autor, Levy and Murnane (2003). It assumes that routine tasks can be automated by digital technologies. Non-routine tasks, in contrast, cannot be fully translated into algorithms at present. In recent literature, the TBA has been used to determine the degree of “automatability” in occupations. While some studies imply that digitalization will lead to full automation of jobs and thus to the replacement of workers by digital technologies (Frey & Osborne, 2017), others emphasized that digitalization will mostly lead to changes in occupational task profiles (Dengler & Matthes, 2018). In line with their emphasis, we prefer the use of the comprehensive and neutral term of “digitalization”.

2.2. Digitalization and Subjective Job Quality

Regarding the impact of digitalization on job quality, two opposing positions have been taken in the field. Some studies have noted the beneficial aspects of technologies. For example, new technologies are seen as key drivers for increasing flexibilization of the organization of work as they facilitate the implementation of telework, home office or flexible working time arrangements. Flexible working time arrangements have been found to have positive effects on employees’ work-life balance (Hill et al., 2001). A good work-life balance is in turn positively associated with job satisfaction and negatively associated with mental health issues (Haar et al., 2014). Additionally, digitalization may reduce the burden of physical labor. Certain technologies, typically industrial robots, are built to execute physically demanding tasks, like lifting heavy loads, or replacing humans in harsh environmental conditions. This could alleviate physical stress and improve occupational safety, thus preventing work-related illnesses (Theurel & Desbrosses, 2019). Other technologies, typically computers, execute cognitive demanding tasks, like complex calculations.

However, the empirical evidence concerning the impact of digitalization on job quality

is not uniformly positive. The field of technostress research focusses in particular on the negative relationship between employees' psychological well-being and the use of new technologies (Bondanini et al., 2020). Such studies have identified different stressors, like inadequate skills to deal with new technologies, or the fear that one's job will be substituted (Tarafdar et al., 2011). The rise of new technologies has led to an intensification and acceleration of work. Faster communication, information, production and distribution can lead to higher stress levels in employees (Green, 2004). In line with this, Germany has experienced an increase in high-speed work and working to tight deadlines in recent years, coinciding with a slight decrease in job satisfaction over the same time period (Hoonakker, 2014). Furthermore, digitalization is related to the blurring of boundaries between working and private life. Felstead and Henseke (2017) found remote working associated with an intensification and greater difficulties switching off from work. Employees' physical well-being can be negatively affected as well. Constant computer use at work has been found to be related to physical strain (Andries, Smulders, & Dhondt, 2002). The use of new technologies can lead employees to work in unhealthy physical postures, as occurs when spending extended periods of time sitting or working at a screen. Long hours of computer work have, for example, been found to be related to wrist and arm problems (Gerr et al., 2002; Gerr, Monteilh, & Marcus, 2006; Jensen, 2003).

2.2.1. Subjective Job Quality

The concept of job quality refers to aspects that contribute to fulfilling employees' work-related needs or ensuring their well-being (Brown et al., 2007; Green, 2006; Muñoz de Bustillo et al., 2011). There are objective and subjective perspectives on job quality. The objective perspective focusses on a bundle of observable job characteristics, like earnings or working time arrangements. In contrast, a subjective job quality perspective focuses on employees' assessments of their job. A subjective perspective considers how characteristics of the occupation are evaluated and prioritized by the employee in accordance with their individual needs, preferences and experiences. One simple way to depict job quality is to use a global measure of job satisfaction (Clark, 2011; Green, 2006). However, this approach has been criticized for oversimplifying the multidimensionality of the concept (Muñoz de Bustillo et al.,

2011).

Therefore, in this study we take job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress as dimensions of subjective job quality. Job satisfaction and stress are commonly used dimensions to depict subjective job quality (Handel, 2005; Olsen, Kalleberg, & Nesheim, 2010; Soh et al., 2016; Warr, 1999). The association between occupational stress and job satisfaction is not as straightforward as it might seem; while higher levels of stress are generally associated with lower levels of satisfaction, some aspects of stress could be associated with higher levels of job satisfaction. In particular, perceived stress does sometimes acts as a motivator, hence occupations can be experienced as both stressful and satisfying at the same time. Some studies distinguish between challenge and hindrance stressors, which show positive or negative associations with work related aspects (Podsakoff, LePine, & LePine, 2007). High workloads, for example, are found to be associated with higher levels of satisfaction with the variety of work tasks and activities or with the salary (Burke, 1976). Therewith, a high workload could be classified as challenge stressor.

Job satisfaction describes workers' overall contentment with different characteristics of their job. Perceived occupational stress describes workers' physical or psychological reaction to a mismatch between their expectations and their actual capacity to meet different work-related demands (Kahn et al., 1964). Job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress can be conceptualized either as global or multidimensional measures. Global measures are either based on single item questions – e.g. ones that asks employees to assess their satisfaction with their current job in general, or by index measures, summing up employees' assessments towards different aspects of their job. Single-item global measures have the advantage that they rely on the employee's preferences and relevance systems, so the selection and weighting of different job aspects is up to the employees themselves. Index global measures, based on employees' assessments towards a pre-selected list of different job-related aspects, raise the problem of how to weight different aspects.

Equal weights are usually applied to all pre-selected aspects of a job in order to build an index. A multidimensional measure of job satisfaction describes employees'

satisfaction with different aspects of their job: e.g. satisfaction with earnings, the kind of work, or opportunities for promotion or career development. A multidimensional measure of perceived occupational stress is comprised of different stressors related to a job, which can be physical or psychosocial in nature. Physical stressors may include monotonous work, high paced work, work in noisy environments or work under extreme climatic conditions. Psychosocial stressors may include bad relationships with colleagues or superiors, time pressure or ambiguous working instructions.

In contrast to global measures, a multidimensional perspective allows to investigate different facets of a concept that are differentially affected by a given phenomenon. Therefore, in this study, we use multidimensional measures for job satisfaction as well as for perceived occupational stress and consider each facet separately in addition to using global measures for job satisfaction and occupational stress.

2.2.2. Subjective Job Quality and Digitalization

The association between subjective job quality and digitalization is to date an understudied topic, especially when it comes to studies using representative data and comprehensive measures for both. For example, we only found few studies that used broad multidimensional measures of job quality and identified a link between job quality and digitalization (Handel, 2005; Olsen, Kalleberg, & Nesheim, 2010). However, both studies only implicitly linked subjective job quality to digitalization and did not incorporate a measure of digitalization in the analyses. While Handel (2005) focused on trends in perceived job quality in the US over time, Olsen, Kalleberg and Nesheim (2010) investigated differences between and within countries at different time points. Overall, both studies mostly demonstrated stability in perceived job quality measured by job satisfaction over time. Moreover, looking at single aspects of job quality, both studies found few significant changes. Specifically, findings pointed to improvement over time for some aspects of job quality and deterioration for others. In contrast to these approaches, Gallie (2003) included “working with new technologies” as a direct measure of digitalization. He found that working with new technologies was associated with higher job quality in 1996 in Europe. Unfortunately, it remains unclear what “working with new technologies” actually measured, since the

study lacked an extensive description of the item. However, it can be assumed that the understanding of “new technologies” was up to the survey respondents themselves, and as a consequence the actual impact of working with new technologies was not uniformly depicted. In addition, this study considered only four aspects of subjective job quality: the quality of working tasks, involvement in decision making, career opportunities and job security. Important aspects such as stress in the workplace, earnings, or relationships with colleagues or with the boss were not considered.

Dengler and Tisch (2020) used a comprehensive measure of digitalization but a rather restricted measure for subjective job quality. The authors investigated the association between potential digitalization and overall physical and psychosocial exposure at work in Germany. The measures for subjective job quality only focused on perceptions of stress and did not cover other aspects of satisfaction with a job. Their findings indicated that new technologies may relieve men of physically demanding work. Since institutional frame-works and labor market preconditions are relevant factors impacting on subjective job quality (Gallie, 2007), a distinct investigation of Germany using an extensive measure of subjective job quality is needed.

2.2.3. Subjective Job Quality, Digitalization and a Composition Effect

As described above, occupations are differentially affected by digitalization, and employees with certain sociodemographic and job-related characteristics vary systematically across different occupations. For example, substitution potentials are found to be highest in the manufacturing sector, occupations concerned with production technology or occupations in business management and organization. Occupations in cleaning services, safety and security or service occupations in the social or cultural sector show the lowest substitution potentials (Dengler & Matthes, 2018). Consequentially, it is likely that differences in subjective job quality are not solely due to differences in the degree of digitalization at work but are at least partly due to employees’ sociodemographic and job-related characteristics. Thus, in line with the studies on subjective job quality and digitalization mentioned above, we consider the following variables as important control variables: age, gender, residency in East or West Germany, educational level, sector of employment, company size,

health status, hourly wage and working hours. The theoretical rationale for including these characteristics is detailed below.

It is well known that men and women are distributed differently among occupations in the German labor market (Busch, 2013); Male-dominated occupations have been found to show higher average potential degrees of digitalization than female-dominated occupations (Piasna & Drahoukoupil, 2017). Regarding job satisfaction, women are found to show on average higher satisfaction than men (Perugini & Vladislavljević, 2019). However, studies on the association between occupational stress and gender show ambiguous findings (Gyllensten & Palmer, 2005). Regarding education and wages, it has been demonstrated that lower degrees of digitalization correlate with higher educational levels and higher individual wages of employees (Dengler & Matthes, 2019). Tasks that are not automatable are often more complex and require higher skills from the employee. Higher educational levels and higher wages may reflect these needs. At the same time, highly educated people usually work in jobs that are objectively characterized by good job quality: they are usually employed in higher paid jobs, have more autonomy at work, and their work is less physically demanding. Employees' age can be assumed to be related with the occupations' potential degree of digitalization and subjective job quality. Studies have found that older employees are expected to be less willing and capable to learn new things (Hauk, Hüffmeier, & Krumm, 2018; Warr & Birdi, 1998), and that computer and internet use at work is lower among older individuals (Huxhold, Hees, & Webster, 2020). Thus, older employees may be less exposed to new digital devices and applications at the workplace. Despite this, with increasing age employees are found to show lower levels of occupational strain due to digital technologies (Hauk, Goritz, & Krumm, 2019; Ragu-Nathan et al., 2008), and higher levels of job satisfaction (Ng & Feldman, 2010). Therefore, we expect job satisfaction to increase and occupational stress to decrease with age in our analyses. The sector of employment is related to the potential degree of digitalization. The industry sector is characterized by repetitive working processes in protected work environments (e.g. factories) that provide favorable circumstances for new technologies. Furthermore, different sectors may be related to different average levels of job satisfaction or occupational stress, since working conditions may differ considerably. Industrial jobs can be often characterized

by a noisy working environment, assembly line work and monotonous working tasks. In contrast, jobs in the public sector often have more favorable working conditions, like good working time regulations or opportunities for further training. Despite German reunification in 1990, East-West differences in job satisfaction and occupational stress seem to persist (Datenreport 2018, 2018). Furthermore, company size can be expected to be related to digitalization and job quality. Bigger companies may have greater financial resources to implement new technologies in the company. Regarding job quality, smaller companies have been found to provide less favorable working conditions compared to larger companies, for example, lower wages or fewer opportunities for skill enhancement (Wagner, Pischner, & Haisken-DeNew, 2002). However, a more familiar atmosphere and shorter communication channels in small companies may compensate for such objectively less favorable working conditions and subjective assessments of working conditions may differ in that respect. The time spent at work may be determined by the employment contract (e.g. part-time) or by individual engagement (e.g. overtime). While there are only little differences between part- and full-time employees regarding (aspects of) job satisfaction (Thorsteinson, 2003) long working hours correlate with several negative health outcomes (Bannai & Tamakoshi, 2014). Lastly, we consider self-rated health (SRH) as an important control variable in our analyses, as it is likely to be related to digitalization as well as subjective job quality. Employees with poor health can be assumed to self-select into jobs with higher degrees of digitalization, since new technologies may compensate for their physical deficiencies. In addition, SRH is an important predictor of subjective well-being (Smith et al., 2010) and job satisfaction and occupational stress are closely related to a person's overall well-being.

2.2.4. Job Insecurity, Subjective Job Quality and Digitalization

In research on job quality job insecurity is named as one crucial determinant with job insecurity showing a negative association with job satisfaction and a positive with occupational stress (Ganster & Rosen, 2013; Hur, 2019; Sverke, Hellgren, & Näswall, 2002). Some longitudinal studies demonstrate that workers in occupations that are highly impacted by digitalization have a higher probability of becoming unemployed (Biagi et al., 2018; Cortes, 2016). Hence, the degree of digitalization of occupations

can be expected to affect subjective job insecurity. In fact, we found a low but significant positive correlation between the degree of digitalization with subjective job insecurity (Spearman's $\rho = 0.115$). Since we are interested in the impact of new technologies on employees' assessments of their working conditions in their current occupation, regardless of any risk of job loss, we control for subjective job insecurity.

2.3. The Current Study

This study aims to answer the following overarching question: how is the digitalization in occupations associated with the subjective job quality of employees aged 40 and older in Germany? Subjective job quality is measured by job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress. We focus on employees in the second half of their working life for different reasons. First, it can be assumed that due to their long past training phase, a higher share of their skills and knowledge might have become outdated or even obsolete in times of technological change. For older employees, there is less time for training to pay off before they retire. Consequently, broad changes in the occupational task profiles may considerably burden employees in the second half of their working life. Second, employees in the second half of their working life usually have some years of experience in the labor market and may be settled in a job that suits their ideas and needs.

2.3.1. Hypotheses – Digitalization and Job Quality

We expect higher degrees of digitalization in occupations associated with lower levels of the job satisfaction index (H1.1), as well as with job satisfaction as a whole (H1.2). Furthermore, we expect higher degrees of digitalization associated with higher levels of the occupational stress index (H2). This is because, if not controlled for compositional effects, we assume more digitalized occupations to be characterized by aspects typically associated with lower levels of job satisfaction or higher levels of occupational stress. Since the implementation of new, digital technologies in occupations is ever-progressing, employees working in more digitalized occupations may on average still assess their job quality as lower than employees in occupations that are less digitalized.

With respect to specific aspects of job quality, we expect more digitized occupations

to be associated with lower levels of satisfaction with opportunities for further training provided by the employer (H1.a). On one hand, employees facing new technologies may see a greater need for further training. On the other hand, employers may shy away from investing in employees in the second half of life. In contrast to younger employees, older employees have shorter time horizons on the labor market and are not digital natives. Further, we hypothesize that employees working in more digitized occupations report higher levels of stress due to strenuous, physical work (H2.a) and negative environmental factors (H2.b). This is because we expect to find higher digitalization degrees in those occupations with more arduous or harsh working conditions. Therefore, potentially positive effects of new technologies might not be revealed if compositional effects are not controlled for.

2.3.2. Hypotheses – Digitalization and Job Quality While Controlling for Compositional Effects

Controlling for compositional effects of the workforce and based on the literature and considerations mentioned above (Sects. 2.2.2 and 2.2.3), we expect that higher degrees of digitalization of occupations are associated with higher levels of the job satisfaction index (H3.1) and job satisfaction as a whole (H3.2), as well as with lower levels of the occupational stress index (H4). The reasoning behind these assumptions is that compositional effects of the workforce may overshadow a positive effect of new technologies on global measures of job satisfaction and occupational stress.

In addition, we hypothesize that, controlling for compositional effects, employees in more digitalized occupations are less satisfied with opportunities for further training provided by the employer (H3.a). The rationale corresponds to that of H1.a. Further, digitalization has been shown to lead to higher flexibilization, such as flexible working time arrangements, and to be related to higher autonomy at work. Therefore we expect to find higher levels of satisfaction with working hours (H3.b) and higher levels of satisfaction with the working atmosphere (H3.c) for employees working in more digitalized occupations. The satisfaction with the kind of work is expected to be higher in more digitalized occupations (H3.d), since new technologies may substitute for or alleviate some stressful working tasks. We expect to find employees reporting lower

levels of stress due to strenuous physical tasks (H4.a) and lower stress due to negative environmental factors (H4.b) the higher the degree of digitalization. This is because new technologies may alleviate physically demanding tasks or harsh working conditions. Digitalization has been shown to lead to an acceleration of working processes. Therefore, after controlling for compositional effects, we expect employees working in more digitalized occupations to experience more stress due to tight schedules (H4.c). Furthermore, we expect higher levels of stress due to new responsibilities (H4.d) to be linked with higher degrees of digitalization, since digitalization processes may lead to large and constantly new changes in working tasks requirements.

2.3.3. Hypotheses – Digitalization and Job Quality while Controlling for Compositional Effects and Job Insecurity

As digitalization can lead to job losses due to substitution processes, subjective job insecurity may be higher among employees working in occupations with higher degrees of digitalization. If employees see their job at risk, negative attitudes towards their job may be higher compared to employees who feel their job is secure. Therefore, we expect employees working in more digitalized occupations who do not feel threatened by substitution to show higher levels of the job satisfaction index (H5.1), higher levels with job satisfaction as a whole (H5.2) and lower levels of the occupational stress index (H6). Regarding single aspects of job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress, we expect to find associations similar to those formulated in the hypotheses for the compositional model (H5.a–H5.d & H6.a–H6.d). Furthermore, we hypothesize that higher levels of subjective job insecurity are associated with lower levels of the job satisfaction index (H7.1), job satisfaction as a whole (H7.2), and all aspects of job satisfaction (H7.1–H7.f). Lastly, we expect that the higher the job insecurity, the higher the levels of the occupational stress index (H8) and all aspects of occupational stress (H8.a–H8.d) (for an overview of all hypotheses see supplemental material, Table 14).

3. Method

3.1. Sample

To answer the research question, we used data from the baseline sample of the 2014 wave of the German Ageing Survey (DEAS) (Klaus et al., 2017). The DEAS 2014 is a cross-sectional and longitudinal survey representative for the resident population of private households aged 40 and above in Germany. The baseline sample is based on registration office data, is stratified by age, gender and place of residence, and comprises 6002 respondents in 2014. The DEAS is based on a standardized, computer-assisted personal interview that has been conducted by professional interviewers in the respondents' homes. It contains detailed information on the living and working situations of people in the second half of life as well as assessments of different aspects like job satisfaction or occupational stress. Furthermore, we used data on the digitalization of occupations, namely substitution potential, calculated by the IAB.

The analyses investigated employees between the ages of 40 and 65 that are subject to social insurance contributions. Individuals that were not employed full- or part-time and those aged 66 and above were excluded from the sample. Furthermore, individuals with imprecise occupational information (that is ISCO codes less precise than unit group level) were excluded, as detailed information on the occupation was essential for the analyses. The sample was comprised of $N = 1541$ employees (49% female; $M_{age} = 51.8$; $SD_{age} = 6.15$) and showed a slight overrepresentation of highly educated employees, a bias documented also for the general DEAS 2014 sample (Klaus et al., 2017) (see supplemental material, Table 1).

3.2. Measures

3.2.1. Dependent Variables

Subjective job quality was captured by two dimensions: job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress. Besides index measures of both dimensions, both measures were broken down into their sub-dimensions to get a more detailed picture.

Job satisfaction: We used a job satisfaction index built from six items on employees' assessments towards different aspects of their job, stated on a 5-point Likert-scale

(McDonald's omega: 0.75). The different aspects of job satisfaction concerned earnings, the job itself, working hours, opportunities for career development or promotion, opportunities for further training offered by the company and the working atmosphere. In addition satisfaction with employees' work as a whole was considered. The answer scale ranged from "very satisfied" to "very unsatisfied" and was inverted, such higher values indicate more satisfaction. On average, employees reported being "rather satisfied" with their job; the mean of the job satisfaction index was 3.83, while the mean of job satisfaction as a whole was slightly higher (4.16).

Occupational stress: In DEAS 2014 four aspects of occupational stress were assessed: Employees perceived stress due to physical activities, negative environmental factors, heavy workloads or tight deadlines, and new job responsibilities. The 5-point response scale ranged from "very stressed" to "not at all stressed" and was inverted. The single aspects were additionally aggregated to an index (McDonald's omega: 0.61). On average, employees reported being slightly stressed (mean index: 2.85).

3.2.2. Independent Variables

Digitalization: To depict the occupations' degree of digitalization, we used substitution potential determined by the Federal Institute of Employment Research (IAB, Institut für Arbeitsmarkt- und Berufsforschung) (Dengler & Matthes, 2018). This was calculated by dividing the share of occupational core tasks that were potentially automatable by the share of all core tasks of the same occupation. If an occupational task was considered as automatable or not relied on independent judgements from three experts. In our study, we interpreted substitution potential as a measure of the degree of digitalization thrust in occupations. We assume that occupations with higher substitution potential have already undergone processes of digitalization to a larger degree than occupations with lower substitution potential. We were able to assign a valid substitution potential value to 95 percent of the sample. For the remaining five percent a meaningful value was imputed. Occupations with high degrees of digitalization are, for example, clerical workers or machine operators in the production; Teachers or bus drivers are occupations assigned to low degrees of digitalization.

Job insecurity: Subjective job insecurity is measured by asking about the respondents' appraisal of the likelihood of losing their job in the near future. The 4-point answer scale ranged from "very likely" to "very unlikely". Job insecurity was slightly positively correlated with occupations' degree of digitalization (0.1 Spearman's rho). Overall, employees assessed the likelihood of job loss in the near future as rather low (mean: 1.65).

3.2.3. Control Variables

We controlled for the stratification variables of age, gender and residency underlying the DEAS sample. Age was measured in years and added as a continuous variable to the analysis. Gender and residency were added as dummy variables, with "1" for "male" "living in West Germany"⁴² respectively. We also controlled for job characteristics to address a potential composition effect—here, we looked at educational level, sector, firm size, SRH, hourly wage and working hours. We controlled for the educational level using a three-level classification based on the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) to distinguish between a low, middle and high educational level (OECD, Eurostat, & UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2015). A low educational level was used as the base category. Regarding information on the sector an occupation is located in, DEAS data allows differentiation between five major sectors: agriculture and forestry, industry, handicraft, commercial and service and public service. We added the sector as a categorical variable to our analysis (agriculture and forestry, industry, handicraft, commercial and services, public services) with "agriculture and forestry" as base category. Company size was measured by the number of employees and ranges from "1" for "less than five employees" to "5" for "more than 2000 employees". We used SRH measured by the single question "How do you rate your current state of health?" to control for the employees' health. The 5-point answer scale ranges from "very good" to "very bad" and was inverted for a more intuitive interpretation. Hourly wages were added as a continuous variable to our analyses. They were determined by dividing the monthly net income by working hours. This gave us a measure for the monetary valuation of

⁴² Former Federal Republic of Germany excluding Berlin.

work independent of differences in working hours. To control for differences in working hours specifically, we added information on employees' weekly working hours, including overtime to our analyses. There was no indication of high multicollinearity among the considered variables (Cohen, 1988).⁴³

3.3. Analyses

To analyze the potential impact of digitalization on job quality, we estimated three multiple linear regression models for each dependent variable and reported unstandardized partial regression coefficients. In the first model – the pure model – we estimated the relationship between job satisfaction or, perceived occupational stress and digitalization, while controlling for age, gender and residency to account for the disproportional sampling in DEAS. In the second model – the compositional model – we added information on education, sector, company size, SRH, wage and working hours to control for compositional effects within the workforce. In the third model – the job insecurity model – we also controlled for subjective job insecurity.

To make full use of the data, multiple imputation was used to impute missing values on all variables considered in our analyses (Rubin, 1987). Specifically, multiple imputation with chained equations (MICE) and M = 50 imputation models were applied. We used chained equations, as the missing pattern in the data is multivariate and not monotonous. Additionally, some of the variables containing missing values were not continuous. We applied several tests suggested in the literature to check the quality of the imputation (Nguyen, Carlin, & Lee, 2017). Some robustness tests performed substantiate the stability of our findings (see supplemental material, Tables 10–13). We present the results of our analyses in the following section.⁴⁴ An association is considered to be statistically significant if the coefficient's p-value value falls below 0.05.

⁴³ The highest correlation was found between working hours and gender (0.46), which can be assessed as “middle” correlation (Cohen, 1988).

⁴⁴ Find a detailed presentation of the results in Tables 4–9 in the supplemental material.

4. Results

4.1. Digitalization and Job Quality

In the pure model, we found no significant associations between higher levels of digitalization in occupations and the index measure of job satisfaction ($b = 0.009$; $p = 0.889$) or employees' satisfaction with their work as a whole ($b = 0.092$; $p = 0.233$). Similarly, no significant association of digitalization with the index measure of perceived occupational stress was found ($b = 0.106$; $p = 0.186$). Therefore, hypotheses H1.1, H1.2 and H2 have to be rejected.

Regarding single aspects of job satisfaction, higher degrees of digitalization were associated with higher satisfaction with working hours ($b = 0.429$; $p = 0.000$); yet, higher digitalization was linked to lower levels of satisfaction with opportunities for further training ($b = -0.362$; $p = 0.004$). Therefore, hypothesis H1.a was confirmed. In line with our hypotheses H2.a and H2.b, we found higher degrees of digitalization related to more stress due to physical activities ($b = 0.381$; $p = 0.002$) and due to negative environmental factors ($b = 0.810$; $p = 0.000$). Lastly, we found digitalization negatively associated with stress due to tight schedules (see Table 1, p. 18).

4.2. Compositional Effects

In the composition model, we found positive associations of digitalization with both global measures of job satisfaction (index: $b = 0.172$; $p = 0.019$; job satisfaction as a whole: $b = 0.181$; $p = 0.035$), but no association with the index measure of occupational stress ($b = -0.034$; $p = 0.693$). Therefore, hypotheses H3.1 and H3.2 were confirmed, but hypothesis H4 not.

Regarding single aspects of job quality, we found support for hypothesis H3.b. Working in more digitalized occupations correlates with higher satisfaction with working hours ($b = 0.465$; $p = 0.000$). Further, employees working in occupations that are digitalized to higher degrees are more satisfied with their earnings ($b = 0.253$; $p = 0.020$) as well as with opportunities for career development ($b = 0.249$; $p = 0.045$). Hypotheses H3.a, H3.c and H3.d were not confirmed (further training: $b = -0.109$; $p = 0.448$; working atmosphere: $b = 0.103$; $p = 0.318$; kind of work: $b = 0.069$;

$p = 0.462$). Regarding aspects of perceived occupational stress in the compositional model, higher levels of digitalization were found to be associated with more stress due to negative environmental factors ($b = 0.345$; $p = 0.011$), but less stress due to tight schedules ($b = -0.518$; $p = 0.000$). Thus, the results were contrary to our expectations formulated in hypotheses H4.b and H4.c. No significant association was found for digitalization with occupational stress due to strenuous physical tasks ($b = -0.055$; $p = 0.667$) and due to new responsibilities ($b = 0.093$; $p = 0.465$). Consequently, hypotheses H4.a and H4.d were also rejected.

While the educational level of employees does not seem to have a great impact on (aspects of) job satisfaction, it appears as important control variable regarding (aspects of) occupational stress. High educated employees report on average lower stress due to physical or environmental factors, but higher stress due to tight schedules and new responsibilities at work. Furthermore, job satisfaction and stress are found to be impacted significantly by the size of the company, employees' health status and wages. Bigger companies seem to be associated with lower job satisfaction and higher stress among employees. Contrary to that, the employees' health status and wages show positive associations with (most aspects of) job satisfaction and occupational stress (see Table 1, p.18).

4.3. Job Insecurity

As in the compositional model, and in line with hypotheses H5.1 and H5.2 for the job insecurity model, higher degrees of digitalization were associated with higher levels of job satisfaction, measured by global measures (index: $b = 0.188$; $p = 0.009$; as a whole: $b = 0.198$; $p = 0.018$). Likewise, hypothesis H6 was rejected, as no significant association was found for the occupational stress index ($b = -0.040$; $p = 0.639$).

Controlling for perceived job insecurity and compositional effects, we found that higher degrees of digitalization associated with more satisfaction with working hours ($b = 0.473$; $p = 0.000$) and less stress due to tight schedules ($b = -0.522$; $p = 0.000$). Hence, hypothesis H5.b was confirmed but H6.c had to be rejected. Contrary to hypothesis H6.b, we found a significant relationship between working in more

digitalized occupations and higher levels of stress due to negative environmental factors at work ($b = 0.336$; $p = 0.014$). We also found positive associations between higher degrees of digitalization of occupations with employees' satisfaction with earnings ($b = 0.266$; $p = 0.014$) and with opportunities for career development ($b = 0.274$; $p = 0.025$). Hypotheses H5.a, H5.c, H5.d and hypotheses H6.a and H6.d were not confirmed, as no significant associations were found (further training: $b = -0.081$; $p = 0.568$; working atmosphere: $b = 0.116$; $p = 0.260$; kind of work: $b = 0.081$; $p = 0.384$; physical activities: $b = -0.060$; $p = 0.639$; new responsibilities: $b = 0.085$; $p = 0.504$).

Furthermore, our results indicate that employees feeling more at risk of losing their jobs reported lower levels of job satisfaction, measured by global measures (index: $b = -0.165$; $p = 0.000$; as a whole: $b = -0.180$; $p = 0.000$) or regarding single aspects of job satisfaction (further training: $b = -0.285$; $p = 0.000$; working hours: $b = -0.073$; $p = 0.036$; working atmosphere: $b = -0.128$; $p = 0.000$; kind of work: $b = -0.124$; $p = 0.000$; earnings: $b = -0.130$; $p = 0.000$, career opportunities: $b = -0.248$; $p = 0.000$). Therefore, hypotheses H7.1–H7.f were confirmed. A positive association with the perceived stress index ($b = 0.065$; $p = 0.021$) as well as with stress due to environmental factors ($b = 0.091$; $p = 0.043$) was found. An association significant on 90 percent confidence level was found for stress due to new responsibilities and job insecurity ($b = 0.081$; $p = 0.054$). Therefore, hypotheses H8, H8.b and H8.d were confirmed, but hypotheses H8.a and H8.c were rejected (physical activities: $b = 0.051$; $p = 0.231$; tight schedules: $b = 0.036$; $p = 0.347$) (see Table 1, p.18).

5. Discussion

In sum, higher degrees of digitalization in occupations may lead to both improvements and encumbrances for employees in the second half of working life in Germany, such as more occupational stress due to negative environmental factors. However, overall job satisfaction is higher for employees working in more digitalized occupations. These findings are in line with related studies on job quality in times of digitalization (Handel, 2005; Hoonakker, 2014; Olsen, Kalleberg, & Nesheim, 2010).

5.1. Digitalization and Job Quality

Overall, employees in more digitalized occupations differ in a few aspects of job satisfaction from employees in less digitized jobs. They are more satisfied with their working hours. This may result from greater flexibility in working time arrangements and opportunities to work from home facilitated by new technologies. In line with this, digitalization is associated with lower levels of stress due to tight schedules, deadlines or nervous tensions. This result seems surprising, since in the literature digitalization has been associated with higher stress levels due to an intensification and acceleration of work (Green, 2004; Green & McIntosh, 2001). However, one explanation – in line with the findings of Shultz et al. (2010) – could be that those employees enjoy more flexibility to organize their work. Thus they are provided with more room for maneuver to deal with tight schedules and deadlines and are consequently able to cope with the acceleration of work. Furthermore, employees working in more digitalized occupations report lower satisfaction with opportunities to take part in employer-provided further training. However, this association was found in the pure model only. This may be because more digitalized jobs involve less training. Contrary to our expectations, perceived stress due to strenuous physical activities and negative environmental factors was on average higher among employees working in more digitalized occupations. It can be assumed that more digitalized occupations are not only those with inherently worse opportunities for further training but also those with worse working environments or more physically demanding work.

5.2. Compositional Effects

Our findings show that controlling for compositional effects is important when investigating subjective job quality. More digitalized occupations were characterized by lower subjective job quality or at least their employees were more likely to have characteristics usually associated with low job quality. Because under control of compositional effects, we find the job satisfaction index and satisfaction with work as a whole positively associated with more digitalized occupations. The negative

association with employees' satisfaction with further training is not significant after controlling for compositional effects. Corresponding to the findings of the pure model, satisfaction with working hours is higher and stress due to tight schedules is lower when working in more digitalized occupations. And the higher the degree of digitalization in occupations the higher the satisfaction with career prospects or promotion. Since digitalization processes in occupations rely on transformation processes, old structures may be revised and new opportunities for career development may open up. Another explanation could be that digitalization leads to a higher demand for skilled workers who are able to create, serve or maintain new technologies or evaluate and analyze data collected by new technologies (Goldin & Katz, 2008; Goos & Manning, 2007). Moreover, the compositional model also shows employees working in more digitalized occupations reporting higher stress due to negative environmental factors. The assumed inherent higher physical strain and worse working environments in more digitalized occupations seems to partly explain the reported higher stress due to onerous physical and environmental factors. A further explanation could be that new technologies bring along some negative work environments such as noise, bright screens or flashing light signals. Industrial robots working at high speed may create loud noise and employees working frequently with video screens may perceive stress due to overly dim or bright light. These results are consistent with findings from other studies that found an increase in hard work and stress due to physical work or higher exhaustion over time (Handel, 2005; Olsen, Kalleberg, & Nesheim, 2010). Lastly, even if wages and other factors are assumed to be equal between employees, those working in more digitalized occupations are more satisfied with their earnings. Employees in more digitalized occupations may experience their work as less burdensome overall and respectively more rewarding in terms of non-monetary aspects. Therefore, earnings may be less of a compensation for onerous experiences at work if satisfaction with other work-related aspects is high. For example, higher flexibility and better work-life balance may explain higher reported levels of satisfaction with earnings in more digitalized occupations. Although company size might correspond with greater financial capacities to provide or improve aspects of objective job quality, several aspects of subjective job quality are found to be lower for employees working in larger

companies. This may be due to higher anonymity and more rigid structures in larger companies. Such less attention may be paid to individual preferences and circumstances. Employees with high education and good assessed health have been found to report better job quality. We assume that those beneficial aspects translate into more advantageous working conditions and therefore in higher job satisfaction and less stress.

5.3. Job Insecurity

Taking into account that some employees might fear losing their jobs due to substitution processes induced by digitalization in the job insecurity model, the findings remain broadly as in the compositional model. Digitalizations associations with different aspects of subjective job quality do not change meaningfully. Nonetheless, subjective job insecurity proved an important control variable, as it was associated with lower levels of (aspects of) job satisfaction. The higher an employee's job insecurity, the more stressed they feel about environmental factors and new responsibilities, and the more stressed they feel in general.

5.4. Limitations

Since these analyses are based on cross-sectional data, it is not clear if digitalization is associated with job satisfaction and perceived stress in the long term or if the associations discovered here are transitional. Future analysis using longitudinal data could shed light on this issue. Also, the concept of digitalization of occupations based on substitution potential only indicates the potential degree of automation within occupations, not the extent to which occupations actually were automated. Hence, the concept relates more to technical feasibility than to the implementation of new technologies. Furthermore, substitution potential does not indicate an exact degree of digitalization of single jobs. The realization of the potential is very specific to the economic situation, organizational preferences or the management style of companies. The substitution potential data used in these analyses only approximate digitalization in occupations. An additional limitation is the overrepresentation of high educated employees in the sample. As mentioned above, highly educated employees

differ from lower educated regarding the occupation they are working in. However, the imbalance of the data regarding education bias results only in the pure model. In the other models, it is controlled for educational level.

5.5. Conclusion

This work provides three key findings. First, for employees aged 40 and above in Germany, higher degrees of digitalization of occupations correspond with predominantly higher subjective job quality. Second, the use of global measures or index measures to depict job quality can be misleading, since different aspects of job quality may show opposing trends which could cancel each other out at the aggregate level. Therefore, regarding subjective job quality and digitalization, it is crucial to pay close attention to the multidimensionality of job quality. In order to develop effective measures to improve job quality, detailed and comprehensive insights are crucial. Third, the positive effects of digitalization on job quality may not show up if compositional effects underlying the workforce are not controlled for, since employees working in occupations showing higher degrees of digitalization may assess their job quality lower per se.

The adaption of new technologies puts new demands on employees and changes their everyday working life. The successful implementation of such technologies at work will, for sure, not take off by itself. Employees need to have the right skills to cope with emerging new work demands. The mismatch between employees' skills and requirements at work is known as one important determinant for occupational switching (Güvenen et al., 2020) and job dissatisfaction (Shevchuk, Strebkov, & Davis, 2019). In 2015 every fifth person aged 25–64 in Germany showed only little digital competencies (Eurostat, 2015). And close to every fourth person states that new technologies have been introduced to the workplace, but no further training have been provided (Initiative D21, 2021). We found lower satisfaction with training provision in more digitalized occupations in the pure model, but the association was not significant under control of compositional effects. Nonetheless and particularly for that reason further research on digitalization and training participation is needed to reveal potential training gaps among different groups.

Recently, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the digitalization in the world of work. For many employees options like telework, online communication or e-commerce have enabled the continuation of work under statutory pandemic restrictions. Though, the sudden introduction of digital technology usage at work may have overwhelmed some employees. Potentials for improvements in the subjective job quality due to new technologies may have not been realized under these circumstances. Our results indicate that new technologies can improve the subjective job quality. However, the ongoing digitalization in the world of work needs to be accompanied by strong employment regulations and provision of further training for all employees.

6. Literature

- Andries, F., Smulders, P. G. W., & Dhondt, S. (2002). The use of computers among the workers in the European Union and its impact on the quality of work. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 21(6), 441-447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929021000036568>
- Arntz, M., Gregory, T., & Zierahn, U. (2016). *The Risk of Automation for Jobs in OECD countries. A Comparative Analysis* (OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers No. 189). <https://doi.org/10.1787/1815199X>
- Autor, D. H., Levy, F., & Murnane, R. J. (2003). The skill content of recent technological change: An empirical exploration. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(4), 1279-1333. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003355303322552801>
- Bannai, A., & Tamakoshi, A. (2014). The association between long working hours and health: A systematic review of epidemiological evidence. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, 40(1), 5-18. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.3388>
- Biagi, F., Naticchioni, P., Ragusa, G., & Vittori, C. (2018). Routinization and the Labour Market: Evidence from European Countries. In L. Pupillo, E. Noam, & L. Waverman (Eds.), *Digitized Labor: The Impact of the Internet on Employment* (pp. 51-69). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-78420-5_4
- Bondanini, G., Giorgi, G., Ariza-Montes, A., Vega-Muñoz, A., & Andreucci-Annunziata, P. (2020). Technostress Dark Side of Technology in the Workplace: A Scientometric Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(21), 8013. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17218013>

- Brown, A., Charlwood, A., Forde, C., & Spencer, D. (2007). Job quality and the economics of New Labour: A critical appraisal using subjective survey data. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, 31(6), 941-971. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cje/bem028>
- Burke, R. J. (1976). Occupational Stresses and Job Satisfaction. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 100(2), 235-244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.1976.9711934>
- Busch, A. (2013). *Die berufliche Geschlechtersegregation in Deutschland: Ursachen, Reproduktion, Folgen [Occupational gender segregation in Germany]*. Springer VS. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-01707-1>
- Cascales Mira, M. (2021). New Model for Measuring Job Quality: Developing an European Intrinsic Job Quality Index (EIJQI). *Social Indicators Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-021-02615-9>
- Clark, A. E. (2011). Worker Well-Being in Booms and Busts. In P. Gregg (Ed.), *The Labour Market in Winter* (pp. 128-143). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780199587377.003.0010>
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2. ed.). Erlbaum.
- Cortes, G. M. (2016). Where Have the Middle-Wage Workers Gone? A Study of Polarization Using Panel Data. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 34(1), 63-105. <https://doi.org/10.1086/682289>
- Datenreport 2018. (2018). *Ein Sozialbericht für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland*. Ed.: Statistischen Bundesamt (Destatis), Wissenschaftszentrum Berlin für Sozialforschung (WZB), in cooperation with Das Sozio-oekonomische Panel (SOEP) at Deutsches Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung (DIW Berlin).
- Dengler, K., & Matthes, B. (2018). The impacts of digital transformation on the labour market: Substitution potentials of occupations in Germany. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 137(2018), 304-316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.09.024>
- Dengler, K., & Matthes, B. (2019). Digitalisierung in Deutschland. Substituierbarkeitspotenziale von Berufen und die möglichen Folgen für die Beschäftigung. In R. Dobischat, B. Käßlinger, G. Molzberger, & D. Münk (Eds.), *Bildung 2.1 für Arbeit 4.0?* (pp. 49-62). Springer VS. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-23373-0_3
- Dengler, K., & Tisch, A. (2020). Examining the Relationship Between Digital Transformation and Work Quality: Substitution Potential and Work Exposure in Gender-Specific Occupations. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 72, 427-453. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-020-00674-3>
- Eurostat. (2015). *Individuals' level of digital skills* (isoc_sk_dskl_i) [indicator]. https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=isoc_sk_dskl_i&lang=en

- Felstead, A., & Henseke, G. (2017). Assessing the growth of remote working and its consequences for effort, well-being and work-life balance. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 32(3), 195-212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ntwe.12097>
- Fernández-Macías, E. (2012). Job Polarization in Europe? Changes in the Employment Structure and Job Quality, 1995-2007. *Work and Occupations*, 39(2), 157-182. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888411427078>
- Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation? *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 114, 254-280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.08.019>
- Gallie, D. (2003). The Quality of Working Life: Is Scandinavia Different? *European Sociological Review*, 19(1), 61-79. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/19.1.61>
- Gallie, D. (2007). *Employment regimes and the quality of work*. Oxford Univ. Pr. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199230105.001.0001>
- Ganster, D. C., & Rosen, C. C. (2013). Work Stress and Employee Health: A Multidisciplinary Review. *Journal of Management*, 39(5), 1085-1122. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206313475815>
- Gerr, F., Marcus, M., Ensor, C., Kleinbaum, D., Cohen, S., Edwards, A., Gentry, E., Ortiz, D. J., & Monteilh, C. (2002). A prospective study of computer users: I. Study design and incidence of musculoskeletal symptoms and disorders. *American Journal Of Industrial Medicine*, 41(4), 221-235. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajim.10066>
- Gerr, F., Monteilh, C. P., & Marcus, M. (2006). Keyboard use and musculoskeletal outcomes among computer users. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, 16(3), 259-271. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-006-9037-0>
- Goldin, C. D., & Katz, L. F. (2008). *The Race Between Education and Technology*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjf9x5x>
- Goos, M., & Manning, A. (2007). Lousy and Lovely Jobs: The Rising Polarization of Work in Britain. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 89(1), 118-133. <https://doi.org/10.1162/rest.89.1.118>
- Green, F. (2004). Work Intensification, Discretion, and the Decline in Well-Being at Work. *Eastern Economic Journal*, 30(4), 615-625. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40326152>
- Green, F. (2006). Workers' Well-Being. In F. Green (Ed.), *Demanding Work* (pp. 150-169). Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400849437.150>
- Green, F., & McIntosh, S. (2001). The intensification of work in Europe. *Labour Economics*, 8(2), 291-308. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-5371\(01\)00027-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-5371(01)00027-6)

- Guvenen, F., Kuruscu, B., Tanaka, S., & Wiczer, D. (2020). Multidimensional Skill Mismatch. *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 12(1), 210-244. <https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20160241>
- Gyllensten, K., & Palmer, S. (2005). The role of gender in workplace stress: A critical literature review. *Health Education Journal*, 64(3), 271-288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001789690506400307>
- Haar, J. M., Russo, M., Suñe, A., & Ollier-Malaterre, A. (2014). Outcomes of work–life balance on job satisfaction, life satisfaction and mental health: A study across seven cultures. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 85(3), 361-373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2014.08.010>
- Handel, M. J. (2005). Trends in Perceived Job Quality, 1989 to 1998. *Work and Occupations*, 32(1), 66-94. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888404271901>
- Hauk, N., Goritz, A. S., & Krumm, S. (2019). The mediating role of coping behavior on the age-technostress relationship: A longitudinal multilevel mediation model. *PLoS one*, 14(3), e0213349. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0213349>
- Hauk, N., Hüffmeier, J., & Krumm, S. (2018). Ready to be a Silver Surfer? A Meta-analysis on the Relationship Between Chronological Age and Technology Acceptance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 84, 304-319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.01.020>
- Henseke, G. (2018). Good jobs, good pay, better health? The effects of job quality on health among older European workers. *The European Journal of Health Economics*, 19(1), 59-73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10198-017-0867-9>
- Hill, E. J., Hawkins, A. J., Ferris, M., & Weitzman, M. (2001). Finding an Extra Day a Week: The Positive Influence of Perceived Job Flexibility on Work and Family Life Balance. *Family Relations*, 50(1), 49-58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3729.2001.00049.x>
- Hoonakker, P. (2014). Information and Communication Technology and Quality of Working Life: Backgrounds, Facts, and Figures. In C. Korunka & P. Hoonakker (Eds.), *The Impact of ICT on Quality of Working Life* (pp. 9-24). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8854-0>
- Hur, H. (2019). Job security matters. A systematic review and meta-analysis of the relationship between job security and work attitudes. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 1-31. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2019.3>
- Huxhold, O., Hees, E., & Webster, N. J. (2020). Towards bridging the grey digital divide: changes in internet access and its predictors from 2002 to 2014 in Germany. *European Journal of Ageing*, 17(3), 271-280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-020-00552-z>

- Initiative D21. (2021). *D21-Digital-Index 2020/ 2021. Jährliches Lagebild zur Digitalen Gesellschaft*. https://initiated21.de/app/uploads/2021/02/d21-digital-index-2020_2021.pdf
- Jensen, C. (2003). Development of neck and hand-wrist symptoms in relation to duration of computer use at work. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, 29(3), 197-205. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.722>
- Kahn, R. L., Wolfe, D. M., Quinn, R. P., Snoek, J. D., & Rosenthal, R. A. (1964). *Organizational stress: Studies in role conflict and ambiguity*. Wiley.
- Kirchner, S. (2015). Konturen der digitalen Arbeitswelt. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 67(4), 763-791. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-015-0344-3>
- Klaus, D., Engstler, H., Mahne, K., Wolff, J. K., Simonson, J., Wurm, S., & Tesch-Römer, C. (2017). Cohort Profile: The German Ageing Survey (DEAS). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 46(4), 1105-1105g. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw326>
- Körner, U., Müller-Thur, K., Lunau, T., Dragano, N., Angerer, P., & Buchner, A. (2019). Perceived stress in human-machine interaction in modern manufacturing environments. Results of a qualitative interview study. *Stress and Health*, 35(2), 187-199. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smi.2853>
- Muñoz de Bustillo, R., Fernández-Macías, E., Esteve, F., & Antón, J.-I. (2011). E pluribus unum? A critical survey of job quality indicators. *Socio-Economic Review*, 9(3), 447-475. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwr005>
- Ng, T. W. H., & Feldman, D. C. (2010). The Relationships of Age with Job Attitudes: A Meta-Analysis. *Personnel Psychology*, 63(3), 677-718. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2010.01184.x>
- Nguyen, C. D., Carlin, J. B., & Lee, K. J. (2017). Model checking in multiple imputation: An overview and case study. *Emerging Themes in Epidemiology*, 14(8). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12982-017-0062-6>
- Olsen, K. M., Kalleberg, A. L., & Nesheim, T. (2010). Perceived job quality in the United States, Great Britain, Norway and West Germany, 1989-2005. *European Journal of Industrial Relations*, 16(3), 221-240. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959680110375133>
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development – OECD. (2021, 20.08.2021). *ICT Access and Use by Businesses*. OECD Telecommunications and Internet Statistics. Retrieved 30.08.2021 from <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/content/data/9d2cb97b-en>
- OECD, Eurostat, & UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2015). *ISCED 2011 Operational Manual. Guidelines for Classifying National Education Programmes and Related*

Qualifications. OECD Publishing.

<https://doi.org/doi:https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264228368-en>

Perugini, C., & Vladisavljević, M. (2019). Gender inequality and the gender-job satisfaction paradox in Europe. *Labour Economics*, 60, 129-147.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2019.06.006>

Piasna, A., & Drahokoupil, J. (2017). Gender inequalities in the new world of work. *Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research*, 23(3), 313-332.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1024258917713839>

Podsakoff, N. P., LePine, J. A., & LePine, M. A. (2007). Differential Challenge Stressor-Hindrance Stressor Relationships With Job Attitudes, Turnover Intentions, Turnover, and Withdrawal Behavior: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(2), 438-454.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.2.438>

Ragu-Nathan, T. S., Tarafdar, M., Ragu-Nathan, B. S., & Tu, Q. (2008). The Consequences of Technostress for End Users in Organizations: Conceptual Development and Empirical Validation. *Information Systems Research*, 19(4), 417-433.

<https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.1070.0165>

Royuela, V., & Suriñach, J. (2013). Quality of Work and Aggregate Productivity. *Social Indicators Research*, 113(1), 37-66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-012-0081-1>

Rubin, D. B. (1987). *Multiple imputation for nonresponse in surveys*. John Wiley & Sons.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470316696>

Shevchuk, A., Strebkov, D., & Davis, S. N. (2019). Skill mismatch and work-life conflict: the mediating role of job satisfaction. *Journal of Education and Work*, 32(2), 181-195.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2019.1616281>

Shultz, K. S., Wang, M., Crimmins, E. M., & Fisher, G. G. (2010). Age Differences in the Demand-Control Model of Work Stress: An Examination of Data From 15 European Countries. *Journal of Applied Gerontology*, 29(1), 21-47.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0733464809334286>

Siegrist, J., Wahrendorf, M., von dem Knesebeck, O., Jürges, H., & Börsch-Supan, A. (2006). Quality of work, well-being, and intended early retirement of older employees. Baseline results from the SHARE Study. *European Journal of Public Health*, 17(1), 62-68.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckl084>

Smith, J., Fleeson, W., Geiselman, B., & Settersten, R. (2010). Wohlbefinden im hohen Alter. Vorhersagen aufgrund objektiver Lebensbedingungen und subjektiver Bewertung. In U. Lindenberger, J. Smith, K. U. Mayer, & P. B. Baltes (Eds.), *Die Berliner Altersstudie* (3. ed., pp. 521-547). Akademie Verlag. <http://hdl.handle.net/21.11116/0000-0000-E1D4-2>

- Soh, M., Zarola, A., Palaiou, K., & Furnham, A. (2016). Work-related well-being. *Health Psychology Open*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055102916628380>
- Sverke, M., Hellgren, J., & Näswall, K. (2002). No security: A meta-analysis and review of job insecurity and its consequences. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 7(3), 242-264. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1076-8998.7.3.242>
- Tarafdar, M., Tu, Q., Ragu-Nathan, T., & Ragu-Nathan, B. (2011). Crossing to the Dark Side: Examining Creators, Outcomes, and Inhibitors of Technostress. *Communications of the ACM*, 54(9), 113-120. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1995376.1995403>
- Theurel, J., & Desbrosses, K. (2019). Occupational Exoskeletons: Overview of Their Benefits and Limitations in Preventing Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders. *IISE Transactions on Occupational Ergonomics and Human Factors*, 7(3-4), 264-280. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24725838.2019.1638331>
- Thorsteinson, T. J. (2003). Job attitudes of part-time vs. full-time workers: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 76(2), 151-177. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317903765913687>
- Wagner, G. G., Pischner, R., & Haisken-DeNew, J. P. (2002). The Changing Digital Divide in Germany. In B. Wellman & C. Haythornthwaite (Eds.), *The Internet in Everyday Life* (pp. 164-185). Blackwell Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470774298.ch5>
- Warr, P. (1999). Well-being and the Workplace. In D. Kahneman, E. Diener, & N. Schwarz (Eds.), *Well-being: The Foundations of Hedonic Psychology* (pp. 392-412). Russell Sage Foundation.
- Warr, P., & Birdi, K. (1998). Employee age and voluntary development activity. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 2(3), 190-204. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2419.00047>

Appendix

Table 1: Digitalisation and Job Quality, Models 1–3.

job satisfaction		index		... with work as a whole		...with earnings		...with the kind of work		...with working hours		...with career development or promotion		...with further training		...with the working atmosphere	
		b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
Pure Model	digitalisation	0.009	0.068	0.092	0.077	-0.034	0.103	-0.004	0.085	0.429	0.099	-	-	-0.362	0.127	-0.020	0.093
Composition Model	digitalisation	0.172	0.073	0.181	0.085	0.253	0.109	0.069	0.094	0.465	0.104	0.249	0.124	-0.109	0.144	0.103	0.104
Job Insecurity Model	digitalisation	0.188	0.072	0.198	0.084	0.266	0.108	0.081	0.093	0.473	0.104	0.274	0.122	-0.081	0.142	0.116	0.103
	subj. job insecurity	-0.165	0.024	-0.180	0.028	-0.130	0.036	-0.124	0.031	-0.073	0.035	-0.248	0.040	-0.285	0.048	-0.128	0.034

occupational stress		index		... due to physical activities		... due to environmental factors		... due to tight schedules		... due to new responsibilities	
		b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
Pure Model	digitalisation	0.106	0.080	0.381	0.122	0.810	0.126	-0.618	0.107	-	-
Composition Model	digitalisation	-0.034	0.086	-0.055	0.128	0.345	0.136	-0.518	0.115	0.093	0.127
Job Insecurity Model	digitalisation	-0.040	0.086	-0.060	0.128	0.336	0.136	-0.522	0.115	0.085	0.127
	subj. job insecurity	0.065	0.028	0.051	0.042	0.091	0.045	0.036	0.038	<i>0.081</i>	0.042

Source: DEAS 2014. N=1541. Note: All models include the control variables gender, residency, age. From the composition model onwards it is controlled for: education, sector, company size, SRH, wage, working hours. The job insecurity model additionally controls for subjective job insecurity (1=low–5=high). Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics; “-”: model is not significant. Rounded to three decimal places. Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes.

III. Digitalization in Occupations and Self-perceptions of Aging of Older Workers

Authors: Lisa Katharina Kortmann, Georg Henning, Oliver Huxhold

Accepted: 29th September 2023 Published online: 24th October 2023

Journal: The Journal of Ageing and Social Change, 13 (2): 129-156

Abstract: Digitalization alters working processes, contents, and skill demands for workers. Common age stereotypes attribute lower digital competences and abilities to adapt to technological changes to older workers. Thus far, it is unclear how workers' self-perceptions of aging (SPA) are affected by the emergence of digital skill demands at work. Therefore, this study investigates if and how digital skill demands in occupations are associated with the level of and changes in older workers' SPA. To shed light on this question, data from the German Ageing Survey (2014 and 2017) is used. In latent change score models, the level and change of workers' SPA in the domains of physical and social losses, ongoing development, and self-knowledge are investigated. Level and change of digitalization in workers' occupations are used as predictors of change and are based on digital skill demands in occupations that are determined via job ads data. Interindividual differences in the baseline levels and interindividual differences in changes in all domains of SPA are found. When controlling for digitalization in occupations, sociodemographic and job related characteristics, higher digitalization levels (DLs) in occupations are associated with improvements in SPA in the domains of ongoing development and self-knowledge. No significant associations with older workers' SPA are found for changes in the DL. Our results suggest that compassionate ageism that intends to protect older workers from digital demands is inappropriate, since indications of empowering effects in some domains of SPA have been found.

Keywords: Digital Skills; Self-Perceptions of Aging; Ageism; Latent Change Score Approach; Stereotype Embodiment Theory

1. Introduction

Individual's attitudes toward their own aging, namely self-perceptions of aging (SPA), are known to be influenced by contextual factors like the working environment (Bandura, 1986). Similarly, embodied age stereotypes can affect people's SPA (Levy, 2009). Since ongoing digitalization has and will alter working processes and several existing age stereotypes attribute low technology competences or low ability to adapt to changes at work to older individuals (Petery et al., 2020; Posthuma & Campion, 2009), the question appears if and how an occupations' digitalization level (DL) is related to the SPA of older workers. To date, little is known on that topic, although it is highly relevant in the face of recent demographic and economic trends. In many developed countries, demographic trends put welfare systems and labor markets increasingly under pressure. At the same time, digitalization processes create new skill demands on the labor market and force workers to adapt to new demands in many areas. This study focuses on older workers in their middle and late adulthood in Germany, which is a country that is particularly challenged by the above-mentioned trends. The funding of the pay-as-you-go pension scheme in Germany is highly dependent on contributions from the economically active population. In order to avert the increasing imbalance between contributors and beneficiaries in the welfare state, recent policies aim at maintaining the employability of workers and prolonging working lives. Here, positive SPA may help to counteract early retirement, as they have been found to be associated with several psychological and physical outcomes, such as better self-rated health, longevity, better performance of activities of daily living, and better cognitive functioning (Tully-Wilson et al., 2021). Thus, particularly in view of demographic trends and digitalization processes in the world of work, it becomes increasingly relevant for older workers not to perceive aging as a loss of potential and abilities but as a phase of ongoing development and lifelong learning.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Digitalization in the World of Work

Digitalization has and will change work processes, contents and skill demands for workers. Changes can be observed at the occupational and the individual level. Based

on the task-based approach (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003) studies have shown that task profiles – and relatedly the skill content – within occupations have changed profoundly over the past years due to technological change (Spitz-Oener, 2006). The task-based approach assumes that while some occupational tasks, namely routine tasks, can be automated or substituted due to new, digital technologies, others are not automatable (yet) (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003). Therefore, it is argued in the literature that some occupations will be more affected by changes due to digitalization processes than others (Autor, Levy, & Murnane, 2003; European Commission et al., 2019).

This change is also reflected on the individual level. It appears that workers in different occupations have faced and will face different demands for digital skills. In general, the relevance and pace of learning at the workplace has been growing over the past years as digitalization increased the skill variety in jobs and lowered the half-time of knowledge and competencies (Kubicek, Paškvan, & Korunka, 2015; Wegman et al., 2018). Over recent years, the overall demand for digital skills in occupations in Germany increased, while the demand varies between specific occupations (O'Kane et al., 2020). This implies, in line with the task-based approach, that some workers are exposed to greater changes at work due to digitalization and need to adapt more than others to new skill demands. Compared to younger workers who are new to the labor market, older workers in their middle and late adulthood may be settled in a job and have built their skill set over a longer period of professionalization in their chosen occupation.

2.2. Age Stereotypes and Workplace Digitalization

A vast range of negative and positive stereotypes about older workers has been identified in literature (Petery et al., 2020). In the context of workplace digitalization, negative age stereotypes assume older workers to be resistant to change, less willing to learn, uncomfortable with technologies, less flexible, or relying on outdated knowledge and methods (Petery et al., 2020; Posthuma & Campion, 2009). Of course, there are also positive general age stereotypes that do not specifically relate to the handling of digital technologies, such as older workers being more reliable. However,

negative stereotypes outnumber the positive ones (Bal et al., 2011; Posthuma & Campion, 2009).

According to Levy's (2009) stereotype embodiment theory, age stereotypes are internalized across the individual's life span and become self-relevant as individuals age and identify themselves with the stereotyped age group. The endorsement of age stereotypes relating to older workers can result in age discrimination and is linked to insufficient or lack of opportunities for training or promotion (North & Fiske, 2016). In addition, age stereotypes seem to have direct deteriorating effects on workers themselves, like lower work engagement or a stronger desire to retire (Weber, Angerer, & Müller, 2019). Perceived age stereotypes can even be found in job ads and can act as employment barriers for older people (Bal et al., 2011; Burn et al., 2021). Embodied age stereotypes can, therefore, impact on individuals' self-views, such as their SPA (Kornadt, Voss, & Rothermund, 2015). Specifically, being confronted with digital skill demands at work, age stereotypes related to digitalization may become self-relevant for older workers in their middle and late adulthood. To date, it is not entirely clear whether and how digitalization processes in the work context are related to older workers' SPA. Hence, this study investigates whether or not and in what way digitalization in occupations is associated with older workers' SPA.

2.3. Self-Perceptions of Aging

The concept of SPA is well described by Diehl et al. (2021) as "individuals' perceptions of their own aging that they can articulate and reflect about". They are based on individuals' personal experiences with their own age and aging process and expectations about their future development. It is emphasized in the literature that individuals hold multiple, domain-specific SPA that can be gain or loss oriented and change over the life course (Diehl et al., 2021; Jung et al., 2021; Kornadt & Rothermund, 2015). It has been demonstrated that the concept of SPA is different from more general dispositional or well-being concepts like negative affect or self-rated health, and also different from the related concept of *subjective age* (Spuling et al., 2020). In contrast to SPA, subjective age simply refers to how old an individual feels in relation to their chronological age (Stephan, 2021). It is usually measured by single-

item questions like “What age do you feel?”.⁴⁵ Hence, an individual’s felt age is neither an assessment of his or her (dis)satisfaction with own age or the aging process nor is it sensitive for potential variations in different life domains.⁴⁶ This work is interested in workers’ evaluative attitudes toward their own age and aging process – their SPA – and its relation to digitalization.

In general, SPA have been found to be an important predictor for several physiological and psychological outcomes (Tully-Wilson et al., 2021). Specifically, it has been shown that positive SPA protect against daily stressors (O’Brien, Torres, & Neupert, 2020), are associated with higher social involvement (Schwartz, Ayalon, & Huxhold, 2020), lower risks for dementia (Levy et al., 2018), less cognitive declines, and better self-rated health (Sargent-Cox, Anstey, & Luszcz, 2012; Siebert, Wahl, & Schröder, 2016; Westerhof et al., 2014; Wurm et al., 2017). In the working context, more negative SPA were found to be associated with lower occupational self-efficacy (Paggi & Jopp, 2015).⁴⁷

2.4. Digitalization and Self-Perceptions of Aging

To our knowledge, only a few studies have investigated the relationship between of SPA and digitalization. The existing studies on this topic found more positive SPA of older individuals to be associated with higher use of different kinds of new, digital technologies, such as the computer or the internet (Chen & Chan, 2014; Cohn-Schwartz, Schafer, & Ayalon, 2022; Mariano et al., 2021a, 2021b). In detail, higher private computer use by older individuals has been found to be associated with more positive general SPA three years later; and in line with that, higher general internet use seems to precede more positive SPA in the domains of ongoing development and social losses (Köttl, Cohn-Schwartz, & Ayalon, 2021; Mariano et al., 2021a, 2021b).

⁴⁵ While in the majority of recent literature a unidimensional concept of subjective age is used (measured by single-item questions), in early literature subjective age was defined as multidimensional concept and included assessments on how old an individual looks, feels, acts, and what interests they have (Barak, 1987; Kastenbaum et al., 1972).

⁴⁶ See Gendron, Inker and Welleford (2017) for a thorough critique on the operationalization of subjective age in recent literature.

⁴⁷ For a summary on recent literature on associations of subjective age and work outcomes see Cleveland, Hanscom and Huebner (2017) and (Rudolph, Kunze, & Zacher, 2019).

This pattern is also supported by some specific internet uses and age(ing)-related self-perceptions about of one's own competences (Mariano et al., 2021b). In turn, the general SPA of older individuals have been found to be associated with higher private computer use three years later (Mariano et al., 2021a); while only higher competence-related SPA seem to precede higher internet use in general and for several social or functional causes, like searching information, communication with existing contacts, or online banking (Mariano et al., 2021b). This pattern is also matched by the findings of Cheng and Chan (2008), who observed more positive SPA and life satisfaction to be associated with a higher use of diverse gerontechnology products among older individuals. In contrast to this, Köttl and colleagues (2021) found no evidence for any domain of SPA being associated with an older individual's engagement in private internet use three years later.

Overall, previous literature mainly indicates a positive interrelation of the use of digital technologies and older individuals' SPAs, especially those related to personal competences. However, the literature outlined above either used cross-sectional approaches (Chen & Chan, 2014), general SPA measures (Mariano et al., 2021a), or focused on the private and very specific uses of digital technologies of older persons (Chen & Chan, 2014; Köttl, Cohn-Schwartz, & Ayalon, 2021; Mariano et al., 2021a, 2021b). To our knowledge, there is no literature on the SPA-digitalization-interrelation focussing on the working context specifically. However, being confronted with digital technologies at work may differ significantly from the private context, since it may be less linked to one's own motivation, learning competence, and preferences. Therefore, we contribute to the literature by shedding light on the working context and investigating the association of different domains of workers' SPA and the general demands for digital skills, not the use of specific technologies.

3. The Present Study – Digitalization and Workers' Self-Perceptions of Aging

Specifically, we are investigating the following questions in the present study:

- (1) Is the DL of workers' occupations associated with their SPA?
- (2) Is the DL of workers' occupations associated with changes in their SPA?

(3) Is the change in the digitalization level (CDL) of workers' occupations associated with changes in their SPA?

Building on data from the 2014 and 2017 waves of the German Aging Survey, we model changes in older workers' SPA between 2014 and 2017 using a latent change score (LCS) approach within the structural equation modeling framework. The DL of older workers' occupations is used as a predictor for changes in SPA.

3.1. Hypotheses

In line with the stereotype embodiment theory (Levy, 2009), internalised age stereotypes about older people having lower digital competencies and being less capable of adapting to changes at work (Petery et al., 2020; Posthuma & Campion, 2009) may become self-relevant for older workers in their middle and late adulthood as they are confronted with rising demands for digital skills at work. They may experience a devaluation of existing skills or a lack of relevant digital competences as they are exposed to new digital technologies or work processes. This may lead to a deterioration of a worker's SPA related to ongoing development and self-knowledge. Workers may question their ability to adapt to new demands at work and may harbor doubts about being able to rely on their existing competences to do valuable work. Existing age stereotypes, that attribute, for example, lower capabilities to adapt to changes or to deal with new technologies to older individuals, may weaken workers' confidence in coping with new digital demands at work. Moreover, being aware that other individuals may harbor negative age stereotypes toward older workers, older employees may feel less needed and respected by colleagues, clients, or superiors. This may lead to a deterioration of their SPA in the social domain in general. In the context of digitalization, SPA related to the physical constitution of older workers are probably least affected by negative stereotypes about older workers. On the one hand, digital technologies can in fact be expected to relieve workers from physically demanding tasks. On the other hand, digitalization can accelerate work processes (Hoonakker, 2014). Since older workers sometimes are stereotyped as slow in completing tasks (Petery et al., 2020), SPA related to a worker's physical constitution may become more negative when working in more digital occupations. Based on

Levy's stereotype embodiment theory and the aforementioned considerations outlined earlier, we make the following assumption regarding all SPA domains:

(H1) The higher the DL in workers' occupations, the more negative their SPA. The incorporation of age stereotypes into one's view of their own aging may happen immediately or with a delay. It is also conceivable that working in a more digital occupation may go along with a more extensive exposure to related age stereotypes and consequently result in lower SPA. Therefore, in addition to our first hypothesis, we additionally assume the following:

(H2) Working in occupations with higher DL is associated with stronger decreases in the SPA of workers over time.

Workplace digitalization is an ongoing process and develops differently in different occupations. Some occupations show high demands for digital skills ever since, e.g., software engineers. Other occupations, that showed low or moderate demands for digital skills previously, can experience a digitalization push due to the emergence of useful technological innovations and their increasing proliferation, e.g., restaurant managers. Here, we expect greater needs for adapting to new, digital work demands for older workers and relatedly to find stronger decreases in older workers' SPA:

(H3) Working in occupations with more pronounced changes in the DL is associated with stronger decreases in the SPA of workers over time.

3.2. Method

3.2.1. Data and Sample

To answer the research questions, data from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS, dt.: Deutscher Alterssurvey) for the years 2014 and 2017 was used. The DEAS is a nationwide, cross-sectional, and longitudinal cohort study, representative of the German community-dwelling population aged 40 years and older (Klaus et al., 2017). It is based on computer-assisted personal interviews conducted in the interviewees' household supplemented by a short, written questionnaire for self-completion (Drop off). The DEAS contains rich information on the living and working situation of individuals, as well as attitudes toward and assessments of different aspects of life, for example, aging. Data on the extent of digitalization in occupations in Germany was

determined by Bertelsmann and Burning Glass Technologies (O’Kane et al., 2020) and matched to DEAS data using the International Standard Classification of Occupations 2008. The final sample contained workers aged 40–65 years working full- or part-time or in irregular or marginal employment in Germany at the time of the interview. The baseline sample comprised $n_{2014} = 2,722$ workers, whereof 53.63 percent were women, 48.49 percent had a high educational level, and the mean age was 54 years ($SD_{age} = 5.99$), in 2017, 1,567 workers participated again (Table 1).

Table 1: Sample Description of the Study Variables, 2014.

Variable	Range / Coding	Categories	Mean / %	Standard Deviation	Observations
Gender	(0 1)	0 = Female 1 = Male	53.6 46.4	0.01	2,722
Region	(0 1)	0 = East Germany 1 = West Germany	31.0 69.0	0.01	2,722
Education	(0 1)	0 = Not high (ISCED 0–4) 1 = High (ISCED 5–6)	51.5 48.5	0.01	2,722
Age	40–65	years	53.5	5.99	2,722
Self-Rated Health	1–5	1 = very bad– 5 = very good	3.69	0.78	2,720
Digitalization Level (DL)	0–88		4.2	15.64	2,715
Change in DL	-5 to 33		14.6	7.15	2,715
<i>Self-perceptions of Aging</i>					
Index Physical Losses	1–4		2.3	0.52	2,661
Index Social Losses	1.25–4		3.2	0.51	2,664
Index Ongoing Development	1–4		3.1	0.50	2,673
Index Self-Knowledge	1.5–4		3.0	0.44	2,660

Note: FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014. ISCED = International Standard Classification of Education.

4. Analyses

We apply structural equation modeling using an LCS approach to investigate potential links between SPA of workers aged 40–65 years and digitalization in their occupations over time. We expect to find differences in the intraindividual change of SPA between workers operating in more digitalized occupations and workers in less digitalized occupations. The LCS approach allows model changes in workers’ SPA over time directly by a latent variable (McArdle, 2009). In our LCS model, we investigate changes

between two time points, 2014 (T1) and 2017 (T2). We assume that a worker's SPA at T2 can be perfectly explained by the baseline level of SPA at T1 and the change between SPA at T1 and T2 (Δ SPA). Hence, no residual for SPA at T2 has to be specified and the regressions of SPA at T1 as well as the Δ SPA on SPA at T2 are fixed to 1. Since the CDL between 2014 and 2018 could not have had an impact on other variables at T1, only the Δ SPA is regressed on the CDL. The path diagram in Figure 1 illustrates our specified LCS model. Data preparation was carried out in STATA 15, and LCS models were estimated in Mplus 8.7 (Muthén & Muthén, 2017). Selectivity bias was reduced by using full information maximum likelihood estimation (Acock, 2005). The highest share of missing values among the variables at T1 considered in our analyses was 2.03 percent on the SPA in the domains of physical losses and self-knowledge (eighty-seven cases).

Figure 1: Path Diagram of the Latent Change Score Model.

Notes: Control variables are gender, region, age, education, and self-rated health. SPA = Self-perceptions of aging. [1] = 2014. [2] = 2017. DL = Digitalization level. CDL = Change in the DL between 2014 and 2018. Source: Kortmann, Henning and Huxhold.

We include gender, age, region, education, and self-rated health as control variables at the baseline level (2014). Model fit was assessed using the comparative fit index (CFI), the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), and the standardized root mean residual (SRMR) as suggested in the literature (Usami, Hayes, & McArdle, 2016). CFIs of 0.90 or higher and RMSEA and SRMR values of 0.08 and lower indicate an acceptable model fit (Marsh, 2007). Standard errors were clustered at the level of

occupations. To ensure the robustness of our analysis, we reestimated our model (1) using a subsample of workers without a professional change between 2014 and 2017, (2) using a subsample of workers aged 50–65 years, (3) not including self-rated health as a control variable in the model, and (4) adding participation in further training as an additional control variable to the model. The results of these additional analyses are reported in Tables 3–6 in the Appendix.

4.1. Dependent Variables

SPA are measured by the Aging-related Cognitions (AgeCog) scales for domain-specific views on aging (Dittmann-Kohli et al., 1997; Steverink et al., 2001). The AgeCog scales refer to four different domains of life. Each of the four domain-specific SPA scales consists of four different statements on individuals' views on aging in the domains of physical losses (phyloss), social losses (socloss), ongoing development (ongdev), and self-knowledge (sfknow). Each statement starts with “Ageing means to me, that...” or “For me, getting older means that...”. The four-point answer scale reaches from 1 “strongly agree” to 4 “strongly disagree”. The reliability of the four scales is acceptable (phyloss: $\omega_{2014} = 0.79$, $\omega_{2017} = 0.78$; socloss: $\omega_{2014} = 0.73$, $\omega_{2017} = 0.74$; ongdev: $\omega_{2014} = 0.78$; $\omega_{2017} = 0.78$; sfknow: $\omega_{2014} = 0.63$; $\omega_{2017} = 0.62$) (Taber 2018). For an intuitive interpretation, the positively formulated items of the SPA domains' ongoing development and self-knowledge were inverted; such higher values can be interpreted as more positive SPA (Table 2).

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Matrix, 2014.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) Physical Loss	1									
(2) Social Loss	0.46*	1								
(3) Ongoing Development	0.39*	0.46*	1							
(4) Self-Knowledge	0.23*	0.33*	0.49*	1						
(5) Digitalization Level (DL)	0.02	0.08*	0.10*	-0.01	1					
(6) Change in DL	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.02	-0.20*	1				
(7) Gender	-0.05*	0.02	-0.04*	-0.07*	0.16*	-0.08*	1			
(8) Region	0.01	-0.04	0.07*	0.01	0.10*	0.03	0.02	1		
(9) Age	-0.01	-0.01	-0.05*	-0.02	-0.01	-0.01	0.04*	-0.01	1	
(10) Self-Rated Health	0.32*	0.16*	0.22*	0.14*	0.08*	0.04*	-0.02	0.03	-0.11*	1
(11) Education	0.02	0.09*	0.15*	0.03	0.22*	0.11*	0.08*	-0.05*	0.05*	0.10*

Note: FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014; n = 2,722. Significance level: * p < 0.05.

4.2. Independent Variables

Digitalization in occupations is depicted by two measures. First, the relative, average DL of occupations in 2014 and, second, the CDL that occupations experienced between 2014 and 2018. Both measures are determined based on information from online job ads by Burning Glass Technologies and Bertelsmann (O'Kane et al., 2020). Job ads data has been scraped from different online job boards, duplicates and other noise have been removed, and information on occupation and the demanded skills were identified with the help of a text recognition tool. Based on expert assessments, the identified skills were categorized and weighted according to their level of digital proficiency into five skill types, reaching from “not digital” to “digital proficiency”. For each occupation, the average recall for each weighted skill was determined, summed up, taken the log, and normalized (Colombo, Mercurio, & Mezzanzanica, 2019; O'Kane et al., 2020). The DL of occupations indicates the relative average demand for digital skills in occupations in Germany. Differences in the number of job ads of single occupations between 2014 and 2018 were taken into account in determining the CDL. Over the past years, data that is based on online job ads is gaining increasing attention in economics and social sciences (Cammeraat & Squicciarini, 2021; Mezzanzanica & Mercurio, 2019) and is used in several studies (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2020; Azar et al., 2020; Deming & Noray, 2020).

4.3. Control Variables

We include gender, region, age, education, and self-rated health in our model as control variables for potentially confounding effects. Educational level and self-rated health have been identified as important control variables when analysing SPA in the literature (Diehl et al., 2021; Tully-Wilson et al., 2021). Gender, region, and age are sampling variables in the German Ageing Survey. Gender is dummy coded with 1 equals “male” and 0 equals “female”. Whether a worker lives in East or West Germany is indicated by the dummy variable region with 1 equals “West Germany”. The worker’s age is measured in years. The educational level is based on the International Standard Classification for Education (ISCED) and distinguishes between 0 “low or middle education (ISCED 0–4)” and 1 “high education (ISCED 5–6),” where high education comprises tertiary education. Self-rated health was measured by the single-item

question “How would you rate your present state of health?” (Fayers & Sprangers, 2002). The five-point answer scale was inverted for a more intuitive interpretation and ranges now from 1 “very bad” to 5 “very good”. The DL, age, and self-rated health were centered at the mean. A detailed variable description and Pearson correlations of all variables in our analysis are presented in Table 1 and 2. Item formulations can be found in Table 7a in the Appendix.

5. Results

The results of our basic model revealed a significant positive mean change for the SPA domain of self-knowledge ($b = 0.037$, $SE = 0.011$, $p = 0.001$), meaning that workers’ average SPA in the domain of self-knowledge has improved significantly between T1 and T2. The mean change was not significant for the SPA domains of physical and social losses and ongoing development. However, the baseline level at T1 and the change in all domains of SPA vary significantly between older workers in their middle or late adulthood (*level: phyloss: $b = 0.273$, $SE = 0.007$, $p = 0.000$; socloss: $b = 0.262$, $SE = 0.007$, $p = 0.000$; ongdev: $b = 0.254$, $SE = 0.007$, $p = 0.000$; sfknow: $b = 0.197$, $SE = 0.006$, $p = 0.000$; change: phyloss: $b = 0.204$, $SE = 0.009$, $p = 0.000$; socloss: $b = 0.191$, $SE = 0.010$, $p = 0.000$; ongdev: $b = 0.176$, $SE = 0.009$, $p = 0.000$; sfknow: $b = 0.171$, $SE = 0.008$, $p = 0.000$) (Table 3).*

Table 3: Estimated Parameters for the Basic Model Assessing Domain-Specific Self-Perceptions of Aging of Workers Aged 40–65 Years.

	Physical Losses		Social Losses		Ongoing Development		Self-Knowledge	
	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)
Mean	2.335* (0.01)	0.007 (0.01)	3.225* (0.01)	0.015 (0.01)	3.065* (0.01)	0.015 (0.01)	3.015* (0.01)	0.037* (0.01)
Variiances	0.273* (0.01)	0.204* (0.01)	0.262* (0.01)	0.191* (0.01)	0.254* (0.01)	0.176* (0.01)	0.197* (0.01)	0.171* (0.01)
Akaike (AIC)	5,536.07		5,328.05		5,172.80		4,332.65	
Bayesian (BIC)	5,565.55		5,357.53		5,202.29		4,362.13	
Observations (n)	2,686		2,689		2,691		2,688	

Note: FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and 2017. Change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). Significance level: * $p < 0.05$.

These differences in changes between workers were further investigated in our LCS models controlling for potentially confounding effects, and findings are displayed in

Table 4. Working in occupations with higher DLs was associated with higher SPA in the domains of social losses and ongoing development at the baseline (socloss: $b = 0.002$, $SE = 0.001$, $p = 0.006$; ongdev: $b = 0.002$, $SE = 0.002$, $p = 0.003$). However, no significant associations of the DL of occupations with SPA in the domains of physical losses and self-knowledge were found. Therefore, our first hypothesis was not supported, respectively, contradicted by our findings (H1: more negative SPA if working in an occupation with higher DL). In addition, we found people working in occupations with higher DLs showing significantly higher improvements in their SPA related to ongoing development and self-knowledge (ongdev: $b = 0.002$, $SE = 0.001$, $p = 0.004$; sfknow: $b = 0.002$, $SE = 0.001$, $p = 0.002$). This did not support, respectively, contradict our second hypothesis (H2: stronger decreases in SPA if working in occupations with higher DL). Neither was our third hypothesis supported by our findings (H3: stronger decreases in SPA if working in occupations with more pronounced positive CDL) since more positive CDLs of workers' occupations between 2014 and 2018 were not associated with significant changes in any SPA domain between 2014 and 2017. Overall, all estimated models showed an acceptable fit (Table 4). Our results were supported by the additional analyses using subsamples or reestimating our model with slight modifications in the control variables (see Tables 3a–6a, Appendix). Only the estimations using a subsample of workers without professional changes between 2014 and 2017 differed slightly from the findings in our main analysis. The baseline levels of the DL were not significant in the SPA domains of social losses and ongoing development. Since the coefficients in both analyses are similar, we assume the differences in the significance levels result from lower statistical power in the analysis using the subsample of workers without professional changes. In additional estimations using the Attitudes Towards Own Aging subscale developed by the Philadelphia Geriatric Centre Moral Scale, no significant digitalization-SPA associations were found (Lawton, 1975; Liang & Bollen, 1983). Results are presented in Tables 1a and 2a in the Appendix.

Table 4: Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain-Specific Self-Perceptions of Aging of Workers Aged 40–65 Years.

	Physical Losses		Social Losses		Ongoing Development		Self-Knowledge	
	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)	Level b (SE)	Change b (SE)
Intercept	2.359*	0.980*	3.219*	1.240*	2.980*	1.066*	3.031*	1.424*
	(0.02)	(0.06)	(0.02)	(0.08)	(0.02)	(0.07)	(0.02)	(0.10)
Autoregression	-	-0.397*	-	-0.381*	-	-0.363*	-	-0.465*
		(0.02)		(0.02)		(0.02)		(0.03)
Digitalization Level (DL)	-0.001 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)
Change in DL	-	-0.001 (0.00)	-	0.002 (0.00)	-	<i>0.003</i> (0.00)	-	<i>0.002</i> (0.00)
Gender (male = 1)	-0.043* (0.02)	-0.014 (0.02)	0.009 (0.02)	-0.033 (0.02)	-.058* (0.02)	0.021 (0.02)	-0.061* (0.02)	-0.043* (0.02)
Age	0.002 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	<i>-0.003</i> (0.001)	-0.002 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002 (0.00)
Region (west = 1)	0.006 (0.02)	-0.026 (0.02)	-0.043* (0.02)	-0.025 (0.03)	0.074* (0.02)	-0.003 (0.02)	0.004 (0.02)	0.013 (0.03)
Education (high =1)	-0.018 (0.02)	-0.034 (0.02)	0.065* (0.02)	-0.003 (0.02)	0.125* (0.02)	0.022 (0.02)	0.018 (0.02)	-0.024 (0.02)
Self-Rated Health	0.216* (0.01)	0.071* (0.02)	0.099* (0.01)	0.034* (0.01)	0.125* (0.02)	<i>0.032</i> (0.01)	0.076* (0.01)	<i>0.023</i> (0.01)
$\chi^2(1)$	0.022*	p = 0.882	0.349*	p = 0.555	1.166*	p = 0.280	0.287*	p = 0.592
RMSEA (90% CI)	0.000	p = 0.996	0.000	p = 0.979	0.008	p = 0.937	0.000	p = 0.982
SRMR		0.000		0.002		0.004		0.001
CFI		1.000		1.000		1.000		1.000
Akaike (AIC)		81,070.44		81,077.30		80,784.49		80,107.65
Bayesian (BIC)		81,383.62		8,1390.48		81,097.67		80,042.83

Notes: 4. FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and 2017; $n_{2014} = 2,722$. Change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). SE = Standard Errors. The variables DL, age, and self-rated health are centred at grand mean. Significance levels: * $p < 0.05$, italic $p < 0.1$.

6. Discussion

In the present study, we investigated the association of workers' SPA in different domains of life with the extent of digitalization in their occupations. In our basic model, we found evidence for interindividual differences in all domains of SPA in the year 2014 and interindividual differences in the worker's changes in SPA over time. We only found for workers' self-knowledge-related SPA a significant mean improvement over time. For all other SPA domains, single trajectories of changes in workers' SPA cancel each other out at the group mean. Based on the finding that there are differences in changes in workers' SPA, we investigated digitalization in occupations as a predictor of interindividual differences in change, controlling for other job-related, as well as sociodemographic factors. We found people working in occupations with higher DLs to show significantly higher improvements in their SPA related to ongoing development

and self-knowledge. In addition, participants were found to hold less negative attitudes toward their own aging in the domain of social losses and more positive views in the domain of ongoing development if they were working in occupations with higher DLs in 2014.

Working in occupations with higher DLs may involve working in more age-diverse teams. Hence, older workers in their middle and late adulthood may have greater opportunities for exchange with workers from younger age groups. In addition, people working in occupations with higher DLs and who may, therefore, have a greater set of digital skills may also make use of their digital skills in other social contexts besides working life. For example, they might help others with computer problems or employ digital skills in volunteering activities. Overall, this may positively influence their SPA, especially in the social domain. This potential explanation for our findings would be in line with the intergroup contact theory that states that positive contact experiences with other age groups weaken a person's ingroup identification, which may be connected with negative age-stereotypes (Pettigrew, 1998). In relation to SPA, people aged 40 and above who have more younger individuals in their close social networks were found to show improvements in their general SPA over time (Cohn-Schwartz, Schafer, & Ayalon, 2022). However, potential associations between the age composition of companies or teams at work and workers' SPA have not been addressed to our knowledge. Though, higher age diversity at work is found to be associated with higher levels of perceived age discrimination among employees in Germany (Kunze, Boehm, & Bruch, 2011). An explanation for our findings that the DL of occupations was associated with improvements in SPA in the domains of ongoing development and self-knowledge could be that workers may hold more positive self-images of competence-related perceptions of their aging processes if working in more digital occupations. Specifically, the skills and competences used at work may be evaluated as up-to-date and valuable for today's society. Working in occupations with high digital demands, workers may gain positive experiences related to learning success, achievement of adapting well to new demands, and being encouraged to rely on their competences. Contrary to existing age stereotypes, their experiences in the workplace may give them the feeling of keeping up with the times, still being able to make valuable

contributions in the workplace, and being able to meet the challenge of changed skill demands at work. However, the digitalization-SPA associations could also be driven by selection processes of highly competent individuals into more digital occupations since, for example, computer skill requirements in jobs can act as a recruitment barrier for some older workers (Turek & Henkens, 2020). However, selection effects could most likely only account for differences in initial levels of SPA and not for changes in workers' SPA. Since changes in SPA on the individual level are unlikely to cause short-term changes in the DL of occupations, we draw the cautious conclusion that working in occupations with higher DL leads to changes toward more positive SPA in the domains of ongoing development and self-knowledge.

Some limitations of this study have to be mentioned. First, the digitalization index used in this study contains a slightly prospective perspective because the demand for digital skills is derived from job ads and may not accurately depict the skills demanded in a person's job at the present point in time. In addition, it is determined by the level of occupations, not jobs. Therefore, this study cannot account for different demands for digital skills between different jobs within the same occupation. Another point that should be mentioned is that the statistical power of the model could be improved by considering more time points (Usami, Hayes, & McArdle, 2016). Due to data restrictions, in our analysis, we estimated change between two time points only, 2014 and 2017. Future studies using data for longer time periods or more time points could make further contributions to the investigation of the association of digitalization in occupations and workers' SPA.

Aside from the aforementioned weaknesses, three of the greatest strengths of this study should be highlighted. First, the study operates on two levels: the occupational level and the individual level. The changes in the average DL of occupations are unlikely to be impacted by changes in individuals' SPA because the DL are not derived from the participant's estimations of their work environment but by matching real-time job ads data on digital skill demands in occupations. Thus, the directionality of the associations investigated in our model is likely to be one-sided, with the occupational level impacting on the individual level. Second, our analysis of the association of

workers' SPA and digitalization in occupations is based on representative panel data, which allows us to address selectivity issues. Third, in contrast to previous studies using autoregressive cross-lagged panel models to investigate the association of SPA and digitalization in a broader sense (Köttl, Cohn-Schwartz, & Ayalon, 2021; Mariano et al., 2021a, 2021b), our study uses an LCS approach. This allows us to control for intraindividual differences in trajectories of SPA over time.

In sum, our study shows that digitalization at work is not an impending ordeal for older workers in their middle and late adulthood but may have beneficial effects on workers' attitudes toward their own aging regarding their competences and knowledge of their own character, skills, motivations, and preferences. Since positive SPA are related to multiple beneficial outcomes, for example, physical and mental health (Tully-Wilson et al., 2021), operational and political measures should support the participation and involvement of older workers in digital processes at work. Our study demonstrates that compassionate ageism at work (such as older workers should not be bothered or burdened with dealing with new technologies) is inappropriate since it is based on age stereotypes and older workers profit from working in digital occupations. Compassionate ageism toward older individuals resulting in inappropriate paternalism and a homogenization of the group of older individuals was recently observed in the public debates during the COVID-19 pandemic (Kornadt et al., 2021; Naughton, Padeiro, & Santana, 2021; Vervaecke & Meisner, 2020). This narrative must not be repeated when it comes to the topic of digitalization in the world of work and older workers. To exploit and even strengthen the potential of older workers, they must not be excluded from digital work tasks for protective reasons, but they must be involved in such work tasks without prejudice. Future studies investigating the relationship between domains of individuals' SPA and digitalization at work should take operational characteristics into account, such as the role of human resource measures that accompany digitalization processes.

7. Literature

- Acemoglu, D., & Restrepo, P. (2020). Robots and Jobs: Evidence from US Labor Markets. *Journal of Political Economy*, 128(6), 2188-2244. <https://doi.org/10.1086/705716>
- Acock, A. C. (2005). Working With Missing Values. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 67(4), 1012-1028. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3737.2005.00191.x>
- Autor, D. H., Levy, F., & Murnane, R. J. (2003). The skill content of recent technological change: An empirical exploration. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(4), 1279-1333. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003355303322552801>
- Azar, J., Marinescu, I., Steinbaum, M., & Taska, B. (2020). Concentration in US labor markets: Evidence from online vacancy data. *Labour Economics*, 66, 101886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2020.101886>
- Bal, A. C., Reiss, A. E. B., Rudolph, C. W., & Baltes, B. B. (2011). Examining Positive and Negative Perceptions of Older Workers: A Meta-Analysis. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 66B(6), 687-698. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbr056>
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action. A social cognitive theory*. Prentice Hall.
- Barak, B. (1987). Cognitive Age: A New Multidimensional Approach to Measuring Age Identity. *The International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, 25, 109-128.
- Burn, I., Button, P., Corella, L. M., & Neumark, D. (2021). Does Ageist Language in Job Ads Predict Age Discrimination in Hiring? *Journal of Labor Economics*, 40(3), 613-667. <https://doi.org/10.1086/717730>
- Cammeraat, E., & Squicciarini, M. (2021). Burning Glass Technologies' data use in policy-relevant analysis: An occupation-level assessment. (*OECD Science, Technology and Industry Working Papers No. 2021/05*). <https://doi.org/10.1787/cd75c3e7-en>
- Chen, K., & Chan, A. H. S. (2014). Gerontechnology acceptance by elderly Hong Kong Chinese: a senior technology acceptance model (STAM). *Ergonomics*, 57(5), 635-652. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2014.895855>
- Cheng, G. H.-L., & Chan, D. K.-S. (2008). Who Suffers More from Job Insecurity? A Meta-Analytic Review. *Applied Psychology*, 57(2), 272-303. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1464-0597.2007.00312.x>
- Cleveland, J. N., Hanscom, M. E., & Huebner, L.-A. M. (2017). Subjective Age and Work. In N. A. Pachana (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Geropsychology* (pp. 2301-2312). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-082-7_328

- Cohn-Schwartz, E., Schafer, M. H., & Ayalon, L. (2022). Age integration in later life social networks and self-perceptions of aging: examining their reciprocal associations. *European Journal of Ageing*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-022-00688-0>
- Colombo, E., Mercurio, F., & Mezzanzanica, M. (2019). AI meets labor market: Exploring the link between automation and skills. *Information Economics and Policy*, 47, 27-37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infoecopol.2019.05.003>
- Deming, D. J., & Noray, K. (2020). Earnings Dynamics, Changing Job Skills, and STEM Careers. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 135(4), 1965-2005. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjaa021>
- Diehl, M., Wettstein, M., Spuling, S. M., & Wurm, S. (2021). Age-related change in self-perceptions of aging: Longitudinal trajectories and predictors of change. *Psychology and Aging*, 36(3), 344-359. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pag0000585>
- Dittmann-Kohli, F., Kohli, M., Künemund, H., Model, A., Steinleitner, C., Westerhof, G. J., & infas-Sozialforschung. (1997). Lebenszusammenhänge, Selbst- und Lebenskonzeptionen - Erhebungsdesign und Instrumente des Alters. SurveyForschungsgruppe Altern und Lebenslauf (FALL) (Forschungsbericht 61). http://www.fall-berlin.de/lit/FALL_Forschungsbericht_61.pdf
- European Commission, Centre, J. R., Goenaga, X., Gonzalez Vazquez, I., Napierala, J., Arregui Pabollet, E., Cabrera Giraldez, M., Caena, F., Fernández-Macías, E., Biagi, F., Torrejon Perez, S., Punie, Y., Kamylyis, P., Gomez Gutierrez, E., Urzi Brancati, C., Milasi, S., Marschinski, R., Tolan, S., Inamorato dos Santos, A., . . . Klenert, D. (2019). *The changing nature of work and skills in the digital age*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/679150>
- Fayers, P. M., & Sprangers, M. A. G. (2002). Understanding self-rated health. *The Lancet*, 359(9302), 187-188. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(02\)07466-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(02)07466-4)
- Gendron, T. L., Inker, J., & Welleford, A. (2017). "How Old Do You Feel?" The Difficulties and Ethics of Operationalizing Subjective Age. *The Gerontologist*, 58(4), 618-624. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnx098>
- Hoonakker, P. (2014). Information and Communication Technology and Quality of Working Life: Backgrounds, Facts, and Figures. In C. Korunka & P. Hoonakker (Eds.), *The Impact of ICT on Quality of Working Life* (pp. 9-24). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8854-0>
- Jung, S., Cham, H., Siedlecki, K. L., & Jopp, D. S. (2021). Measurement Invariance and Developmental Trajectories of Multidimensional Self-Perceptions of Aging in Middle-Aged

- and Older Adults. *The journals of gerontology. Series B, Psychological sciences and social sciences*, 76(3), 483-495. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbz099>
- Kastenbaum, R., Derbin, V., Sabatini, P., & Artt, S. (1972). "The Ages of Me": Toward Personal and Interpersonal Definitions of Functional Aging. *Aging and Human Development*, 3(2), 197-211. <https://doi.org/10.2190/TUJR-WTXK-866Q-8QU7>
- Klaus, D., Engstler, H., Mahne, K., Wolff, J. K., Simonson, J., Wurm, S., & Tesch-Römer, C. (2017). Cohort Profile: The German Ageing Survey (DEAS). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 46(4), 1105-1105g. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw326>
- Kornadt, A. E., Albert, I., Hoffmann, M., Murdock, E., & Nell, J. (2021). Perceived Ageism During the Covid-19-Crisis Is Longitudinally Related to Subjective Perceptions of Aging. *Front Public Health*, 9, 679711. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.679711>
- Kornadt, A. E., & Rothermund, K. (2015). Views on Aging: Domain-Specific Approaches and Implications for Developmental Regulation. *Annual Review of Gerontology & Geriatrics*, 35(1), 121-144. <https://doi.org/10.1891/0198-8794.35.121>
- Kornadt, A. E., Voss, P., & Rothermund, K. (2015). Age Stereotypes and Self-Views Revisited: Patterns of Internalization and Projection Processes Across the Life Span. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 72(4), 582-592. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbv099>
- Köttl, H., Cohn-Schwartz, E., & Ayalon, L. (2021). Self-Perceptions of Aging and Everyday ICT Engagement: A Test of Reciprocal Associations. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 76(9), 1913-1922. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbaa168>
- Kubicek, B., Paškvan, M., & Korunka, C. (2015). Development and validation of an instrument for assessing job demands arising from accelerated change: The intensification of job demands scale (IDS). *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 24(6), 898-913. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432x.2014.979160>
- Kunze, F., Boehm, S. A., & Bruch, H. (2011). Age diversity, age discrimination climate and performance consequences-a cross organizational study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 32(2), 264-290. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.698>
- Lawton, M. P. (1975). The Philadelphia Geriatric Center Morale Scale: A Revision. *Journal of Gerontology*, 30(1), 85-89. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronj/30.1.85>
- Levy, B. (2009). Stereotype Embodiment: A Psychosocial Approach to Aging. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 18(6), 332-336. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2009.01662.x>
- Levy, B. R., Slade, M. D., Pietrzak, R. H., & Ferrucci, L. (2018). Positive age beliefs protect against dementia even among elders with high-risk gene. *PLOS ONE*, 13(2), e0191004. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0191004>

- Liang, J., & Bollen, K. A. (1983). The Structure of the Philadelphia Geriatric Center Morale Scale: A Reinterpretation. *Journal of Gerontology*, 38(2), 181-189.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/geronj/38.2.181>
- Mariano, J., Marques, S., Ramos, M. R., & de Vries, H. (2021a). Cognitive functioning mediates the relationship between self-perceptions of aging and computer use behavior in late adulthood: Evidence from two longitudinal studies. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 121, 106807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106807>
- Mariano, J., Marques, S., Ramos, M. R., & de Vries, H. (2021b). Internet use by middle-aged and older adults: Longitudinal relationships with functional ability, social support, and self-perceptions of aging. *Psychology and Aging*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pag0000643>
- Marsh, H. W. (2007). Application of Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Structural Equation Modeling in Sport and Exercise Psychology. In G. Tenenbaum & R. C. Eklund (Eds.), *Handbook of Sport Psychology* (Vol. 3, pp. 774-798). Wiley & Sons.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118270011.ch35>
- McArdle, J. J. (2009). Latent variable modeling of differences and changes with longitudinal data. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 60(1), 577-605.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.60.110707.163612>
- Mezzanzanica, M., & Mercurio, F. (2019). Big Data for labour market intelligence: an introductory guide. <https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2019-06/Big%20data%20for%20LMI.pdf>
- Muthén, L. K., & Muthén, B. O. (2017). *Mplus User's Guide* (8 ed.). CA: Muthén & Muthén.
- Naughton, L., Padeiro, M., & Santana, P. (2021). The twin faces of ageism, glorification and abjection: A content analysis of age advocacy in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Aging Studies*, 57, 100938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaging.2021.100938>
- North, M. S., & Fiske, S. T. (2016). Resource Scarcity and Prescriptive Attitudes Generate Subtle, Intergenerational Older-Worker Exclusion. *Journal of Social Issues*, 72(1), 122-145. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12159>
- O'Kane, L., Narasimhan, R., Nania, J., & Taska, B. (2020). *Digitalization in the German Labor Market: Analyzing Demand for Digital Skills in Job Vacancies* (TD/TNC 142.690). Bertelsmann Stiftung. <http://aei.pitt.edu/id/eprint/103213>
- O'Brien, E. L., Torres, G. E., & Neupert, S. D. (2020). Cognitive Interference in the Context of Daily Stressors, Daily Awareness of Age-Related Change, and General Aging Attitudes. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 76(5), 920-929.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbaa155>

- Paggi, M. E., & Jopp, D. S. (2015). Outcomes of Occupational Self-Efficacy in Older Workers. *The International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, 80(4), 357-378. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091415015607640>
- Petery, G. A., Wee, S., Dunlop, P. D., & Parker, S. K. (2020). Older workers and poor performance: Examining the association of age stereotypes with expected work performance quality. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 28(4), 510-521. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijisa.12309>
- Pettigrew, T. F. (1998). Intergroup contact theory. *Annual review of psychology*, 49(1), 65-85. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.49.1.65>
- Posthuma, R. A., & Campion, M. A. (2009). Age Stereotypes in the Workplace: Common Stereotypes, Moderators, and Future Research Directions. *Journal of Management*, 35(1), 158-188. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206308318617>
- Rudolph, C. W., Kunze, F., & Zacher, H. (2019). Getting Objective About Subjective Age: Introduction to a Special Issue. *Work, Aging and Retirement*, 5(4), 265-272. <https://doi.org/10.1093/workar/waz019>
- Sargent-Cox, K. A., Anstey, K. J., & Luszcz, M. A. (2012). The relationship between change in self-perceptions of aging and physical functioning in older adults. *Psychol Aging*, 27(3), 750-760. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0027578>
- Schwartz, E., Ayalon, L., & Huxhold, O. (2020). Exploring the Reciprocal Associations of Perceptions of Aging and Social Involvement. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 76(3), 563-573. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/qbaa008>
- Siebert, J. S., Wahl, H.-W., & Schröder, J. (2016). The Role of Attitude Toward Own Aging for Fluid and Crystallized Functioning: 12-Year Evidence From the ILSE Study. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 73(5), 836-845. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbw050>
- Spitz-Oener, A. (2006). Technical Change, Job Tasks, and Rising Educational Demands: Looking outside the Wage Structure. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 24(2), 235-270. <https://doi.org/10.1086/499972>
- Spuling, S. M., Klusmann, V., Bowen, C. E., Kornadt, A. E., & Kessler, E.-M. (2020). The uniqueness of subjective ageing: convergent and discriminant validity. *European Journal of Ageing*, 17(4), 445-455. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-019-00529-7>
- Stephan, Y. (2021). Subjective Age. In D. Gu & M. E. Dupre (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Gerontology and Population Aging* (pp. 4792-4797). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-22009-9_114

- Steverink, N., Westerhof, G. J., Bode, C., & Dittmann-Kohli, F. (2001). The Personal Experience of Aging, Individual Resources, and Subjective Well-Being. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 56(6), 364-373. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/56.6.P364>
- Tully-Wilson, C., Bojack, R., Milleer, P. M., Stallman, H. M., Allen, A., & Mason, J. (2021). Self-perceptions of aging: A systematic review of longitudinal studies. *Psychology and Aging*, 36(7), 773-789. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pag0000638>
- Turek, K., & Henkens, K. (2020). How Job Requirements Affect the Recruitment Likelihood of Older Workers. The Indirect Role of Age Stereotypes. *Work, Employment & Society*, 34(4), 550–570. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017019847943>
- Usami, S., Hayes, T., & McArdle, J. J. (2016). Inferring Longitudinal Relationships Between Variables: Model Selection Between the Latent Change Score and Autoregressive Cross-Lagged Factor Models. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 23(3), 331-342. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705511.2015.1066680>
- Vervaecke, D., & Meisner, B. A. (2020). Caremongering and Assumptions of Need: The Spread of Compassionate Ageism During COVID-19. *The Gerontologist*, 61(2), 159-165. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnaa131>
- Weber, J., Angerer, P., & Müller, A. (2019). Individual consequences of age stereotypes on older workers: A systematic review. *Zeitschrift für Gerontologie und Geriatrie*, 52(S3), 188-205. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00391-019-01506-6>
- Wegman, L. A., Hoffman, B. J., Carter, N. T., Twenge, J. M., & Guenole, N. (2018). Placing Job Characteristics in Context: Cross-Temporal Meta-Analysis of Changes in Job Characteristics Since 1975. *Journal of Management*, 44(1), 352-386. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206316654545>
- Westerhof, G. J., Miche, M., Brothers, A. F., Barrett, A. E., Diehl, M., Montepare, J. M., Wahl, H.-W., & Wurm, S. (2014). The Influence of Subjective Aging on Health and Longevity: A Meta-Analysis of Longitudinal Data. *Psychology and aging*, 29(4), 793-802. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038016>
- Wurm, S., Diehl, M., Kornadt, A. E., Westerhof, G. J., & Wahl, H.-W. (2017). How do views on aging affect health outcomes in adulthood and late life? Explanations for an established connection. *Developmental Review*, 46, 27-43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2017.08.002>

7.2. Supplemental Material of the Papers

I. Supplemental Material – Paper 1

Digitalisation, Gender, and Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany

Lisa Katharina Kortmann, Stefan Stuth und Julia Simonson

1.	Extensive Variable Description.....	165
2.	Extensive Results.....	167
3.	Regression Diagnostics.....	168
4.	Additional Analyses.....	172
5.	Illustrative Material.....	174
6.	Literature.....	174

Tables and Figures

Table 4:	Variable Description.....	165
Table 5:	Participation in Training of Employees in Their Second Half of Working Life in Germany.....	167
Table 6:	Desire to Participate in Training of Employees in Their Second Half of Working Life in Germany.....	168
Table 7:	Correlation Matrix for Independent Variables.....	169
Table 8:	Correlation Matrix for Training and Gender.....	170
Table 9:	Cross Tabulation Training Participation and Desire to Participate in Training Separated for Gender.....	171
Table 10:	Participation in Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life Controlled for Their Desire for Training Participation.....	172
Table 11:	Participation in Training – Robustness Checks.....	173
Table 12:	Desire to Participate in Training – Robustness Checks.....	174
Table 13:	Occupations with highest/lowest (Change in the) DL.....	175
Figure 5:	Receiver-Operator-Characteristic (ROC) Curves.....	169
Figure 6:	Frequency Distribution of Male and Female Employees across Occupations' (Change in the) Digitalization Level.....	175

1. Extensive Variable Description

The plausibility of each value of variables considered in the analyses was tested. Extremely high working hours, that deviated three standard deviations from the mean (>75 hours) were truncated and recoded to missing. If the number of years of employees' career interruption was assessed as not plausible in view of employee's age and years employed, related values were recoded to missing. Furthermore, values were recoded to missing if the stated age at that employees plan to stop working exceeds 100 years. For employees that stated to be undecided about their planned age at that they stop working the mean value was used to avoid missing values. A detailed description of all variables considered in the analyses can be found in table 4.

Table 4: Variable Description.

Variable	Question in DEAS 2017 / Conceptualisation of Variable in Other Data Source
participation in training	"There are courses and advanced occupational training programs available for many occupations. Think back over the past 3 years. Did you attend any training, courses, seminars or events ofigned to provide occupational training or vocational retraining?"
desire to participate in training in future	"Would you like to take part in an advanced occupational training course or program in the near future?"
digitalisation level	Source: (O'Kane et al., 2020). The digitalisation level was built by calculating the average recall for each skill in each occupation by dividing the number of job postings for occupation _x asking for skill _y by the total number of job postings for occupation _x . Then, each determined average recall was multiplied by the related weight of the skill type and the weighted recalls for every skill by occupation were summed up. Then, for each occupation-specific skill demand value the logarithm was taken, and the values were normalized to range between 0 and 100.
change in digitalisation level	Source: (O'Kane et al., 2020) The change in the digitalisation level was determined by calculating the difference in the digitalisation level between 2014 and 2018, scaling the digitalisation level 2014 in terms of the digitalisation level 2018 for accurate comparison.
gender	Sex of respondent assessed by interviewer.
age	"Many questions are guided by the year of birth. I sincerely ask you to give me your date of birth so that I can ask you only those questions that apply to your age." The age was generated in DEAS 2017 by subtracting the respondents' date of birth from the date of the survey interview.
residency	Residency was generated in DEAS 2017 based on respondents' current residential address. "East Germany" includes the territory of the German Democratic Republic including East Berlin. "West Germany" includes the territory of the Federal Republic of Germany including West Berlin.
high education	Level of education referring to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), 3-level. The variable was generated in DEAS 2017 based on information on kind and place of respondents' education. No 0: ISCED0–4

	Yes 1: ISCED 5–6
gender composition of occupations	Source:(Stuth, 2022), based on the German Microcensus 2015
responsible for major part of housework	<p>“Now I would like to ask which one of you does the housework. Who is mainly responsible for tasks like cooking meals, washing dishes, doing laundry, cleaning, and buying groceries?”</p> <p>Categorical scale: 1: Mainly me; 2: Both my partner and I, equally often; 3: Mainly my partner; 4: Mainly another person in the household; 5: Mainly another person who does not live in the household; 6: Does not apply, nursing home</p> <p>No 0: 2–6 Yes 1: 1 & living alone</p>
young children in same household	<p>“Do you have children? By this I mean kind of your own, children who have grown up or are growing up in your household, as well as any children who may no longer be alive. [If children existing:] And how many children do you have?”</p> <p>“What year was [child x] born?”</p> <p>“Does [child x] live in your house or household?”</p> <p>No 0: No child younger than 13 years living in same household Yes 1: >=1 child younger than 13 years in same household</p>
working time	“How many hours a week do you currently work at your job, including overtime?”
small enterprise	<p>“Approximately how many other people work for the company you work for, including owners and trainees?”</p> <p>Ordinal scale: 1: fewer than 5 employees; 2: 5 and more, but less than 20 employees; 3: 20 and more, but less than 100 employees; 4: 100 and more, but less than 200 employees; 5: 200 and more, but less than 2,000 employees; 6: 2,000 employees and more</p> <p>No 0: 3–6 Yes 1: 1–2</p>
public service	“If you think about your current job: What sector is the company in where you work? Is it [...] part of the public service?”
years till planned end of work	<p>“At what age do you plan to stop working?”</p> <p>Planned age when stop working is subtracted by age. To avoid correlation with age, the residuals from years till planned end of working regressed on age are determined. Information for respondents with the answer “Don’t know yet” was replaced by the mean value.</p>
career interruption	<p>“Since the start of your working life, have you ever had an extended interruption in employment, either once or more than once, for a period longer than six months? What is meant here are only extended breaks between two jobs.”</p> <p>“How many years in total has your working life been interrupted?”. [Rounded to full years.]</p>
professional change	“Have you made any professional changes since [date of respondents last survey]? For example, have you started a new job or changed careers or taken on new tasks or responsibilities at work?”.

2. Extensive Results

Table 5: Participation in Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	0.134 (0.122)	0.154 (0.124)	0.148 (0.120)
Gender (ref.: male)	0.109 (0.205)	0.111 (0.206)	1.012 (0.455)
Female		-0.039 (0.213)	0.003 (0.195)
Gender # Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}			0.270 (0.130)
Change in Digitalisation Level ^b			-0.418 (0.175)
Gender # Change in Digitalisation Level ^b			-0.120 (0.076)
Age ^{a,b}	-0.112 (0.077)	-0.112 (0.077)	-0.120 (0.076)
Residency ^a (ref.: West GER)	-0.376 (0.164)	-0.376 (0.164)	-0.408 (0.166)
East GER			0.602 (0.167)
Educational Level ^a (ref.: not high)	0.605 (0.173)	0.601 (0.170)	0.602 (0.167)
High			
Gender Composition of Occupations (ref.: mixed)			
Female Dominated	0.350 (0.316)	0.344 (0.328)	0.396 (0.319)
Male Dominated	-0.015 (0.210)	-0.013 (0.208)	0.067 (0.214)
Housework ^{a,c}	-0.147 (0.142)	-0.145 (0.143)	-0.148 (0.145)
Young Child in Same HH ^{a,c}	-0.130 (0.192)	-0.135 (0.188)	-0.139 (0.192)
Working Hours (per week) ^{a,b}	0.486 (0.107)	0.487 (0.108)	0.500 (0.106)
Public Service ^a	0.811 (0.196)	0.810 (0.193)	0.791 (0.199)
Small Enterprise ^a (<20 employees)	-0.067 (0.201)	-0.069 (0.195)	-0.066 (0.191)
Years till Planned End of Working ^{a,b,d}	0.053 (0.074)	0.053 (0.074)	0.046 (0.073)
Career Interruption (in years) ^{a,b,c}	0.042 (0.073)	0.041 (0.073)	0.048 (0.074)
Professional Change ^a	0.008 (0.169)	0.007 (0.168)	-0.005 (0.169)
Constant	0.528 (0.183)	0.525 (0.178)	-0.065 (0.357)
n	1,020	1,020	1,020
Prob. > χ^2	0.000	0.000	0.000
R ² _{Adj. McFadden}	0.078	0.078	0.085
AIC	1,274.595	1,276.512	1,271.043

Note: b = partial logistic regression coefficients (log odds). SE = clustered standard errors (by occupation). Bold: significant at 95% level.

^a centred at the mean; ^b standardized; ^c information for variable from DEAS 2014, ^d planned years controlled for age (residuals).

Source: DEAS 2017.

Table 6: Desire to Participate in Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	0.151 (0.089)	0.127 (0.107)	0.126 (0.110)
Gender (ref.: male)	-0.171 (0.206)	-0.172 (0.207)	0.347 (0.367)
Female		0.048 (0.170)	-0.006 (0.178)
Gender # Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}			0.383 (0.115)
Change in Digitalisation Level ^b			-0.225 (0.138)
Gender # Change in Digitalisation Level ^b			
Age ^{a,b}	-0.622 (0.096)	-0.622 (0.096)	-0.627 (0.098)
Residency ^a (ref.: West GER)	-0.223 (0.135)	-0.224 (0.135)	-0.260 (0.137)
East GER			
Educational Level ^a (ref.: not high)	0.716 (0.149)	0.721 (0.150)	0.732 (0.147)
High			
Gender Composition of Occupations (ref.: mixed)			
Female Dominated	0.307 (0.232)	0.315 (0.245)	0.309 (0.251)
Male Dominated	0.061 (0.198)	0.058 (0.197)	0.311 (0.221)
Housework ^a	-0.143 (0.194)	-0.146 (0.194)	-0.152 (0.199)
Young Child in Same HH ^a	0.017 (0.300)	0.021 (0.299)	0.009 (0.302)
Working Hours (per week) ^{a,b}	0.145 (0.108)	0.143 (0.108)	0.149 (0.106)
Public Service ^a	0.601 (0.183)	0.603 (0.183)	0.563 (0.193)
Small Enterprise ^a (<20 employees)	0.146 (0.181)	0.150 (0.181)	0.172 (0.186)
Years till Planned End of Working ^{a,b,d}	0.026 (0.074)	0.025 (0.074)	0.029 (0.073)
Career Interruption (in years) ^{a,b}	-0.077 (0.077)	-0.077 (0.078)	-0.075 (0.077)
Professional Change ^a	0.531 (0.176)	0.532 (0.176)	0.524 (0.176)
Constant	0.836 (0.178)	0.838 (0.177)	-0.063 (0.315)
n	1,018	1,018	1,018
Prob. > χ^2	0.000	0.000	0.000
R ² _{Adj. McFadden}	0.103	0.103	0.113
AIC	1,217.473	1,219.360	1,209.529

Note: b = partial logistic regression coefficients (log odds). SE = clustered standard errors (by occupation). Bold: significant at 95% level.

^a centred at the mean; ^b standardized; ^d planned years controlled for age (residuals).

Source: DEAS 2017.

3. Regression Diagnostics

Regression diagnostics were conducted for model 3. The regressions have been checked for influential cases by using Pregibon's $dbeta$ (Pregibon, 1981). One influential case with a predicted $dbeta$ greater than 0.3 was identified and excluded from the analyses regarding training participation. Regarding the desire for training participation no outlier was identified. In addition, the Hosmer and Lemeshow's goodness-of-fit-test using ten quantiles was conducted (Hosmer & Lemeshow, 1980; Hosmer, Lemeshow, & Sturdivant, 2013). The test indicated that both models – for the training participation and the desire for training participation – were good specified. To display the overall performance of the model for the predicted probabilities the Receiver-Operating-Characteristic (ROC) was calculated (see. Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Receiver-Operator-Characteristic (ROC) Curves.

Source: DEAS 2017.

In order to check if the considered control variables are correlated to each other, a correlation matrix was generated (see tab. 7). To check for multicollinearity, the variance inflation factors (VIF) have been determined. No serve correlations were identified, neither for the analysis of the participation in training nor the desire to take part in training.

Table 7: Correlation Matrix for Independent Variables.

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1 Digitalisation Level	1.000														
2 Change in Digitalisation Level	0.117	1.000													
3 Gender	-0.118	0.126	1.000												
4 Age	-0.055	-0.008	0.032	1.000											
5 Residency	-0.052	0.004	0.079	0.032	1.000										
6 High Education	0.274	0.061	-0.106	0.040	0.051	1.000									
7 Housework	-0.144	0.049	0.568	-0.005	0.021	-0.138	1.000								
8 Young Child in Same HH	0.156	0.032	-0.179	-0.461	-0.076	0.104	-0.164	1.000							
9 Gender Compos. of Occ.	0.209	-0.299	-0.487	-0.055	0.055	0.019	-0.295	0.091	1.000						
10 Working Time	0.219	-0.046	-0.455	-0.057	0.095	0.192	-0.360	0.047	0.330	1.000					
11 Public Service	-0.013	0.153	0.127	0.140	-0.020	0.183	0.044	-0.012	-0.187	-0.053	1.000				
12 Small Enterprise	-0.189	-0.049	0.153	0.033	0.040	-0.112	0.149	-0.052	-0.126	-0.240	-0.144	1.000			
13 Years till End of Work	0.044	-0.021	-0.093	-0.031	0.021	0.100	-0.027	0.040	0.063	0.087	0.057	-0.003	1.000		
14 Career Interruption	-0.078	0.037	0.322	0.048	-0.028	-0.110	0.216	-0.054	-0.239	-0.310	0.025	0.148	0.002	1.000	
15 Professional Change	-0.003	0.016	0.052	-0.083	-0.046	0.024	0.076	-0.019	-0.090	-0.041	-0.032	0.041	0.029	0.021	1.000

Source: DEAS 2017.

Table 8: Correlation Matrix for Training and Gender.

Variable	1	2	3
1 Training Participation	1.000		
2 Desire to Participate in Training	0.299	1.000	
3 Gender	-0.054	-0.078	1.000

Source: DEAS 2017.

Table 9: Cross Tabulation Training Participation and Desire to Participate in Training Separated for Gender.

Male			
Training Participation	Desire to Participate in Training		total
	no	yes	
no	77	88	165
	46.67	53.33	100.00
	51.33	26.75	34.45
yes	73	241	314
	23.25	76.75	100.00
	48.67	73.25	65.55
total	150	329	479
	31.32	68.68	100.00
	100	100	100
Female			
Training Participation	Desire to Participate in Training		total
	no	yes	
no	127	87	214
	59.35	40.65	100.00
	60.77	26.36	39.70
yes	82	243	325
	25.23	74.77	100.00
	39.23	73.64	60.30
total	209	330	539
	38.78	61.22	100.00
	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: DEAS 2017.

4. Additional Analyses

Table 10: Participation in Training of Employees in the Second Half of Working Life Controlled for Their Desire for Training Participation.

	Model 3	Model 3 + Desire for Training
Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	0.148 (0.120)	0.116 (0.126)
Gender (ref.: male)	1.012	0.914
Female	(0.455)	(0.428)
Gender # Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	0.003 (0.195)	0.022 (0.190)
Change in Digitalisation Level ^b	0.270 (0.130)	0.243 (0.120)
Gender # Change in Digitalisation Level ^b	-0.418 (0.175)	-0.357 (0.163)
Age ^{a,b}	-0.120 (0.076)	-0.047 (0.079)
Residency ^a (ref.: West GER)	-0.408	-0.423
East GER	(0.166)	(0.176)
Educational Level ^a (ref.: not high)	0.602	0.436
High	(0.167)	(0.171)
Gender Composition of Occupations (ref.: mixed)		
Female Dominated	0.396 (0.319)	0.377 (0.308)
Male Dominated	0.067 (0.214)	0.079 (0.213)
Housework ^{a,c}	-0.148 (0.145)	-0.142 (0.150)
Young Child in Same HH ^{a,c}	-0.139 (0.192)	-0.113 (0.201)
Working Hours (per week) ^{a,b}	0.500 (0.106)	0.463 (0.109)
Public Service ^a	0.791 (0.199)	0.751 (0.196)
Small Enterprise ^a (<20 employees)	-0.066 (0.191)	-0.101 (0.191)
Years till Planned End of Working ^{a,b,d}	0.046 (0.073)	0.006 (0.077)
Career Interruption (in years) ^{a,b,c}	0.048 (0.074)	0.029 (0.076)
Professional Change ^a	-0.005 (0.169)	-0.075 (0.176)
Desire to Participate in Training ^{a,c}		1.028 (0.171)
Constant	-0.065 (0.357)	-0.027 (0.331)
n	1,020	1,010
Prob. > χ^2	0.000	0.000
R ² _{Adj. McFadden}	0.085	0.115
AIC	1,271.043	1,217.734

Note: b = partial logistic regression coefficients (log odds). SE = clustered standard errors (by occupation). Bold: significant at 95% level.

^a centred at the mean; ^b standardized; ^c information for variable from DEAS 2014, ^d planned years controlled for age (residuals).

Source: DEAS 2017.

Table 11: Participation in Training – Robustness Checks.

	Model 3	Model 3 Subsample 50 to 65 Years	Model 3 Random Sample (80%)	Model 3 Exclusion Highest 5 DL	Model 3 Exclusion Highest 5 CDL
Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	0.148 (0.120)	0.311 (0.116)	0.205 (0.147)	0.207 (0.125)	0.126 (0.122)
Gender (ref.: male)	1.012 (0.455)	0.739 (0.491)	0.930 (0.528)	0.982* (0.460)	0.821 (0.465)
Female					
Gender # Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	0.003 (0.195)	-0.213 (0.195)	-0.052 (0.223)	-0.037 (0.201)	0.018 (0.206)
Change in Digitalisation Level ^b	0.270 (0.130)	0.225 (0.131)	0.229 (0.158)	0.259 (0.132)	0.304 (0.136)
Gender # Change in Digitalisation Level ^b	-0.418 (0.175)	-0.323 (0.185)	-0.388 (0.209)	-0.413 (0.177)	-0.331 (0.177)
Age ^{a,b}	-0.120 (0.076)	-0.004 (0.119)	-0.179 (0.094)	-0.139 (0.077)	-0.131 (0.077)
Residency ^a (ref.: West GER)	-0.408 (0.166)	-0.419 (0.191)	-0.305 (0.171)	-0.381 (0.167)	-0.359 (0.173)
East GER					
Educational Level ^a (ref.: not high)	0.602 (0.167)	0.605 (0.189)	0.582 (0.188)	0.614 (0.168)	0.636 (0.168)
High					
Gender Composition of Occupations (ref.: mixed)					
Female Dominated	0.396 (0.319)	0.354 (0.320)	0.474 (0.336)	0.404 (0.322)	0.421 (0.360)
Male Dominated	0.067 (0.214)	-0.045 (0.221)	-0.012 (0.246)	0.064 (0.217)	0.097 (0.222)
Housework ^{a,c}	-0.148 (0.145)	0.044 (0.169)	-0.093 (0.162)	-0.172 (0.146)	-0.146 (0.148)
Young Child in Same HH ^{a,c}	-0.139 (0.192)	0.007 (0.322)	-0.232 (0.214)	-0.161 (0.195)	-0.134 (0.198)
Working Hours (per week) ^{a,b}	0.500 (0.106)	0.532 (0.115)	0.536 (0.117)	0.476 (0.106)	0.474 (0.106)
Public Service ^a	0.791 (0.199)	0.757 (0.211)	0.841 (0.237)	0.809 (0.199)	0.753 (0.204)
Small Enterprise ^a (<20 employees)	-0.066 (0.191)	-0.070 (0.198)	-0.078 (0.217)	-0.072 (0.192)	-0.064 (0.198)
Years till Planned End of Working ^{a,b,d}	0.046 (0.073)	0.128 (0.101)	0.047 (0.087)	0.050 (0.074)	0.049 (0.074)
Career Interruption (in years) ^{a,b,c}	0.048 (0.074)	0.067 (0.077)	0.033 (0.079)	0.040 (0.074)	0.057 (0.075)
Professional Change ^a	-0.005 (0.169)	0.070 (0.196)	-0.120 (0.196)	-0.010 (0.171)	0.003 (0.175)
Constant	-0.065 (0.357)	0.035 (0.372)	0.052 (0.429)	-0.015 (0.362)	-0.124 (0.372)
n	1,020	811	816	1,009	987
Prob. > χ^2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
R ² _{Adj.} McFadden	0.085	0.093	0.088	0.088	0.083
AIC	1,271.043	1,017.171	1,017.607	1,253.342	1,228.876

Note: b = partial logistic regression coefficients (log odds). SE = clustered standard errors (by occupation). Bold: significant at 95% level. Bold and italic: significant at 90% level.

^a centred at the mean; ^b standardized; ^c information for variable from DEAS 2014, ^d planned years controlled for age (residuals). Source: DEAS 2017.

Table 12: Desire to Participate in Training – Robustness Checks.

	Model 3	Model 3 Subsample 50 to 65 Years	Model 3 Random Subsample (80%)	Model 3 Exclusion Highest DL	Model 3 Exclusion Highest CDL
Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	0.126 (0.110)	0.209 (0.110)	0.144 (0.125)	0.152 (0.111)	0.117 (0.112)
Gender (ref.: male)	0.347 (0.367)	0.260 (0.423)	0.357 (0.414)	0.297 (0.370)	0.321 (0.395)
Female					
Gender # Digitalisation Level ^{a,b}	-0.006 (0.178)	-0.034 (0.196)	-0.070 (0.194)	-0.039 (0.180)	-0.035 (0.181)
Change in Digitalisation Level ^b	0.383 (0.115)	0.431 (0.116)	0.386 (0.123)	0.374 (0.115)	0.407 (0.126)
Gender # Change in Digitalisation Level ^b	-0.225 (0.138)	-0.284 (0.152)	-0.154 (0.147)	-0.216 (0.139)	-0.196 (0.158)
Age ^{a,b}	-0.627 (0.098)	-0.756 (0.124)	-0.573 (0.107)	-0.630 (0.098)	-0.634 (0.100)
Residency ^a (ref.: West GER)	-0.260 (0.137)	-0.244 (0.162)	-0.264 (0.159)	-0.237 (0.137)	-0.264 (0.140)
East GER					
Educational Level ^a (ref.: not high)	0.732 (0.147)	0.804 (0.164)	0.671 (0.179)	0.725 (0.147)	0.730 (0.151)
High					
Gender Composition of Occupations (ref.: mixed)					
Female Dominated	0.309 (0.251)	0.285 (0.277)	0.369 (0.273)	0.308 (0.250)	0.300 (0.270)
Male Dominated	0.311 (0.221)	0.160 (0.226)	0.497 (0.253)	0.291 (0.221)	0.334 (0.232)
Housework ^a	-0.152 (0.199)	0.046 (0.221)	-0.266 (0.209)	-0.144 (0.200)	-0.179 (0.201)
Young Child in Same HH ^a	0.009 (0.302)	-0.010 (0.464)	0.172 (0.282)	0.049 (0.308)	0.108 (0.320)
Working Hours (per week) ^{a,b}	0.149 (0.106)	0.170 (0.114)	0.114 (0.117)	0.144 (0.106)	0.148 (0.108)
Public Service ^a	0.563 (0.193)	0.511 (0.212)	0.547 (0.202)	0.587 (0.192)	0.559 (0.198)
Small Enterprise ^a (<20 employees)	0.172 (0.186)	0.151 (0.197)	0.126 (0.211)	0.172 (0.186)	0.144 (0.190)
Years till Planned End of Working ^{a,b,d}	0.029 (0.073)	0.005 (0.092)	0.023 (0.097)	0.035 (0.074)	0.031 (0.075)
Career Interruption (in years) ^{a,b}	-0.075 (0.077)	-0.085 (0.078)	-0.186 (0.071)	-0.075 (0.077)	-0.085 (0.080)
Professional Change ^a	0.524 (0.176)	0.447 (0.198)	0.577 (0.197)	0.517 (0.177)	0.550 (0.182)
Constant	-0.063 (0.315)	0.105 (0.324)	-0.302 (0.336)	-0.015 (0.318)	-0.123 (0.335)
n	1,018	808	812	1,007	985
Prob. > χ^2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
R ² _{Adj. McFadden}	0.113	0.118	0.116	0.114	0.117
AIC	1,209.529	989.626	977.475	1,198.670	1,167.172

Note: b = partial logistic regression coefficients (log odds). SE = clustered standard errors (by occupation). Bold: significant at 95% level. Bold and italic: significant at 90% level.

^a centred at the mean; ^b standardized; ^d planned years controlled for age (residuals). Source: DEAS 2017.

5. Illustrative Material

Table 13: Occupations with Highest/Lowest (Change in the) DL.

Highest DL	Highest CDL
Web and Multimedia Developers	Cartographers and Surveyors
Database Designers and Administrators	Restaurant Manager
Systems Administrators	Companions and Valets
Lowest DL	Lowest CDL
Cleaners and Helpers in Offices, Hotels and Other Establishments	Woodworking-Machine Tool Setters and Operators
Bricklayers and Related Workers	Wood Processing Plant Operators
Heavy Truck and Lorry Drivers	Toolmakers and Related Workers

Source: DEAS 2017, n= 2,010.

Figure 6: Frequency Distribution of Male and Female Employees across Occupations' (Change in the) Digitalization Level.

Source: DEAS 2017, n= 2,010.

6. Literature

- Hosmer, D. W., & Lemeshow, S. (1980). Goodness of fit tests for the multiple logistic regression model. *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 9(10), 1043-1069. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610928008827941>
- Hosmer, D. W., Lemeshow, S., & Sturdivant, R. X. (2013). *Applied logistic regression, third edition* (3rd ed.). John Wiley and Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118548387>
- O'Kane, L., Narasimhan, R., Nania, J., & Taska, B. (2020). *Digitalization in the German Labor Market: Analyzing Demand for Digital Skills in Job Vacancies* (TD/TNC 142.690). Bertelsmann Stiftung. <http://aei.pitt.edu/id/eprint/103213>
- Pregibon, D. (1981). Logistic Regression Diagnostics. *The Annals of Statistics*, 9(4), 705-724. <https://doi.org/10.1214/aos/11176345513>

Stuth, S. (2022). *Occupational Environments - An Activity-Based Approach Based on Holland Version 1.0.0* [Data Set]. WZB - Wissenschaftszentrum Berlin für Sozialforschung. <https://doi.org/10.7802/2502>

II. Supplemental Material – Paper 2

Digitalisation and Employees' Subjective Job Quality in the Second Half of Working Life in Germany

Lisa Katharina Kortmann, Julia Simonson, Claudia Vogel, Oliver Huxhold

1.	Sample Description.....	178
	<i>Tab. 1: Distribution of Selected Characteristics of the DEAS baseline sample 2014...</i>	<i>178</i>
	<i>Tab. 2: Characteristics of Employees in Most/Least Digitalised Occupations.....</i>	<i>178</i>
	<i>Tab. 3: Comparison of Distributions among Different Levels of Self-Rated Health.....</i>	<i>179</i>
2.	Analyses.....	180
	a) Pure Model	
	<i>Tab. 4: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction.....</i>	<i>180</i>
	<i>Tab. 5: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress.....</i>	<i>180</i>
	b) Composition Model	
	<i>Tab. 6: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction Controlled for Compositional Effects.....</i>	<i>181</i>
	<i>Tab. 7: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress Controlled for Compositional Effects.....</i>	<i>182</i>
	c) Job Insecurity Model	
	<i>Tab. 8: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction Controlled for Job Insecurity.....</i>	<i>183</i>
	<i>Tab. 9: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress Controlled for Job Insecurity.....</i>	<i>184</i>
3.	Additional Analyses.....	185
	<i>Tab. 10: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction with Clustered Standard Errors for Occupations.....</i>	<i>185</i>
	<i>Tab. 11: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress with Clustered Standard Errors for Occupations.....</i>	<i>186</i>
	<i>Tab. 12: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction without Controlling for Self-Rated Health.</i>	<i>187</i>
	<i>Tab. 13: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress without Controlling for Self-Rated Health.</i>	<i>189</i>
4.	Hypotheses.....	190
	<i>Tab. 14: Overview of all Formulated Hypotheses and Related Results.....</i>	<i>190</i>

1. Sample Description

Table 1: Distribution of Selected Characteristics of the DEAS Baseline Sample 2014.

gender %		company size %	
female	49	less than 5	6
male	51	5 to 20 employees	19
education (ISCED) %		21 to 100 employees	24
low	3	101 to 200 employees	12
middle	53	201 to 2000 employees	23
high	44	2000 and more	16
region %		sector %	
East Germany	32	agriculture & forestry	1
West Germany	68	industry	22
age Ø		handicraft	9
Mean	52	commercial or service	44
SD	6.15	public service	24

Source: DEAS 2014; employees subject to social insurance contributions; N = 1541.

Table 2: Characteristics of Employees in Most/Least Digitalised Occupations.

most digitalised occupations (>=70%)		least digitalised occupations (<30%)	
gender %		gender %	
female	30	female	50
male	70	male	49
education (ISCED) %		education (ISCED) %	
low	5	low	4
middle	78	middle	42
high	17	high	54
region %		region %	
East Germany	28	East Germany	32
West Germany	72	West Germany	68
age Ø	52	age Ø	52
wage (€/h) Ø	11	wage (€/h) Ø	13
working hours (week) Ø	39	working hours (week) Ø	40
company size %		company size %	
less than 5	6	less than 5	6
5 to 20 employees	12	5 to 20 employees	12
21 to 100 employees	22	21 to 100 employees	22
101 to 200 employees	11	101 to 200 employees	11
201 to 2000 employees	31	201 to 2000 employees	31
2000 and more	18	2000 and more	18
sector %		sector %	
agriculture & forestry	1	agriculture & forestry	1
industry	53	industry	15
handicraft	17	handicraft	6
commercial or service	21	commercial or service	46
public service	8	public service	32

Source: DEAS 2014; employees subject to social insurance contributions. Most digital occupations (>=70%): N = 174; least digitalised occupations (<30%): N = 733. Numbers rounded to integers.

Table 3: Comparison of Distributions among Different Levels of Self-Rated Health.

self-rated health	Our sample (n = 1541)	DEAS baseline sample; 40–65 years (n = 1850)
very bad	0.59%	0.70%
bad	5.66%	5.68%
middle	29.76%	29.94%
good	51.67%	52.00%
very good	12.32%	11.68%

Source: DEAS 2014.

2. Analyses

2.1. Pure Model

Table 5: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction.

job satisfaction	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		(6)		(7)		(8)	
	index		... with work as a whole		... with earnings		... with the kind of work		... with working hours		... with opp. for career development or promotion		... with opp. for further training		... with working atmosphere	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	0.009	0.068	0.092	0.077	-0.034	0.103	-0.004	0.085	0.429	0.099	0.049	0.111	-0.362	0.127	-0.020	0.093
male	-0.030	0.035	-0.047	0.041	0.123	0.053	0.011	0.044	-0.182	0.052	-0.047	0.058	-0.101	0.066	0.016	0.049
age (in years)	<0.001	0.003	0.004	0.003	<0.001	0.004	0.001	0.004	<i>0.007</i>	0.004	0.003	0.005	0.006	0.005	-0.013	0.004
West Germany	0.165	0.038	0.180	0.043	0.285	0.057	0.147	0.047	0.245	0.055	0.063	0.061	0.142	0.070	0.110	0.052
constant	3.710	0.154	3.840	0.177	3.384	0.232	4.073	0.192	3.378	0.225	3.407	0.251	3.306	0.283	4.712	0.212
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.001		0.000		0.000		0.047		0.000		0.701		0.003		0.004	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places.

Table 6: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress.

occupational stress	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)	
	index		... due to physical activities		... due to negative environmental factors		... due to tight schedules		... due to new responsibilities	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	0.106	0.080	0.381	0.122	0.810	0.126	-0.618	0.107	-0.152	0.116
male	0.051	0.041	0.007	0.063	<i>0.108</i>	0.065	0.074	0.056	0.015	0.060
age (in years)	0.001	0.003	<i>0.010</i>	0.005	-0.007	0.005	<0.001	0.005	0.002	0.005
West Germany	-0.300	0.044	-0.523	0.068	-0.314	0.070	-0.278	0.059	-0.087	0.065
constant	2.930	0.180	2.614	0.276	2.555	0.285	3.817	0.243	2.733	0.263
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.421	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places.

2.2. Composition Model

Tale 7: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction Controlled for Compositional Effects.

job satisfaction	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		(6)		(7)		(8)	
	index		... with work as a whole		... with earnings		... with the kind of work		... with working hours		... with opp. for career development or promotion		... with opp. for further training		... with working atmosphere	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	0.172	0.073	0.181	0.085	0.253	0.109	0.069	0.094	0.465	0.104	0.249	0.124	-0.109	0.144	0.103	0.104
male	<i>-0.072</i>	0.041	<i>-0.083</i>	0.048	<i>-0.062</i>	0.061	<i>-0.077</i>	0.052	0.058	0.059	-0.194	0.068	-0.169	0.078	0.013	0.058
age (in years)	0.001	0.003	0.005	0.003	<i>-0.001</i>	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.008	0.004	0.002	0.005	0.005	0.005	-0.011	0.004
West Germany	0.085	0.038	0.149	0.045	0.115	0.056	0.106	0.049	0.116	0.054	0.028	0.064	0.054	0.071	<i>0.091</i>	0.054
education (ref.: low)																
middle	0.022	0.096	-0.067	0.113	<i>-0.071</i>	0.143	<i>-0.045</i>	0.123	<i>-0.057</i>	0.138	0.208	0.160	0.145	0.184	<i>-0.048</i>	0.137
high	0.023	0.098	<i>-0.092</i>	0.116	<i>-0.079</i>	0.146	<i>-0.067</i>	0.126	0.042	0.141	0.106	0.165	0.107	0.188	0.033	0.141
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)																
industry	0.076	0.158	0.128	0.187	<i>-0.088</i>	0.235	0.064	0.203	0.092	0.228	0.149	0.265	0.048	0.311	0.189	0.225
handicraft	0.180	0.162	0.228	0.191	<i>-0.082</i>	0.240	0.110	0.207	0.241	0.233	0.308	0.271	0.082	0.320	<i>0.422</i>	0.229
commercial & service	0.078	0.155	0.171	0.183	<i>-0.144</i>	0.230	0.018	0.198	<i>-0.005</i>	0.223	0.194	0.258	0.121	0.306	0.281	0.219
public service	0.193	0.158	0.200	0.186	0.013	0.233	0.051	0.202	0.157	0.227	0.362	0.262	0.309	0.312	0.268	0.224
company size	-0.032	0.013	-0.029	0.015	0.018	0.019	<i>-0.020</i>	0.016	-0.068	0.018	-0.042	0.021	<i>-0.013</i>	0.025	-0.068	0.018
self-rated health	0.154	0.022	0.184	0.026	0.159	0.033	0.196	0.028	0.219	0.032	0.057	0.037	0.112	0.042	0.183	0.031
hourly wage (€/h)	0.032	0.004	0.016	0.005	0.060	0.006	0.019	0.005	0.025	0.006	0.035	0.007	0.038	0.007	0.016	0.006
working hours (per week)	-0.001	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.003	<i>0.004</i>	0.002	-0.029	0.003	0.011	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.001	0.003
constant	2.787	0.261	2.799	0.306	2.192	0.386	2.994	0.332	3.501	0.373	2.187	0.437	2.147	0.504	3.701	0.368
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Self-rated health: 1=low–5=high.

Table 8: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress Controlled for Compositional Effects.

occupational stress	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)	
	index		... due to physical activities		... due to negative environmental factors		... due to tight schedules		... due to new responsibilities	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	-0.034	0.086	-0.055	0.128	0.345	0.136	-0.518	0.115	0.093	0.127
male	-0.056	0.047	0.058	0.070	0.104	0.075	-0.194	0.064	-0.191	0.070
age (in years)	-0.002	0.003	0.008	0.005	-0.010	0.005	-0.004	0.004	-0.002	0.005
West Germany	-0.236	0.044	-0.369	0.066	-0.251	0.070	-0.211	0.059	<i>-0.112</i>	0.066
education (ref.: low)										
middle	-0.044	0.110	<i>-0.308</i>	0.166	-0.363	0.175	0.195	0.150	<i>0.298</i>	0.165
high	-0.142	0.113	-0.682	0.170	-0.655	0.179	0.316	0.154	0.452	0.169
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)										
industry	-0.073	0.183	-0.126	0.275	-0.389	0.289	0.171	0.246	0.052	0.272
handicraft	-0.092	0.187	0.112	0.280	-0.134	0.295	-0.151	0.252	-0.197	0.278
commercial & service	-0.217	0.179	-0.184	0.269	-0.777	0.282	0.056	0.240	0.037	0.265
public service	-0.142	0.182	-0.184	0.273	-0.592	0.287	0.081	0.245	0.125	0.270
company size	0.062	0.015	0.016	0.022	0.077	0.023	0.073	0.020	0.083	0.022
self-rated health	-0.287	0.025	-0.342	0.038	-0.273	0.040	-0.307	0.035	-0.226	0.038
hourly wage (€/h)	-0.020	0.005	-0.049	0.007	-0.036	0.007	-0.009	0.006	0.015	0.007
working hours (per week)	0.009	0.002	0.005	0.003	-0.005	0.004	0.024	0.003	0.013	0.003
constant	4.107	0.300	4.953	0.451	5.238	0.476	3.833	0.404	2.404	0.447
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Self-rated health: 1=low–5=high.

2.3. Job Insecurity Model

Table 9: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction Controlled for Job Insecurity.

job satisfaction	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		(6)		(7)		(8)	
	index		... with work as a whole		... with earnings		... with the kind of work		... with working hours		... with opp. for career development or promotion		... with opp. for further training		... with working atmosphere	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	0.188	0.072	0.198	0.084	0.266	0.108	0.081	0.093	0.473	0.104	0.274	0.122	-0.081	0.142	0.116	0.103
subj. job insecurity	-0.165	0.024	-0.180	0.028	-0.130	0.036	-0.124	0.031	-0.073	0.035	-0.248	0.040	-0.285	0.048	-0.128	0.034
male	-0.063	0.040	-0.074	0.047	-0.055	0.061	-0.071	0.052	0.061	0.059	-0.181	0.067	-0.154	0.078	0.019	0.057
age (in years)	<0.001	0.003	0.004	0.003	-0.002	0.004	0.001	0.004	<i>0.008</i>	0.004	<0.001	0.005	0.003	0.005	-0.012	0.004
West Germany	<i>0.065</i>	0.037	0.127	0.044	<i>0.099</i>	0.056	<i>0.090</i>	0.048	<i>0.107</i>	0.055	-0.003	0.063	0.019	0.071	0.076	0.054
education (ref.: low)																
middle	0.045	0.094	-0.042	0.112	-0.053	0.142	-0.028	0.123	-0.047	0.138	0.242	0.158	0.184	0.182	-0.030	0.137
high	0.052	0.097	-0.061	0.115	-0.057	0.146	-0.045	0.126	0.055	0.141	0.149	0.163	0.156	0.185	0.055	0.140
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)																
industry	0.131	0.156	0.187	0.185	-0.044	0.234	0.105	0.202	0.116	0.228	0.232	0.262	0.143	0.308	0.232	0.225
handicraft	0.201	0.160	0.251	0.189	-0.066	0.239	0.126	0.206	0.250	0.232	0.340	0.269	0.119	0.317	<i>0.438</i>	0.229
commercial & service	0.115	0.153	0.211	0.180	-0.115	0.229	0.046	0.197	0.012	0.223	0.250	0.255	0.185	0.303	0.310	0.219
public service	0.189	0.155	0.196	0.184	0.010	0.232	0.048	0.201	0.155	0.226	0.356	0.259	0.301	0.309	0.265	0.223
company size	-0.036	0.013	-0.033	0.015	0.016	0.019	-0.022	0.016	-0.070	0.018	-0.047	0.021	-0.019	0.024	-0.071	0.018
self-rated health	0.143	0.022	0.171	0.026	0.150	0.033	0.187	0.028	0.214	0.032	0.039	0.037	0.092	0.042	0.174	0.031
hourly wage (€/h)	0.029	0.004	0.012	0.005	0.058	0.006	0.017	0.005	0.023	0.006	0.030	0.007	0.032	0.007	0.014	0.006
working hours (per week)	-0.001	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.003	<i>0.004</i>	0.002	-0.029	0.003	0.011	0.003	0.002	0.004	<0.001	0.003
constant	3.174	0.262	3.221	0.309	2.496	0.393	3.286	0.338	3.673	0.381	2.769	0.444	2.817	0.508	4.002	0.374
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Self-rated health and job insecurity: 1=low–5=high.

Table 10: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress Controlled for Job Insecurity.

occupational stress	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)	
	index		... due to physical activities		... due to negative environmental factors		... due to tight schedules		... due to new responsibilities	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	-0.040	0.086	-0.060	0.128	0.336	0.136	-0.522	0.115	0.085	0.127
subj. job insecurity	0.065	0.028	0.051	0.042	0.091	0.045	0.036	0.038	<i>0.081</i>	0.042
male	-0.059	0.047	0.055	0.070	0.100	0.075	-0.196	0.064	-0.195	0.070
age (in years)	-0.002	0.003	<i>0.008</i>	0.005	<i>-0.009</i>	0.005	-0.004	0.004	-0.001	0.050
West Germany	-0.288	0.044	-0.363	0.066	-0.240	0.070	-0.207	0.059	-0.101	0.066
education (ref.: low)										
middle	-0.053	0.110	<i>-0.315</i>	0.166	-0.375	0.175	0.190	0.150	<i>0.287</i>	0.165
high	-0.154	0.113	-0.069	0.170	-0.671	0.179	0.310	0.154	0.438	0.169
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)										
industry	-0.095	0.183	-0.143	0.275	-0.420	0.289	0.159	0.247	0.025	0.272
handicraft	-0.101	0.186	0.105	0.280	-0.145	0.294	-0.155	0.252	-0.207	0.278
commercial & service	-0.232	0.179	-0.196	0.269	-0.797	0.282	0.048	0.241	0.019	0.265
public service	-0.141	0.182	-0.183	0.273	-0.590	0.287	0.082	0.245	0.128	0.270
company size	0.064	0.015	0.017	0.040	0.079	0.023	0.074	0.020	0.085	0.022
self-rated health	-0.283	0.025	-0.339	0.038	-0.267	0.040	-0.305	0.035	-0.220	0.038
hourly wage (€/h)	-0.019	0.005	-0.048	0.007	-0.034	0.007	-0.009	0.006	0.016	0.007
working hours (per week)	0.009	0.002	0.005	0.003	-0.005	0.004	0.024	0.003	0.014	0.003
constant	3.955	0.306	4.833	0.460	5.025	0.487	3.749	0.414	2.213	0.457
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Self-rated health and job insecurity: 1=low–5=high.

3. Additional Analyses

In order to check the robustness of our analyses further estimations based on model 3 (job insecurity model) have been made. We re-estimated our model (1) using clustered standard errors for occupation and (2) without controlling for self-rated health. The findings of the re-estimation with clustered standard errors is very similar to the findings of the original job insecurity model. This indicates a good quality of the imputation of missing values on the digitalisation variable. Likewise the findings of the re-estimation without the consideration of the control variable self-rated health are similar to the findings the original model. Self-rated health does not seem to vary greatly between employees in more/less digitalised occupations.

Table 11: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction with Clustered Standard Errors for Occupation.

job satisfaction	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		(6)		(7)		(8)	
	index		... with work as a whole		... with earnings		... with the kind of work		... with working hours		... with opp. for career development or promotion		... with opp. for further training		... with working atmosphere	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	<i>0.188</i>	0.096	<i>0.198</i>	0.102	0.266	0.124	0.081	0.120	0.473	0.100	0.274	0.138	-0.081	0.182	0.116	0.131
subj. job insecurity	-0.165	0.024	-0.180	0.034	-0.130	0.041	-0.124	0.033	<i>-0.073</i>	0.038	-0.248	0.042	-0.285	0.047	-0.128	0.037
male	-0.063	0.043	-0.074	0.048	-0.055	0.071	-0.071	0.057	0.061	0.062	-0.181	0.067	<i>-0.154</i>	0.082	0.019	0.051
age (in years)	<0.001	0.003	0.004	0.003	-0.002	0.004	0.001	0.004	0.008	0.004	<0.001	0.005	0.003	0.005	-0.012	0.004
West Germany	0.065	0.044	0.127	0.048	0.099	0.062	0.090	0.057	<i>0.107</i>	0.059	-0.003	0.066	0.019	0.075	0.076	0.049
education (ref.: low)																
middle	0.045	0.079	-0.042	0.116	-0.053	0.192	-0.028	0.123	-0.047	0.120	<i>0.242</i>	0.146	0.184	0.170	-0.030	0.114
high	0.052	0.085	-0.061	0.123	-0.057	0.199	-0.045	0.124	0.055	0.125	0.149	0.154	0.156	0.180	0.055	0.112
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)																
industry	0.131	0.178	0.187	0.194	-0.044	0.281	0.105	0.146	0.116	0.254	0.232	0.303	0.143	0.281	0.232	0.269
handicraft	0.201	0.176	0.251	0.186	-0.066	0.277	0.126	0.144	0.250	0.249	0.340	0.305	0.119	0.300	<i>0.438</i>	0.255
commercial & service	0.115	0.173	0.211	0.184	-0.115	0.270	0.046	0.141	0.012	0.252	0.250	0.297	0.185	0.281	0.310	0.257
public service	0.189	0.172	0.196	0.194	0.010	0.270	0.048	0.144	0.155	0.251	0.356	0.296	0.301	0.284	0.265	0.262
company size	-0.036	0.013	-0.033	0.014	0.016	0.019	-0.022	0.017	-0.070	0.016	-0.047	0.021	-0.019	0.027	-0.071	0.020
self-rated health	0.143	0.023	0.171	0.029	0.150	0.032	0.187	0.034	0.214	0.033	0.039	0.037	0.092	0.042	0.174	0.037
hourly wage (€/h)	0.029	0.005	0.012	0.005	0.058	0.008	0.017	0.005	0.023	0.006	0.030	0.007	0.032	0.007	0.014	0.006
working hours (per week)	-0.001	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.003	-0.029	0.003	0.011	0.003	0.002	0.004	<0.001	0.003
constant	3.174	0.293	3.221	0.315	2.496	0.447	3.286	0.370	3.673	0.437	2.769	0.455	2.817	0.552	4.002	0.374
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Estimations based on the job insecurity model. Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Self-rated health and job insecurity: 1=low–5=high.

Table 12: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress with Clustered Standard Errors for Occupation.

occupational stress	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)	
	index		... due to physical activities		... due to negative environmental factors		... due to tight schedules		... due to new responsibilities	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	-0.040	0.125	-0.060	0.204	0.336	0.209	-0.522	0.135	0.085	0.139
subj. job insecurity	0.065	0.027	0.051	0.042	<i>0.091</i>	0.048	0.036	0.035	0.081	0.039
male	-0.059	0.063	0.055	0.096	0.100	0.093	-0.196	0.082	-0.195	0.078
age (in years)	-0.002	0.003	0.008	0.005	-0.009	0.005	-0.004	0.005	-0.001	0.005
West Germany	-0.228	0.049	-0.363	0.062	-0.240	0.078	-0.207	0.058	-0.101	0.076
education (ref.: low)										
middle	-0.053	0.112	<i>-0.315</i>	0.166	-0.375	0.161	0.190	0.181	<i>0.287</i>	0.168
high	-0.154	0.111	-0.690	0.164	-0.671	0.177	<i>0.310</i>	0.181	0.438	0.167
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)										
industry	-0.095	0.152	-0.143	0.293	-0.420	0.298	0.159	0.224	0.025	0.250
handicraft	-0.101	0.157	0.105	0.307	-0.145	0.303	-0.155	0.231	-0.207	0.256
commercial & service	-0.232	0.149	-0.196	0.301	-0.797	0.290	0.048	0.219	0.019	0.243
public service	-0.141	0.156	-0.182	0.310	<i>-0.590</i>	0.301	0.082	0.229	0.128	0.243
company size	0.064	0.019	0.017	0.024	0.079	0.031	0.074	0.024	0.085	0.025
self-rated health	-0.283	0.024	-0.339	0.037	-0.267	0.041	-0.305	0.033	-0.220	0.043
hourly wage (€/h)	-0.019	0.004	-0.048	0.007	-0.034	0.009	-0.009	0.006	0.016	0.008
working hours (per week)	0.009	0.003	0.005	0.004	-0.005	0.004	0.024	0.003	0.014	0.003
constant	3.955	0.281	4.833	0.472	5.025	0.455	3.749	0.418	2.213	0.470
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Estimations based on the job insecurity model. Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Self-rated health and job insecurity: 1=low–5=high.

Table 13: Digitalisation and Job Satisfaction without Controlling for Self-Rated Health.

job satisfaction	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		(6)		(7)		(8)	
	index		... with work as a whole		... with earnings		... with the kind of work		... with working hours		... with opp. for career development or promotion		... with opp. for further training		... with working atmosphere	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	0.200	0.073	0.213	0.085	0.279	0.109	0.098	0.095	0.491	0.105	0.277	0.122	-0.073	0.142	0.131	0.104
subj. job insecurity	-0.177	0.024	-0.194	0.029	-0.142	0.036	-0.140	0.031	-0.091	0.035	-0.251	0.040	-0.293	0.047	-0.143	0.035
male	<i>-0.075</i>	0.040	<i>-0.087</i>	0.048	<i>-0.067</i>	0.061	<i>-0.085</i>	0.053	0.045	0.059	-0.184	0.067	-0.161	0.078	0.006	0.058
age (in years)	<i>-0.002</i>	0.003	0.002	0.003	<i>-0.004</i>	0.004	<i>-0.001</i>	0.004	0.005	0.004	<i>-0.001</i>	0.005	0.002	0.005	-0.014	0.004
West Germany	<i>0.065</i>	0.038	0.126	0.045	<i>0.099</i>	0.057	<i>0.090</i>	0.049	<i>0.107</i>	0.055	<i>-0.003</i>	0.063	0.019	0.071	0.075	0.054
education (ref.: low)																
middle	0.049	0.096	-0.037	0.113	-0.049	0.144	-0.022	0.124	-0.041	0.140	0.243	0.158	0.187	0.182	-0.026	0.138
high	0.075	0.098	-0.034	0.116	-0.033	0.147	-0.016	0.128	0.089	0.143	0.155	0.163	0.171	0.189	0.082	0.141
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)																
industry	0.175	0.159	0.241	0.188	0.002	0.235	0.163	0.205	0.182	0.232	0.244	0.262	0.172	0.308	0.286	0.227
handicraft	0.245	0.162	0.304	0.191	-0.019	0.240	0.184	0.209	0.316	0.236	0.352	0.269	0.147	0.317	0.492	0.231
commercial & service	0.158	0.155	0.263	0.183	-0.069	0.230	0.103	0.200	0.077	0.226	0.261	0.255	0.213	0.303	0.363	0.221
public service	0.229	0.157	0.244	0.186	0.051	0.234	0.101	0.204	0.215	0.230	0.367	0.259	0.327	0.308	0.313	0.225
company size	-0.036	0.013	-0.033	0.015	0.015	0.019	-0.023	0.016	-0.070	0.018	-0.047	0.021	-0.019	0.024	-0.071	0.018
hourly wage (€/h)	0.031	0.004	0.014	0.005	0.060	0.006	0.019	0.005	0.026	0.006	0.031	0.007	0.033	0.007	0.016	0.006
working hours (per week)	-0.001	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.003	<i>0.005</i>	0.002	-0.029	0.003	0.011	0.003	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.003
constant	3.735	0.252	3.894	0.375	3.086	0.375	4.022	0.324	4.513	0.366	3.179	0.420	3.179	0.484	4.686	0.358
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Job insecurity: 1=low–5=high.

Table 14: Digitalisation and Occupational Stress without Controlling for Self-Rated Health.

occupational stress	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)	
	index		... due to physical activities		... due to negative environmental factors		... due to tight schedules		... due to new responsibilities	
	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE	b	SE
digitalisation	-0.065	0.089	-0.089	0.131	0.313	0.138	-0.548	0.118	0.066	0.128
subj. job insecurity	0.089	0.029	<i>0.079</i>	0.043	0.113	0.045	0.061	0.039	0.100	0.043
male	-0.037	0.049	0.082	0.072	0.121	0.076	-0.172	0.065	-0.178	0.071
age (in years)	0.002	0.003	0.013	0.005	-0.006	0.005	<0.001	0.004	0.002	0.005
West Germany	-0.288	0.046	-0.363	0.068	-0.240	0.071	-0.206	0.061	-0.101	0.066
education (ref.: low)										
middle	-0.182	0.115	<i>-0.324</i>	0.171	-0.383	0.178	0.182	0.154	<i>0.281</i>	0.167
high	<i>-0.198</i>	0.118	-0.744	0.175	-0.723	0.182	<i>0.262</i>	0.158	0.403	0.171
sector (ref.: agriculture & forestry)										
industry	-0.182	0.190	-0.248	0.283	<i>-0.502</i>	0.293	0.064	0.253	-0.043	0.275
handicraft	-0.188	0.194	0.001	0.288	-0.228	0.298	-0.250	0.258	-0.275	0.280
commercial & service	<i>-0.317</i>	0.186	-0.299	0.276	-0.878	0.286	-0.045	0.247	-0.048	0.268
public service	-0.220	0.189	-0.277	0.281	-0.664	0.291	-0.003	0.251	0.066	0.273
company size	0.064	0.015	0.018	0.023	0.079	0.024	0.075	0.021	0.085	0.022
hourly wage (€/h)	-0.022	0.005	-0.053	0.007	-0.037	0.008	<i>-0.013</i>	0.007	<i>0.014</i>	0.007
working hours (per week)	0.009	0.002	0.005	0.003	-0.005	0.004	0.023	0.003	0.013	0.003
constant	2.844	0.301	3.501	0.446	3.977	0.466	2.551	0.401	1.347	0.437
observations	1541		1541		1541		1541		1541	
prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Source: DEAS 2014. Notes: Coefficients are unstandardised partial regression slopes. Significant estimates ($p < 0.05$) in bold; estimates with $p < 0.1$ in italics. Rounded to three decimal places. Job insecurity: 1=low–5=high.

4. Hypotheses

Table 15: Overview of all Formulated Hypotheses and Related Results.

Higher degrees of digitalisation in the employees occupation				Higher degrees of digitalisation in the employees occupation			
1. Pure Model		Hypothesis	Finding	2. Compositional Model		Hypothesis	Finding
H1.1	job satisfaction index	-	n.s.	H3.1	job satisfaction index	+	+
H1.2	job satisfaction as a whole	-	n.s.	H3.2	job satisfaction as a whole	+	+
H1.a	job satisfaction with opportunities for further training	-	-	H3.a	job satisfaction with opportunities for further training	-	n.s.
	job satisfaction with working hours	e	+	H3.b	job satisfaction with working hours	+	+
	job satisfaction with the working atmosphere	e	n.s.	H3.c	job satisfaction with the working atmosphere	+	n.s.
	job satisfaction with the kind of work	e	n.s.	H3.d	job satisfaction with the kind of work	+	n.s.
	job satisfaction with earnings	e	n.s.		job satisfaction with earnings	e	+
	job satisfaction with career development and promotion	e	n.s.		job satisfaction with career development and promotion	e	+
H2	occupational stress index	+	n.s.	H4	occupational stress index	-	n.s.
H2.a	occupational stress due to physical work	+	+	H4.a	occupational stress due to physical work	-	n.s.
H2.b	occupational stress due to negative environmental factors	+	+	H4.b	occupational stress due to negative environmental factors	-	+
	occupational stress due to tight schedules	e	-	H4.c	occupational stress due to tight schedules	+	-
	occupational stress due to new responsibilities	e	n.s.	H4.d	occupational stress due to new responsibilities	+	n.s.

Higher degrees of digitalisation in the employees occupation				Higher degrees of subjective job insecurity			
3. Job Insecurity Model		Hypothesis	Finding	3. Job Insecurity Model		Hypothesis	Finding
H5.1	job satisfaction index	+	+	H7.1	job satisfaction index	-	-
H5.2	job satisfaction as a whole	+	+	H7.2	job satisfaction as a whole	-	-
H5.a	job satisfaction with opportunities for further training	-	n.s.	H7.a	job satisfaction with opportunities for further training	-	-
H5.b	job satisfaction with working hours	+	+	H7.b	job satisfaction with working hours	-	-
H5.c	job satisfaction with the working atmosphere	+	n.s.	H7.c	job satisfaction with the working atmosphere	-	-
H5.d	job satisfaction with the kind of work	+	n.s.	H7.d	job satisfaction with the kind of work	-	-
	job satisfaction with earnings	e	+	H7.e	job satisfaction with earnings	-	-
	job satisfaction with career development and promotion	e	+	H7.f	job satisfaction with career development and promotion	-	-
H6	occupational stress index	-	n.s.	H8	occupational stress index	+	+
H6.a	occupational stress due to physical work	-	n.s.	H8.a	occupational stress due to physical work	+	n.s.
H6.b	occupational stress due to negative environmental factors	-	+	H8.b	occupational stress due to negative environmental factors	+	+
H6.c	occupational stress due to tight schedules	+	-	H8.c	occupational stress due to tight schedules	+	n.s.
H6.d	occupational stress due to new responsibilities	+	n.s.	H8.d	occupational stress due to new responsibilities	+	(+)

Note: e = exploratory approach; +/- positive/negative association (significant with $p < 0.05$); (+)/(-) positive/negative association (significant with $p < 0.1$); n.s. not significant. Bold letters indicate that the hypotheses was confirmed by our findings.

III. Supplemental Material – Paper 3

Digitalization in Occupations and Self-perceptions of Aging of Older Workers

Authors: Lisa Katharina Kortmann, Georg Henning, Oliver Huxhold

1.	Additional Analyses Using the ATOA Subscale for General Self-Perceptions of Aging.....	191
	<i>Tab. 1a: Basic Model – Estimated Parameters for the Basic Model Assessing General Self Perceptions of Aging of Workers Aged 40–65 Years.....</i>	<i>191</i>
	<i>Tab. 2a: Analysis Model – Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing General Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers (ATOA).....</i>	<i>192</i>
2.	Robustness Checks.....	193
	<i>Tab. 3a: Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, Subsample: No Professional Change Between T1 and T2.....</i>	<i>193</i>
	<i>Tab. 4a: Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, Subsample: Workers aged 50 to 65.....</i>	<i>194</i>
	<i>Tab. 5a: Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, controlling for training participation.....</i>	<i>195</i>
	<i>Tab. 6a: Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, not controlling for SRH.....</i>	<i>196</i>
3.	Item Formulations.....	197
	<i>Tab. 2a: Items – Domain Specific and General Self-Perceptions of Aging.....</i>	<i>197</i>

1. Additional Analyses Using the ATOA Subscale for General Self-Perceptions of Aging

Table 3a: Basic Model – Estimated Parameters for the Basic Model Assessing General Self-Perceptions of Aging of Workers Aged 40–65 Years.

	<i>Level</i> b (SE)	<u>ATOA</u>	<i>Change</i> b (SE)
Mean	3.071* (0.01)		-0.002 (0.01)
Variances	0.255* (0.01)		0.200* (0.01)
$\chi^2(1)$	0.000*		p = 0.000
Akaike (AIC)		5,265.14	
Bayesian (BIC)		5,294.63	

Notes: 1a. FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2017.; n = 2,690. Δ = change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). Significance Level: * = p < 0.05.

Table 4a: Analysis Model – Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing General Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers (ATOA).

	<i>ATOA</i>	
	<i>Level</i> <i>b (SE)</i>	<i>Change</i> <i>b (SE)</i>
Intercept	3.042* (0.02)	1.287* (0.09)
Autoregression	-	-0.437* (0.03)
Digitalization Level (DL)	0.002* (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)
Change in DL	-	0.003 (0.00)
Gender (male = 1)	-0.069* (0.02)	0.002 (0.02)
Age	-0.000 (0.00)	-0.004 (0.00)
Region (west = 1)	0.037 (0.02)	0.001 (0.02)
Education (high =1)	0.073* (0.02)	-0.013 (0.02)
Self-Rated Health	0.221* (0.01)	0.051* (0.02)
Observations		2,722
$\chi^2(1)$	2.857*	p = 0.091
RMSEA (90% CI)	0.026	p = 0.821
SRMR		0.004
CFI		0.998
Akaike (AIC)		80,694.94
Bayesian (BIC)		81,008.12

Notes: 2a. FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2017; $n_{2014} = 2,722$. Change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). SE = Standard Errors. Variables digitalization level, age and self-rated health are centred at grand mean. Significance Levels: * = $p < 0.05$, italic: $p < 0.1$.

2. Robustness Checks

Subsample – No Professional Change

Table 5a. Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, Subsample: No Professional Change Between T1 and T2.

	Physical Losses		Social Losses		Ongoing Development		Self-Knowledge	
	Level <i>b</i> (SE)	Change <i>b</i> (SE)						
Intercept	2.378*	0.956*	3.241*	1.210*	2.988*	1.003*	3.048*	1.456*
Autoregression	–	-0.393*	–	-0.370*	–	-0.354*	–	-0.481*
Digitalization Level (DL)	-0.001 (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)
Change in DL	–	0.001 (0.00)	–	0.001 (0.00)	–	0.003 (0.00)	–	0.002 (0.00)
Gender (male = 1)	-0.056 (0.03)	-0.022 (0.03)	0.038 (0.03)	-0.035 (0.02)	-0.050 (0.03)	0.026 (0.02)	-0.057* (0.03)	-0.036 (0.02)
Age	0.002 (0.00)	0.002 (0.00)	0.002 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	-0.004 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	-0.002 (0.00)	0.004* (0.00)
Region (west = 1)	0.005 (0.03)	-0.041 (0.03)	-0.054 (0.03)	-0.009 (0.03)	0.111* (0.03)	0.020 (0.02)	0.014 (0.03)	0.030 (0.03)
Education (high =1)	-0.029 (0.03)	-0.019 (0.03)	0.059* (0.03)	0.002 (0.03)	0.099* (0.03)	0.031 (0.03)	-0.012* (0.03)	-0.029 (0.02)
Self-Rated Health	0.238* (0.02)	0.071* (0.02)	0.090* (0.02)	0.037* (0.02)	0.125* (0.02)	0.027 (0.02)	0.084 (0.02)	0.030* (0.02)
$\chi^2(1)$	0.301*	p = 0.583	0.342*	0.559	1.613*	p = 0.204	0.407*	p = 0.524
RMSEA (90% CI)	0.000	p = 0.882	0.000	p = 0.874	0.023	p = 0.658	0.000	p = 0.860
SRMR		0.002		0.003		0.007		0.002
CFI		1.000		1.000		0.999		1.000
Akaike (AIC)		33,475.16		33,476.31		33,267.19		32,897.60
Bayesian (BIC)		33,741.18		33,742.33		33,533.21		33,163.62

Notes: 3a. FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2017; $N_{2014} = 1,118$. Change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). SE = Standard Errors. Variables digitalization level, age and self-rated health are centred at grand mean. Significance Levels: * = $p < 0.05$, italic: $p < 0.1$.

Subsample of 50 to 65-years Old Workers

Table 6a. Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, Subsample: Workers aged 50 to 65.

	Physical Losses		Social Losses		Ongoing Development		Self-Knowledge	
	Level <i>b</i> (SE)	Change <i>b</i> (SE)						
Intercept	2.354*	1.039*	3.252*	1.215*	2.953*	1.049*	3.035*	1.399*
Autoregression	-	-0.408*	-	-0.373*	-	-0.357*	-	-0.458*
Digitalization Level (DL)	-0.001 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.003* (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)
Change in DL	-	-0.002 (0.00)	-	0.001 (0.00)	-	0.001 (0.00)	-	0.003 (0.00)
Gender (male = 1)	-0.063* (0.02)	-0.034 (0.03)	-0.017 (0.02)	-0.020 (0.02)	-0.066* (0.02)	0.014 (0.02)	-0.085* (0.03)	-0.043 (0.03)
Age	0.003 (0.00)	-0.004 (0.00)	-0.001 (0.00)	0.002 (0.00)	-0.004 (0.00)	-0.003 (0.00)	-0.003 (0.00)	-0.001 (0.00)
Region (west = 1)	0.006 (0.02)	-0.028 (0.03)	-0.074* (0.02)	-0.002 (0.03)	0.126* (0.03)	0.027 (0.02)	0.012 (0.03)	0.023 (0.03)
Education (high =1)	0.001 (0.02)	-0.033 (0.03)	0.061* (0.02)	0.005 (0.03)	0.147* (0.02)	0.030 (0.03)	0.028 (0.02)	-0.023 (0.03)
Self-Rated Health	0.219* (0.01)	0.086* (0.02)	0.099* (0.01)	0.024 (0.02)	0.114* (0.02)	0.010 (0.02)	0.062* (0.02)	0.015 (0.02)
$\chi^2(1)$	0.270*	p = 0.603	0.026*	p = 0.871	0.678*	p = 0.410	0.089*	p = 0.765
RMSEA (90% CI)	0.000	p = 0.960	0.000	p = 0.989	0.000	p = 0.922	0.000	p = 0.979
SRMR		0.002		0.001		0.003		0.001
CFI		1.000		1.000		1.000		1.000
Akaike (AIC)		57,774.75		57,895.09		57,648.70		57,167.93
Bayesian (BIC)		58,071.49		58,191.83		57,945.44		57,464.67

Notes: 4a. FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2017; $n_{2014} = 1,996$. Change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). SE = Standard Errors. Variables digitalization level, age and self-rated health are centred at grandmean. Significance Levels: * = $p < 0.05$, italic: $p < 0.1$.

Controlling for Participation in Further Training

Table 7a. Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, controlling for training participation.

	Physical Losses		Social Losses		Ongoing Development		Self-Knowledge	
	Level <i>b</i> (SE)	Change <i>b</i> (SE)						
Intercept	2.393* (0.04)	1.085* (0.08)	3.296* (0.04)	1.261* (0.10)	3.166* (0.04)	1.177* (0.09)	3.074* (0.04)	1.482* (0.11)
Autoregression	-	-0.398* (0.02)		-0.381* (0.02)		-0.370* (0.03)		-0.467* (0.03)
Digitalization Level (DL)	0.000 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002* (0.00)
Change in DL	-	-0.001 (0.00)		0.002 (0.00)		0.002 (0.00)		0.002 (0.00)
Gender (male = 1)	-0.043* (0.02)	-0.014 (0.02)	0.009 (0.02)	-0.033 (0.02)	-0.058* (0.02)	0.021 (0.02)	-0.061* (0.02)	-0.043* (0.02)
Age	0.003 (0.00)		0.001 (0.00)	0.001 (0.00)	-0.002 (0.00)	-0.002 (0.00)	0.000 (0.00)	0.002 (0.00)
Region (west = 1)	0.006 (0.02)	-0.030 (0.02)	-0.045* (0.02)	-0.026 (0.03)	0.070* (0.02)	-0.006 (0.02)	0.003 (0.02)	0.011 (0.03)
Education (high =1)	-0.023 (0.02)	-0.048* (0.02)	0.052* (0.02)	-0.005 (0.02)	0.093* (0.02)	0.009 (0.02)	0.011 (0.02)	-0.032 (0.02)
Self-Rated Health	0.216* (0.01)	0.071* (0.02)	0.098* (0.01)	0.034* (0.01)	0.127* (0.01)	0.033 (0.02)	0.076* (0.01)	0.023 (0.01)
Training	-0.024 (0.02)	-0.067* (0.03)	-0.055* (0.02)	-0.013 (0.03)	-0.132* (0.02)	-0.060* (0.03)	-0.030 (0.02)	-0.034 (0.02)
$\chi^2(1)$	0.059*	<i>p</i> = 0.808	0.150*	<i>p</i> = 0.698	0.467*	<i>p</i> = 0.495	0.155*	<i>p</i> = 0.694
RMSEA (90% CI)	0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.993	0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.988	0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.973	0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.988
SRMR	0.001		0.001		0.002		0.001	
CFI	1.000		1.000		1.000		1.000	
Akaike (AIC)	84,104.13		84,112.01		83,783.50		83,144.19	
Bayesian (BIC)	84,482.32		84,490.28		84,161.68		83,522.37	

Notes: 5a. FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2017; $n_{2014} = 2,722$. Change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). SE = Standard Errors. Variables digitalization level, age and self-rated health are centred at grand mean. Significance Levels: * = $p < 0.05$, italic: $p < 0.1$.

Not Controlling for Self-Rated Health

Table 8a. Estimated Parameters for the Latent Change Score Model Assessing Domain Specific Self-Perceptions of Aging of Older Workers, not controlling for SRH.

	Physical Losses		Social Losses		Ongoing Development		Self-Knowledge	
	Level <i>b</i> (SE)	Change <i>b</i> (SE)						
Intercept	2.340*	0.899*	3.211*	1.214*	2.970*	1.037*	3.025*	1.406*
Autoregression	-	-0.364*	-	-0.373*	-	-0.354*	-	-0.459*
Digitalization Level (DL)	0.001	0.000	0.002*	0.001	0.002*	0.002*	0.000	0.002*
Change in DL	-	-0.001	-	0.002	-	0.003	-	0.003
Gender (male = 1)	-0.054*	-0.012	0.004	-0.034	-0.065*	0.021	-0.065*	-0.043*
Age	-0.001	-0.002	-0.001	0.000	-0.004*	-0.002	-0.002	0.001
Region (west = 1)	0.017	-0.026	-0.038	-0.024	0.080*	-0.004	0.008	0.014
Education (high =1)	0.016	-0.026	0.080*	0.001	0.145*	0.024	0.030	-0.022
Self-Rated Health	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\chi^2(1)$	0.193*	p = 0.660	0.805*	p = 0.370	1.877*	p = 0.171	0.672*	p = 0.413
RMSEA (90% CI)	0.000	p = 0.986	0.000	p = 0.957	0.018	p = 0.892	0.000	p = 0.964
SRMR		0.002		0.003		0.005		0.002
CFI		1.000		1.000		0.999		1.000
Akaike (AIC)		75,041.17		74,804.54		74,561.55		73,818.63
Bayesian (BIC)		75,295.27		75,058.63		74,815.64		74,072.72

Notes: 6a. FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014 and FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2017; $n_{2014} = 2,722$. Change between T1 (2014) and T2 (2017). SE = Standard Errors. Variables digitalization level, age and self-rated health are centred at grand mean. Significance Levels: * = $p < 0.05$, italic: $p < 0.1$.

3. Item Formulations

Table 9a: Items – Domain Specific and General Self-Perceptions of Aging.

<i>AgeCog Scales</i>	
Aging means to me, that... / For me, getting older means that...	
<i>Physical losses</i>	<i>Ongoing development^a</i>
... I am less energetic and fit	... I continue to make plans
... I am less healthy	... my capabilities are increasing
... I cannot make up for my physical losses	... I can still learn new things
... I cannot take as much on as before	... I can still put my ideas into practice
<i>Social losses</i>	<i>Self-knowledge^a</i>
...I feel less needed	...I can deal with my physical weaknesses better
...I feel lonely more often	...I know myself better
...I feel less respected	...I am more relaxed about a lot of things
...I am bored more often	...I have a better idea of what I want
Answer scale	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Disagree 4. Strongly disagree 	
<i>ATOA Subscale</i>	
Things keep getting worse as I get older. I have as much pep as I had last year. ^a As you get older, you are less useful. As I get older, things are better than I thought they would be. ^a I am as happy now as when I was younger. ^a	

Note: Item formulations according to DEAS instrument 2014 (*FDZ-DZA, SUF DEAS 2014*).

^a Answer scale inverted, such high values indicate more positive self-perceptions of aging.

8. Abstract / Zusammenfassung

Abstract: As digitalization continues to transform the world of work, understanding its implications for older workers is crucial. This publication-based dissertation comprises three papers that delve into the ramifications of digitalization on older workers in Germany. Drawing from data of the German Ageing Survey enriched by digitalization data on the occupational level, this dissertation investigates the multifaceted relationships between digitalization, training behavior, subjective job quality, and self-perceptions of aging among workers in the second half of their working lives. In the first paper, the association between training behavior and the extent of digitalization in occupations is explored. Findings reveal positive associations between changes in the level of digitalization in occupations and training participation. Notably, gender differences in training participation are identified, with female employees working in occupations that experienced a strong digitalization boost over the last years potentially facing disadvantages compared to their male counterparts. The second paper shifts the focus to subjective job quality, examining how digitalization impacts various dimensions of job satisfaction and perceived occupational stress among older employees. Findings indicate that while digitalization generally seems to enhance job satisfaction, it can also lead to increased stress in certain aspects of work, such as tight schedules and negative environmental conditions. The third paper investigates, how digitalization in occupations influences older workers' self-perceptions of aging. Latent change score models are employed to explore changes in self-perceptions of aging across domains such as physical and social losses, ongoing development, and self-knowledge. Remarkably, higher levels of digitalization in occupations are associated with positive shifts in self-perceptions of aging, particularly in domains related to ongoing development and self-knowledge. Overall, this dissertation contributes to a better understanding of how older workers fare in digitalizing occupations. By illuminating the complexities of training participation, job quality, and self-perceptions of aging in the context of digital transformation, this research contributes valuable insights to inform policies and practices aimed at supporting older workers in an increasingly digitalized world of work.

Zusammenfassung: Da die Digitalisierung weiterhin die Arbeitswelt transformiert, ist es wichtig, ihre Auswirkungen auf ältere Erwerbstätige zu verstehen. Diese publikationsbasierte Dissertation besteht aus drei Artikeln, die sich mit den Auswirkungen der Digitalisierung auf ältere Erwerbstätige in Deutschland befassen. Gestützt auf Daten des Deutschen Alterssurveys und Digitalisierungsdaten auf Berufsebene, untersucht diese Dissertation die vielschichtigen Beziehungen zwischen Digitalisierung, Weiterbildungsverhalten, Arbeitsqualität und Selbstwahrnehmung des Alter(n)s bei Erwerbstätigen in der zweiten Hälfte ihres Arbeitslebens. Im ersten Artikel wird der Zusammenhang zwischen Weiterbildungsverhalten und dem Ausmaß der Digitalisierung in Berufen untersucht. Die Ergebnisse zeigen positive Zusammenhänge zwischen Veränderungen im Digitalisierungsgrad in Berufen und der Teilnahme an Weiterbildungen auf. Es werden Geschlechtsunterschiede in der Weiterbildungsteilnahme identifiziert, wobei weibliche Arbeitnehmer, in Berufen, die in den letzten Jahren einen starken Digitalisierungsschub erlebt haben, im Vergleich zu ihren männlichen Kollegen möglicherweise benachteiligt sind. Der zweite Artikel beleuchtet die subjektive Arbeitsqualität und untersucht, wie die Digitalisierung verschiedene Dimensionen der Arbeitszufriedenheit und des wahrgenommenen beruflichen Stresses bei älteren Arbeitnehmern beeinflusst. Die Ergebnisse deuten darauf hin, dass die Digitalisierung zwar mit einer Verbesserung der allgemeinen Arbeitszufriedenheit einhergeht, aber auch mit erhöhtem Stress in bestimmten Arbeitsbereichen, wie beispielsweise mit Stress durch enge Zeitpläne oder negative Umweltbedingungen. Der dritte Artikel untersucht, wie die Digitalisierung in Berufen die Selbstwahrnehmung des Alter(n)s älterer Arbeitnehmer beeinflusst. Mittels Latent Change Score Modelle werden Veränderungen in der Selbstwahrnehmung des Alter(n)s in den Bereichen physische und soziale Verluste, kontinuierliche Entwicklung und Selbstkenntnis zu untersucht. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass höhere Digitalisierungsgrade in Berufen mit positiven Veränderungen in den Bereichen kontinuierliche Entwicklung und Selbstkenntnis voranzugehen scheinen. Insgesamt trägt diese Dissertation dazu bei, ein besseres Verständnis für die Situation älterer Erwerbstätiger im Kontext der Digitalisierung zu gewinnen. Zudem beleuchtet diese Arbeit die Komplexitäten von Weiterbildungsteilnahme, Arbeitsqualität und der Selbstwahrnehmung des Alter(n)s im Kontext der Digitalisierung und stellt so eine wertvolle Grundlage für Politik und Praxis da, die darauf abzielen, ältere Erwerbstätige in einer zunehmend digitalisierten Arbeitswelt zu unterstützen.

9. Acknowledgement / Danksagung

Auf meinem Promotionsweg wurde ich von zahlreichen Menschen unterstützt und begleitet. Ich wurde ermutigt die Reise anzutreten, es wurde an mich geglaubt, dass ich den Weg gehen kann, es wurde Vertrauen in mich gesetzt, dass ich Kopf und Kraft habe ans Ziel zu kommen. Mir wurde gezeigt, wie man diesen Weg geht und mir wurde der Rücken gestärkt, wenn es mal schwierig wurde. Und nicht zuletzt haben mich viele liebe Menschen begleitet und ein Stück vergessen lassen, wie lang und mühsam der Weg manchmal sein konnte.

Ein grosser Dank geht an Claudia Vogel, ohne deren Anruf im Frühjahr 2018 ich mich vielleicht nie auf den Weg begeben hätte. Ausserdem möchte ich mich auch besonders bei Oliver Huxhold und Julia Simonson für die guten Ratschläge, die kritischen Fragen und die offenen Ohren und Augen während meines Promotionsweges bedanken.

Den ehemaligen Kolleginnen und Kollegen vom DZA danke ich für das grosse Vertrauen, welches mir von Anfang an entgegengebracht worden ist, die Unterstützung, die Gespräche und die Kaffeepausen. Vielen Dank: Clemens Tesch-Römer, Georg Henning, Stefan Stuth, Alberto Lozano-Alcántara, Svenja Spuling, Ulrike Ehrlich, Stefanie Hartmann, Laura Romeo-Gordo, Daniela Klaus, Mareike Bünning, Michael Weinhardt, Jenna Wünsche und alle weiteren.

Und zuletzt natürlich noch ein Dankeschön an all meine anderen lieben Wegbegleiterinnen und Wegbegleiter: An meine Familie, meine Freunde und an Simon.

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Statement of authorship

Ich erkläre ausdrücklich, dass es sich bei der von mir eingereichten Arbeit um eine von mir selbstständig und ohne fremde Hilfe verfasste Arbeit handelt.

I expressly declare that the work I have submitted was written independently and without external help.

Ich erkläre ausdrücklich, dass ich sämtliche in der oben genannten Arbeit verwendeten fremden Quellen, auch aus dem Internet (einschließlich Tabellen, Grafiken u. Ä.) als solche kenntlich gemacht habe. Insbesondere bestätige ich, dass ich ausnahmslos sowohl bei wörtlich übernommenen Aussagen bzw. unverändert übernommenen Tabellen, Grafiken o. Ä. (Zitaten) als auch bei in eigenen Worten wiedergegebenen Aussagen bzw. von mir abgewandelten Tabellen, Grafiken o.Ä. anderer Autorinnen und Autoren die Quelle angegeben habe.

I expressly declare that all sources used in the abovementioned work – including those from the Internet (including tables, graphic and suchlike) – have been marked as such. In particular, I declare that I have, without exception, stated the source for any statements quoted verbatim and/or unmodified tables, graphics etc. (i.e. quotations) of other authors.

Mir ist bewusst, dass Verstöße gegen die Grundsätze der Selbstständigkeit als Täuschung betrachtet und entsprechend geahndet werden.

I am aware that violations against the principles of academic independence are considered deception and are punished accordingly.

Datum

date

Unterschrift Doktorand/in

signature of doctoral student